

**Assessing Child Rights in Mega Sporting Events: A case study of
Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games**

By

Oluwaseyi Ifeoluwa Aina

School of Business and Creative Industries

University of the West of Scotland

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Abstract

Bidding to host mega sporting events has become increasingly popular, over the years. Recently, however, there has been an increasing interest in mega sporting events and its ability to infringe on child rights, even more so, in the inability of mega sporting events organizers to ensure that children and their rights are sufficiently safeguarded and provided for. In the context of the Olympics, records of violations associated with children have grown in the past 10 years, including trafficking, child labour, exploitation. In response to the issues of child rights infringement in the Olympics, event organizers have tried to create human rights safeguarding plans for these events by working with local organising committees and Non – Government Organizations such as the United Nations (UN), Amnesty International, Centre for Sports and Human Rights. However, child rights commitments are yet to be fully embraced and represented in Olympic Games policies. Using a single case study, I explore child rights in the Olympic Games while discussing the theoretical debates about child rights infringements, protection and participation strategies in sporting events, using past records in the Olympic Games. In addressing the aim and research questions, a qualitative approach was adopted, including documentary analysis of seventeen Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games documents and published guidelines, looking for child rights specifics and seven semi structured interviews. I then present the findings, which evidenced that there were no intentionalities about child rights protection in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, mainly because there was a lack of leadership structure and recognition for the child and his rights at the preparation phase of the event. In conclusion, I argue for the importance of recognizing children as right bearers, embedding child rights specificities in policies guiding each Olympic Games edition, while also emphasizing the need for key actors of the Olympic Games such as the IOC's intentionality in ensuring that child rights provisions move from policies to implementation.

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List of Abbreviations

UNICEF United Nations Children's Fund

TOCOG Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee

LOC Local Organising Committee

JOC Japanese Olympic Committee

OCGC Office of Commonwealth Games Coordination

IOC	International Organising Committee
CSHR	Centre for Sports and Human Rights
HRW	Human Rights Watch
IDHR	International Declaration of Human Rights
NGO	Non-Governmental Organizations
UNCRC	United Nations Conventions on the Rights of the Child
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
OC	Olympic Charter
HCC	Host City Contract
JHRCP	Japan Human Rights Commitment and Pledges
UNGPBHR	UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights.

CHAPTER ONE - INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

Child rights studies have been low on the priority list of discourses in the general sporting events terrain, and in the specific context of mega sporting events, despite of the continual violations of children directly and indirectly linked to these events (see Heerdt, 2018; Chappelet, 2018; Fortier and Lessard, 2020; Talbot, 2022). Donnelly (2008) argues that child rights is one of the branches of human rights which continues to be neglected in sporting events, thereby causing a recurring phenomenon of child rights violations. Providing a reason for this recurring phenomenon, Aina, McGillivray, Carnicelli and McPherson (2021) have argued that the absence of child rights specifics in the strategies prepared, to govern the Olympic Games delivery is one reason why violations occur. However, there remains a research gap in terms of why and how child rights have continued to be unrepresented in policies guiding mega sporting events. Using Tokyo 2020 as case study, in this thesis, I assess child rights in mega sporting events, focusing on what provision already exists to strengthen protection, and how children participate, and are represented in planning and decision-making processes.

In this opening chapter, I provide a background and rationale for studying human rights in the context of mega sporting events, and specifically the topic of child rights. After setting out the study background, a brief introduction to the field of human rights is undertaken before child rights and their linkage to mega sporting events is provided. In both sections, I draw on examples of child rights infringements at the Olympic Games to illustrate the importance and relevance of the study. This then provides the basis of an in-depth discussion of human rights, child rights and mega sporting events in the literature review chapters (chapter two, three and four). Finally, in this chapter, I outline the aims and objectives of this study, describe the thesis structure and outline my contribution to knowledge.

1.2. Study Background

In the past thirty years, sport has made a noticeable progress, particularly mega sporting events, in the way they are organized and used to achieve arrays of benefits (Grix and Houlihan, 2014). According to several studies (see Fourie and Santana- Gallego, 2011; Horne, 2007), the reasons most countries and cities bid for these events have evolved. Countries no longer bid just to host, generate international recognition, and facilitate urban regeneration processes. Amongst other reasons, countries now bid as a way of generating economic, social and cultural outcomes (Foley, McGillivray and McPherson, 2012). In addition, nations bid to combat societal ills (Kidd, 2008), while also aiming to secure a spot on the world map of recognition.

In situating this study, it is pertinent to outline what a mega sporting event is, as this concept and context (Toyko 2020) underpins the remainder of the thesis. As evidenced in academic literature, there is yet to be an agreed definition for mega sporting events because mega events are much discussed but rarely defined (Muller, 2015). In making a distinction between mega events and other events, however, Hiller (2010) argues that the difference is that of size. Similarly, Muller (2015) also notes that mega sporting events can be defined based on size – sporting events which are larger than regular events and attract large scale media focus. Malfas, Houlihan and Theodoraki (2004), on the other hand, argue that mega events can be defined by their impacts and complexity in terms of organization and delivery. Some events are also defined by the significance of their impacts, opening debate about the level of impact a sporting event needs to have for it to be qualified as mega. According to Collins, Jones and Munday (2009), the practical issue surrounding accessing events by impact is that the techniques seeking to assess them are likely to be partial in scope. Applying the aforementioned factors, this study argues that mega sporting events can be classed and defined based on their size, media attention generated and the level of impact they have.

Some scholars have argued that legacy is another significant factor, which distinguishes mega sporting events from others. This, however, according to Collins, Jones and Munday (2009), is influenced by complexities in organization and delivery. As Collins et al (2009) explain, in defining mega sporting events by complexity in organization and delivery, the legacies, outcomes (positive and negative) and the size of the event tend to be determined by the complexity in its planning, bid processes and delivery - an assessment which might also be inaccurate and solely viewed from a singular perspective. Similarly, Girginov (2011) argues that complexity in planning is another crucial factor in defining mega sporting events. They use the London 2012 Olympic Games to demonstrate the strategic planning involved, explaining that there was complexity in its organization and delivery. Even though Raco (2012) argued that complexity is not an influential factor in the delivery of mega sporting events, noting that what is more important is the delivery, drawing on Collins et al's (2009) definition of complexity and delivery being a factor, the Olympic Games is a mega sporting event, as most Olympic Games are complex in nature. And this complexity, sometimes, influences how they are delivered (Raco, 2012).

Bidding is an important aspect of mega sporting events. It is also one of the major factors that determine the outcomes of every mega sporting event. Bidding is relevant to this study because this study is about assessing child rights in mega sporting events. And consequently, child rights in the planning stage would be assessed for this study's outcome. According to Foley et al (2012) the delivery, impact and outcome of mega sporting events, in most cases, is dependent on the host city and country's bidding processes (which could go on for months, sometimes years). This includes the potency of deliberations between the organising committees and awarding bodies for each event. Similarly, having a successful bid to organize a mega sporting event is much more dependent on the aims and objectives of the bidding host communities. Often, the aims and expected outcomes of bidding for mega sporting events differ from the delivery outcomes. For

instance, positive social, cultural and physical impacts are usually planned for, while negatives outcomes occur, even when they are unplanned for. While Foley et al (2012) argue that delivery is the most important aspect of the Olympic Games, Aina et al (2021) have argued that the planning stage should not be neglected, as most of the negative impacts of mega sporting events happen due to lack of adequate planning.

Adopting Roches(2000), cited by Horne (2022), mega sporting events are a broad and comprehensive event, which plays a substantial function, has a wide acceptance rate and is relevant internationally. These characteristics, to an extent, explain the reason why cities are drawn to it, despite the controversies and supposed danger to intending host cities or nations (Horne, 2022). Whether related to bidding, planning, delivery or legacy, there has been an increase in the contestations surrounding mega sporting events, especially around the potentially deleterious effects physically, socio-economically, and socio-culturally (Malfas et al. 2004; Manzenreiter and Horne, 2016). The past ten years, especially, have seen these controversies come to the public's attention with human rights violations being brought to light by academics, non-governmental organizations and advocacy groups. According to Manzenrieter and Horne (2016), the social forces unleashed by mega sporting events and their capabilities to impact social life often develop as a result of the pursuit of intended impacts. They go on to argue that some violations of rights such as non-payment of wages, and displacement, can be recorded as unintended impacts of mega sporting events, as they most usually happen in the pursuit of intended impacts like generating and building enough facilities for a successful mega sporting event. In the same vein, Horne (2017) has observed that some of these impacts are as a result of policy deficiencies, corroborating Aina et al's (2021) argument about the impact of policy deficiencies on children in the planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Horne (2017) suggests that while policies aim to focus on economic and cultural impacts, mega sporting events can also benefit from policies focusing on unintended

impacts such as respecting human rights, alongside increasing economic outcomes. Building on Horne's (2017) recommendation, this study focuses on one of the unintended negative impacts of hosting mega sporting events. Specifically, it focuses on the effect of mega sporting event planning and delivery on children (child rights infringements), exploring the provision for protection of child rights in policies and principles guiding mega sporting events, using Tokyo 2020 as a case study. The idea of policies focusing on improving living conditions and respecting rights, in the past ten years, have been adopted by cities and countries, however, there remains a deficit in terms of how children are represented and catered for within mega event planning.

Mega sporting events are fast becoming an important space where human rights issues are being discussed, debated and advanced (See Ritchie and Hall, 1999; Ganji, 2016; Talbot and Carter, 2018). This study aims to contribute to the debates by focussing on child rights and mega sporting events. In establishing the link between mega sporting events and child rights, there is a need to understand the general concept of human rights, as child rights is a branch of human rights. The next section provides a brief background into general human rights before an in-depth discussion is undertaken in chapter two.

1.3. A brief introduction to human rights

According to Campbell (2011), the study of rights has been controversial and hotly debated both in theory and in practice with questions such as “Where do rights come from? Are they invented or discovered? What sort of rights are there and who is entitled to them”. According to Nowak (1996), human rights are acknowledged and accepted globally, and continues to be developed in different ways (Nowak, 2003). They are not only universally recognized, they have also pervaded every aspect of life and all levels of society (Smith, 2022). As stated by Robertson, Arthur and Merrills (1996), understanding the significance of human rights has to do with being well informed about their guarantees, both in the area of protection and how they can be easily protected. This

means that studying how rights can be promoted, and realised with full participation and inclusion is important, but also pertinent is the study of how human rights can be protected and channeled into making progressive sustainable changes where they are needed.

Even though the International Declaration of Human Rights (IDHR) was endorsed by every country in 1993, Moyn (2010), cited in Horne (2017), noted that the conversations about human rights started in 1977, because it provided an alternative to other failed utopian projects and grand narratives. In sports, however, Samaranch (1999) argued that human rights are not just an alternative to other projects, it is a contribution to global peace. She also went further to argue that promoting and respecting rights in sport is equivalent to respecting peoples' civil rights – absolutely normal and necessary (Samaranch, 1999). Different scholars have advocated for different dimensions of rights relating to both adults and children in mega sporting events. However, child rights have been under-represented, which is why there is a rising awareness about the dimensions of child rights infringements in mega sporting events. The different dimensions of rights infringement in mega sporting events have been discovered to be, among others, in form of dislocation (Suzuki, Ogawa and Inaba (2018), child labour (Risse, 2009; Jarvie, 2013; Lunacek, 2017), and sexual exploitation (Heerdt and Wook, 2022). While it seems like a lot of body of work focus more on the dimensions of human rights infringements in sport, there are limited literature about the cause of these violations. According to Caudwell and McGee (2018), a constant discourse about the dimensions of human rights violations is important, as it will help further researchers discover how rights can be adequately upheld and represented in the mega sporting events terrain. To this end, I explore the relationship between mega sporting events and human rights in more detail in the next section.

1.4. Mega sporting events and human rights

In the past few decades, mega sporting events have become globally important (Jessop, 2002), and continues to be assessed differently. Several scholars (see Lee and Taylor, 2005; Matheson and Baade, 2004; Preuss, 2007; Leeds, Allmen and Matheson, 2018; Van der Wagen and White, 2018) have observed that mega sporting events are typically gauged by how much impacts they have economically. Recently, however, emphasis is now being placed on the negative social impacts associated with them. As noted by various academics (see Harvey, Horne, Safai, Darnell, and Courchesne-O'Neill, 2013; Van der Wagen and White, 2018; Wenner and Billings, 2017), focus is now being placed on the social outcomes of hosting mega sporting events and the impact they have on the host countries and communities affected by hosting. Research topics, such as sport and social justice, including human rights, are rising up in the agenda, when mega sporting events are being discussed in academia and politics (Harvey et al, 2013). According to Walton and Dawson (2008), a recurring subject matter of mega sporting events is the potentiality of majoring on appraisable end results like multiplication of overheads, and employment gains while overlooking other impacts like the infringement of human rights, which can be classed under the umbrella of negative social impacts. However, in the past twenty four years, considerable efforts have been made to focus on both measurable and immeasurable impacts, while also developing different ways to utilize sport as a means of achieving sustainable positive impacts, regeneration, and peace (Kidd, 2008; Darnell, Giulianotti, Howe and Collison, 2018). This has been accompanied by a growing body of literature exploring how mega sporting events can be leveraged as a means of addressing social ills, which almost always tend to be inadequately addressed by public authorities like the local government in host cities and countries (Kidd, 2008). Most of these social ill assessments such as human rights infringements have been championed by advocacy organizations, like Amnesty International, and Terre Des Homme, alongside charities like

UNICEF focused on child rights. As observed by Brownell (2012), the Olympic Game is now being utilized by advocacy organizations to call for accountability from state actors and public authorities.

Despite the increasing involvement of NGOs in mega sporting events, human rights violations linked to the staging of mega sporting events continue to increase enormously. An example of this is the Beijing 2008 Olympics which garnered an intense debate about why it was allowed to host, despite its human rights issues (Black and Bezanson, 2004; Chen and Hsu, 2018). These debates about human rights issues in relation to mega sporting events point towards a call for more proactiveness in how these rights infringements might be avoided. Specifically, in adherence to the United Nations Human Rights objectives, mega sporting events should be addressed from a human rights perspective. This can be achieved through careful and appropriate planning and integrating the management of potential human rights impacts into the security planning for mega sporting events (IHRB, 2013). This might also mean that countries with existing human rights issues would try to use the Olympic Games to address their societal ills while also trying to improve their global perception while hiding the negatives (Næss, 2020). Although Boykoff (2019) calls this sport washing, this is a soft power strategy to address rights issues (Horne, 2017). This played out well for Beijing, as observations on the Beijing Olympics suggest that perceptions of China improved because of its hosting the Games (Foley et al, 2012). Not only did the Games bring awareness of the human rights issues in China at the time the bid was won; hosting the Olympic Games also brought to limelight some other positive attributes that China was not known for, at the time. This speaks to the ability of the Olympic Games to not only help in correcting societal ills, but also help improve host country's image and global perception while at it. Invariably, mega sporting events contribute to infringement of human rights, however,

acknowledging that sporting events also have the prospect to be a force for good for both participants and viewers is pertinent.

Roche (2001) hinges on how the philosophy of Olympism tries to elevate sport into the leading edge of a broader idealistic and universalistic humanitarian mission in the modern world. Similarly, Black and Bezanson (2004), also iterate the highly compatibility of mega sporting events and human rights movement in promoting the universal human rights incorporated in the 1948 UNDHR. However, as noted by Kidd and Donnelly (2000) human rights success cannot be realized without all sport participants fully enjoying those rights. One of the most important questions related to human rights and sports is whether human rights are universal enough to include non-participants of mega sporting events. To this, several studies (see Talbot and Carter, 2018; Risse, 2009; Schofield, Rhind and Blair, 2018) have argued that rights in sport should not be limited to sport participants alone, and that rights in sports should be extended to everyone who is directly or indirectly affected by the activities of sporting events: from the planning stage to the delivery stage and the post-delivery stage especially since there have been experiences of human rights infringements of the most vulnerable people in society – refugees, the poor, recorded at all stages of mega events (Schofield, Rhind and Blair, 2018). In Rio, for instance, there were environmental issues (Gaffney, 2010), forced removals and state-based violence by the police on non-participants, which instigated protests against various human rights abuses in the lead up to the Olympic Games delivery (Talbot and Carter, 2018). Similarly, as observed by Giulianotti (2004), about 500 protesters got killed, in Mexico, ten days ahead of the Games. Furthermore, urban regeneration projects in Atlanta 1996 Olympics left urban residents worse off (Andranovich, Burbank, and Heying, 2001). Even more recently, Suzuki, Ogawa and Inaba (2018) argue that the rights of some of the vulnerable people in the city have been infringed before the delivery of the Tokyo 2020 Games. They argue that rebuilding the National Stadium in advance of the 2020

Summer Olympics in Tokyo fostered the supplanting of specific vulnerable citizens, thereby heightening apprehensions for possible violations to child rights.

1.5. Mega sporting events and child rights

Literature suggests that there are groups which are especially negatively impacted by the planning and hosting of mega sporting events. One of those groups is children. Of late, there have been debates about how children's rights are being violated by mega sporting events (see Brackenridge and Kirby, 1997; Farstad, 2007; Weber, 2009; Giulianotti, 2004). According to David (2004), one particular area where culturally accepted corporal punishments and rigorous trainings, which might be physically and emotionally violating towards children, have been spotlighted is sport. The United Nations, academics, NGOs such as Terre Des Hommes (Children Win initiative) and UNICEF UK, have been raising awareness about violations of child rights in sporting events in recent years. Eliasson (2015), in a study, for example, used the theory of sociology and childhood to explain how child rights might be understood in sport. The findings evidenced that the issue of violations towards children and their rights, in sports, has not been satisfactorily addressed, because child rights are ignored by adults who are of the opinion that they understand what the child wants, more than the child. David (2005:5) also argues that "children involved in competitive sports grow up in a world dominated by adults who have their own sets of interest". Interests, might not necessarily include an adequate assessment and upholding of children's rights, as explained by David (2005). However, citing Alexander et al (2011: 471), Eliasson (2015) observed that even though many children have positive experiences when involved in sport, they also gave accounts of emotional and physical abuse.

Rights issues can be related to sport or non-sporting events, hence, it is important to differentiate between sporting 'risks' and non-sporting ones. Sporting risks can happen of physical or mental violence, injury or abuse, neglect or negligent treatment, maltreatment or exploitation, including

sexual abuse, child labour (Aine, Muhonen and Toivonen, 2022). While non-sporting risks can assume a pattern of forced evictions, police violence, child labour, abuse and harassment. It is important to note that both sporting risks and non sporting risks have some factors in common. However, this study focuses on sporting risks on children involved in mega sporting events (participants and volunteers), in the context of Tokyo 2020 Olympics. As earlier explained, rights issues associated with child participants and volunteers in sport can take the shape of badgering (psychological and physical), ill treatment, coercion, child labour. According to Mountjoy et al (2016), violations occur because the person being abused is at a disadvantage. Being at a disadvantage then means that the person being abused does not have the power to fight back even when they are exposed to negligence, bullying and hazing. Child participants deserve a respectful, unbiased, violence-free, and safe sport environment (Mountjoy et al. 2016).

In a bid to make sport governing bodies accountable for ensuring child rights are protected in mega sporting events, the organization Terre Des Hommes came up with the “*Children win campaign*”, which sought to guarantee child rights protection, preservation and respect in the before and after stages of mega sporting events (Terre Des Hommes, 2018 [online]). One of the ways this can be done is by ensuring that child rights and the preservation of it are adequately taken into consideration from the inception of mega sporting events, through planning, to delivery (Terre Des Hommes, 2018 [online]).

1.6. Key Concepts

This thesis is grounded in the landscape of mega sporting events, but it also draws on concepts of protection and participation principles as outlined by the principles of child rights as highlighted by the UNCRC. Focusing on child rights with regard to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, I draw on the United Nations child rights principle, published in 1990. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child provides guidelines for those working for, and with, children and

adolescents (David, 2004). It has also been the foundation on which child rights are addressed worldwide. The Convention is made up of 54 articles which cover every facets of a child's life. This outlines the economic, political, cultural and social rights that every child qualifies for. The UNCRC also explains how everyone must work together to ensure all children enjoy all their rights, hence, the UNCRC provides the basis of child rights discussed in this study.

To frame the study, I draw on McGillivray et al's (2019) conceptual model and research agenda for bidding and delivering major sport events that lever human rights alongside Lundy's (2007) model of child participation in events. Lundy's (2007) model expands on Article 12 of the UNCRC, which proposes that children be given a voice, and allowed to be involved in decisions in matters that concern them. This model gives voice to the unspoken factors entailed in the actualization of the UNCRC (Article 12). These factors, as highlighted by Lundy (2007) are voice, space, influence and audience. While Lundy's (2007) model focusses more on the important factors that should be considered if child rights are to be realized in sporting events, McGillivray et al's (2019) concept introduces four pathways to be considered in delivering mega sporting events, from a human rights perspective.

1.7. Study Aims and Objectives

The overarching aim of this research is to critically analyze the mechanisms through which children's rights are protected and promoted in mega sporting events, drawing on the context of the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games.

In addressing the overarching research aim, the study's objectives are to:

1. Critically examine the policies and plans in place to protect and promote children's rights in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games

2. Critically evaluate the dimensions of child right infringements associated with the Olympic Games in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.
3. Critically assess the measures in place to mitigate children's rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games.
4. Critically analyze the roles of key stakeholders in ensuring that the UN Convention on the Rights of Child is adhered to in the planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.
5. Critically analyze the level of child rights representations in Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies, in the aspects of transparency, inclusiveness, democratization, formalization and change management plan.

In this thesis, I argue that mega sporting events including the Olympic Games are neither planned nor delivered from a child rights perspective. I also argue that there are different factors responsible for this. These factors include a lack of leadership structure for child rights, children not being recognised as rights bearers, and a lack of adequate representation of child rights in policies and principles guiding the Games. As a result of these, there remains a conceptual gap in how mega sporting events can be holistically planned and delivered from a child rights perspective. This study fills the gap by developing a conceptual framework that can be practically adopted by the planning committees, and event owners of mega sporting events.

1.8. Thesis structure

The opening chapter has introduced the topic and summarized the thesis. It has set the background for the thesis and introduced the concepts of human rights and their relationship with mega sporting events. It has also outlined the conceptual focus of this thesis.

Chapter two provides an in-depth review of existing literature and arguments about human rights, including its concepts, dynamics, movement and general principles. In this chapter, I begin with a

discussion around the history of human rights and the approach to human rights in the early years, after which I discuss the seeming westernization of human rights. Also, in this chapter, I discuss the main international human rights treaties, their effectiveness and relevance to my study – assessing child rights in mega sporting events, reflecting on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

In chapter three, I review extant literature around mega sporting events. In this chapter, I provide a definition of mega sporting events, expanding on the brief introduction to mega sporting events in chapter one. I then discuss in detail the evidence of human rights infringements related to the Olympic Games, noting that these are in tension with the concept of Olympism. After this, there will be a discussion on the Olympic history, the Olympic concept and the Olympic movement. Finally, this chapter advances an argument around the need for bidding for the Olympic Games to be informed by a human rights perspective, while also discussing the IOC's power and ability to ensure that child rights in the Olympic Games are safeguarded.

Chapter four sets out the conceptual framework guiding this research. Setting the background for this study's findings and analysis, I discuss the history of child rights in the Olympic Games before discussing the models and conceptual frameworks that guide this research. In this chapter, I review the importance of the UNCRC, while also noting that the UNCRC is the basis upon which the primary model and framework adopted for this study is built. I then detail how Lundy's (2007) child inclusion guide and a conceptual pathway that helps to delivering mega sporting events that lever on human rights are useful in framing the focus of the study, developed by McGillivray et al. (2019).

In chapter five, the study methodology is detailed. Based on the nature of this research, which seeks to explore the concept and idea of child rights in mega sporting events, a qualitative approach has been adopted. Due to the implications of the Covid-19 pandemic, I was unable to travel to

Tokyo to observe and gather primary data in-situ, therefore a documentary examination of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games legal documents were carried out instead. In addition, in-depth interviews were conducted with stakeholders from the JOC, NGOs and relevant governmental bodies in charge of planning for the Tokyo 2020 Games. I also worked closely and participated in seminars, conferences and workshops at the Centre for Sport and Human Rights, and UNICEF where violations concerning children were discussed in order to gain more knowledge about the rights situation in Japan before the delivery of the Tokyo 2020 Games. Published reports from these workshops and seminars were consulted to present some of the findings of this work.

In chapter six, I present the findings from the documentary analysis, informed by McGillivray et al's (2019) conceptual pathway for delivering a mega sporting event that leverages on human rights to structure the work. The different pathways are used in presenting the documentary examination findings. One of the research objectives guiding this study is to assess what policies were in place to ensure that child rights were adequately protected in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. To achieve that objective, I present findings from Tokyo 2020, in the form of policies, between the periods of 2011 – 2021, when the Games were delivered.

In chapter seven I present interview findings, thematically, drawing primarily on Lundy's (2007) model of participation. In order to further assess the situation of child rights in Tokyo 2020 Olympics, it was important to conduct semi structured interviews with specific stakeholders of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games to complement findings from the documentary analysis and seek clarity on some of the Tokyo 2020 policies and bid documents. Interview themes were informed by both Lundy's (2007) model for child participation and McGillivray et al's (2019) pathways to delivering mega sport events from the perspective of child rights. As a result, I focused on themes relating to provision for protection, participation and management plan to leverage on child rights.

In chapter eight, I provide an analysis of the findings from document examination, semi-structured interviews and present a framework that sets out how the Olympic Games can be delivered from a child rights perspective. Finally, in chapter nine, I present the overall summary of the study. I address the study aims and objectives, while stating whether the objectives were achieved and how they were achieved. I will also provide a summary of the chapters of this study. After which I summarize the main findings in relation to the stated research aim and objectives, while presenting my contribution to knowledge methodologically, empirically and conceptually. Finally, I also present the limitations of this research and future recommendations.

1.9. Conclusion and Contribution to Knowledge

This chapter has provided the roadmap for the remainder of this thesis. By providing a broad overview of three key topics of discussion – human rights, child rights and mega sporting events (the Olympic Games), I have provided background context that makes the case the choice of research area. Drawing on grey and academic literatures, I have outlined the debates that interweave these three key areas of focus, while also discussing how modern-day discourse has created an avenue for viewing mega sporting events, not just from an economic point of view, but also from a human rights and child rights point of view. Stating the recurrence of literature bothering on the continual trend of child rights neglect in mega sporting events (Donnelly, 2008), and the different dimensions of child rights infringements in mega sporting events, I have highlighted the need to address why there seem to be little focus on how child rights are represented in mega sporting events. I have also highlighted the need for a holistic way to address how mega sporting events can be planned and delivered from a child rights perspective.

This thesis contributes to knowledge by addressing the above-mentioned gaps and going further to address these gaps. This study contributes to understanding about why there continues to be a rise in child rights violations in mega sporting events. In providing the rationale for this, I

emphasize the importance of incorporating clearly defined child rights safeguarding initiatives in blueprints and principles informing how mega sporting events should be delivered. Given the lack of research about how mega sporting events can be planned and delivered from a child rights perspective, I also offer a holistic framework for how this can be achieved.

Finally, this thesis contributes to general debates about children as right bearers, linking this with the importance of fostering a recognition of children as capable of exercising participatory rights, while also emphasizing the role of event owners plus state and non-state actors in ensuring that mega sporting events comply with the UNCRC. This research is particularly useful for policy makers and researchers who want to conduct further research on children rights and the Olympic Games. This research, through the framework developed for delivering mega sporting events from a child rights based approach, provides a structure for understanding the dynamics of child rights protection and provision. This study as a whole is a valuable scaffold with respect to which child rights in mega sporting events can be assessed.

CHAPTER TWO – HUMAN RIGHTS PRINCIPLES AND POLICIES

2.1. Introduction

The human rights movement has consistently increased its global influence since it was first established. In this chapter, I provide an analysis of previous and current academic work on human rights, key concepts and the emergence of an international movement. This sets the background for the discussion around mega sporting events and human rights. As discussed in chapter one, human rights are a widely accepted concept, which has generated a lot of controversy and debate over recent decades. The preceding chapter provided a brief background to human rights and their relationship with mega sporting events. In this chapter I discuss in-depth the concept of human rights and its accompanying movement. I begin by discussing early definitions of human rights, before outlining how these have changed in recent decades. Following this, I consider the so-called westernization of human rights and its implication for this study, which focuses on the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games. Finally, in this chapter, I discuss the effectiveness of existing human rights treaties and their applicability to the Tokyo 2020 Games.

2.2. Human Rights Concept and Movement

Prior to the 1940s, the term “human rights” was rarely used, nor was there an international movement or concept by the name human rights (Cmie, 2014). There was also no formal NGO acting to defend human rights principles, or an international law crafted to protect human rights (Cmie, 2014). The contemporary human rights concept and movement can be traced back to the era between the world wars. Worldwide solidarity emerged from the need to have the government of each nation recognize basic civil rights, and put in place structures to address and protect those rights (IJRC, 2019). For example, the international law commission adopted the Declaration of the International Rights of Man in 1929 (Donnelly and Whelan, 2017) and on December 10, 1948, the United Nations General Assembly adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). At the time, delegates clearly noted that the Declaration was not a binding treaty, but rather a

statement of principles (Risse-Kappen, Risse, Ropp and Sikkink, 1999). In this statement, the United Nations, as an organization, described its beliefs and intentions about the human rights movement. “Right” in English, like equivalent words in several other languages, has two central moral and political senses: rectitude and entitlement (Donnelly, 2013). Rights in the sense of rectitude refers to the “right thing to do”, of something being right (or wrong), while rights in the narrower sense of entitlement can be said to be “someone having a right” (Donnelly, 2013). The concept of human rights in this form is based on the belief that human beings are entitled to enjoy their rights without discrimination (IHRC, 2020). These basic rights are based on shared values including dignity, fairness, equality, respect and independence which are defined and protected by the law (EHRC, 2019). However, there remains considerable disagreement among academics about the idea of human rights, its definition and its concept. According to Ghosal (2010):

The concept of human rights is one of the most widely discussed and debated ideas of national and international politics since the beginning of the second half of the century. The swings of human civilization necessarily touch two ends of the same continuum, on one end, there are events of deprivations, inequality, exploitations, killing and all kinds of indignant activities towards human beings and humanity. On the other hand, there are attempts to protect humanity, human values, rights, equality, liberty and other desired ethical goals (pp 1103).

Despite its acclaimed values, the history of human rights is filled with discussions about what has been, and what might/might not be. Since human rights was introduced in 1948, different struggles in varied contexts have been attributed to it (Horne, 2017), which is why there is a considerable variance of opinion as to how best to define human rights (Orend, 2002). This seeming difficulty in having a holistic definition of human rights continually shapes and changes the way it is addressed, outside of its discourse of values and importance. As Nussbaum (1997) argues, when organizations and state actors talk about basic human needs, the word “rights” are frequently adopted. Also, in cases where a group of people are recognized as direly in need of

protection, their representatives also adopt the word “right” when their cases are being legally presented to the right authorities (Nussbaum, 1997). This brings to fore the question of what exactly the definition of “human rights” is, especially since the language of “rights” has different preferences and different meanings in different sectors and contexts.

In order to fully understand the concept of human rights, it is important to define human rights. Over the years, several scholars have attempted to define human rights, and articulate the different ways of thinking about what human rights are, by describing human rights from four different perspectives. Foremost, civil rights theory thinks of human rights as innate and essential, which means that everyone holds equal rights, on account of simply being human (Liang, 2022). This school of thought describes human rights from the perspective of entitlement, subscribing that all humans are entitled to, or deserve some form of rights, by right of being human. Second, other schools of thought argue that human rights were created for social purposes, thereby defining human rights in the context of it being a constructed social concept. A prominent scholar in this school of thought is Brownell (2012) who describes human rights as a concept that was constructed rather than it being a pre-given moral truth. This leads to the belief that human rights were constructed for human existence. In a way, this is like the naturalist’s theory of entitlement. As explained by Nussbaum (1997), the reason why human rights are referred to as entitlements is because human beings are entitled to rights just because they are human, or protection given to some group of people simply because they deserve to be protected. This suggests that if human rights are constructed, then some sets of humans have been identified to be lacking rights protection, and a particular group of people have constructed a form of right that covers this set of marginalized people. Third, other than the definition of human rights being a function of entitlement and social construct, a different body of work, such as Greggs (2012) have also described human rights in the capacity of its usefulness or capability. Keane (2003) expanded on

the usefulness and capabilities of human rights by explaining that even though human rights have been conceived as a concept capable of fostering societal transformations, human rights as a concept is not the transformational factor, transformations are only achieved by the different global social movements of human rights which are sometimes championed by advocacy organizations. This is because advocacy organizations are most often responsible for constructing human rights, promoting them and engaging in how human rights concepts and movements are accepted globally. Finally, human rights have been defined to be a western concept. This school of thought argues that due to the individualistic nature of human rights, they are not suitable for non-western countries (Talbot, 2022).

According to Falk (2008), human rights was initially designed as an unprejudiced western initiative, inaugurated after the second world war. Although, before this western initiative, human rights was designed as a protection strategy for culturally marginalized people in European countries (Falk, 2008, Griffin, 2008, Neier, 2012). The need for designing a set of rules for the protection of culturally marginalized people in Germany was considered unsuccessful because it encouraged military interference. As a result of this, human rights advocacy organizations placed emphasis on civil rights while also condemning governmental intrusion (Falk, 2008). Hence, with the emergence of human rights advocacy organizations, such as Amnesty International, a shift started to arise in the way human rights are being approached and carried out, which shifted the focus and perspective of human rights. Even though some have argued that this ideology is power-related, as all human rights activists have an interest in the way power is used (Waltz, 2020). However, the deviation in how human rights are addressed has strengthened, even brought more awareness to some overlooked aspects of human rights, such as child rights, women's rights and rights of persons with disabilities (Healy, 2008).

According to Caudwell and McGee (2018), the moral imperative of the human rights approach was to formally document violations and abuses. In the past decade, this has expanded to NGOs embracing different approaches to stop human rights infringements from happening, instead of waiting until violations occur. For instance, the overall objectives of the different conventions of the United Nations are to investigate instances of human rights infringements and come up with ways for administering justice and upholding each right under the conventions (OHCHR). In recent years, the UN has broadened its horizon to include creating awareness, holding workshops and publishing documents that seek to provide solutions to human rights problems. This is in line with Caudwell and McGee's (2018) argument that other than advocacy for human rights protection, and discoveries of new forms of human rights violations, necessity requires that the debates around the basic existence and elements of human rights also broaden to include how to provide prevention measures and solutions to help address human rights infringements. This is especially important since human rights are still being abused globally (Simmons, 2014; Freeman, 2017), despite the fact that they have been infused in the national legal and ethical constitution, for some time now (Caudwell and McGee, 2018).

Freeman (2017) argues that human rights violations are facts that are sometimes best expressed numerically, though there is an uneasy relationship between knowledge of numbers and understanding of what they mean. In terms of how human rights violations materialize, philosophers and legal theorists argue that culture, ideology and value are influential factors. This study focuses on the cultural debates because of their relevance to this study and case study. First, Orend (2002) argues that human rights should exist independent of culture, ideology, and value systems, especially as cultures and human rights' discussions are fluid (Donnelly 2007). Similarly, Cohen (2006) also posits that human rights should be presented autonomously, that is, independently of any comprehensive philosophical, cultural or religious doctrine. This is because

a plurality of cultures can affect human rights activities, if they are viewed as being dependent on culture (Cohen, 2006). Donnelly (2007) goes further to explain that human rights should not necessarily be linked to any internal factor such as culture, because human rights have relevance, whatever the context, regardless of culture. Finally, building on the pre-existing notions of human rights being independent of or from cultural ideologies, Forst (2012) also proposes that human rights should not only be unlinked with culture but should also be based on the notion of an individual's right to justification of free and equal persons (Forst, 2012).

While these arguments for human rights being independent of culture or other doctrines are laudable, there are opposing views about this, based on the fluidity of the meaning of culture and how human rights constructs fit into the different cultural dynamics. Moreso, because the idea of human rights, is sometimes, an opposite of its supposed values and the cultural values of different communities (Du preez and Rouz, 2012). While Merry (2001) argues that there should be a way to incorporate human rights into culture, there is, however, the question of how human rights addresses cultural values that encourage violations of rights, especially in nations where hierarchy is embraced above human rights principles and policies. As a response to this, Forst (2011) observes that advocacy organizations such as the United Nations, Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch, and Terre Des Hommes have played a significant role in trying to break the barriers. This, again, reflects the role of advocacy organizations in advancing the human rights movement. While Forst (2011) gives credence to advocacy organizations in the role they play in finding a common ground for culture and human rights, Merry (2001) noted that incorporating human rights into such a culture is still a struggle, as there continue to be conflicts of interest, especially in the field of sport. Regardless of whatever challenge faced, advocacy organizations continue to create awareness and emphasize standard treatments that no human being could justifiably deny to others (Forst, 2011). This, being the consensus about why human rights exist in

the first place: To identify violations, collect incidental data, analysis and publication, promote public awareness while conducting institutional advocacy, and lobby to halt violations (Simmons, 2014).

The human rights movement has been recorded as one of the good things to happen to human rights advocacy since it started shortly after the world war. As argued by Kennedy (2002), there is no question that the human rights movement has done a great deal of good, as it frees individuals from great harm while raising the standards by which governments judge one another. According to Kennedy (2002), careers in the human rights movement have also provided thousands of professionals with a “sense of dignity and confidence that one can sometimes do well while doing good” (p. 101). The idea of the human rights movement itself has been a story of long struggles and sacrifices for supporters (Pavel, 2012). Before the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) emerged, the struggle for civil liberties was considered something for citizens to undertake only within their own countries (Kaufman, 1991). The “why”, “what”, “how” of promoting and upholding rights were relative to each country as there were no general laws guiding how these rights should be protected. The first stage of the legitimization of human rights was embodied in the thirty articles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Although further elaboration and preparation of more specific covenants were seen as essential, implementation gradually became central (Kaufman, 1991). Over the years, the human rights movement has broadened its engagements and terms of reference. It also now attracts and mobilizes thousands of good-hearted people around the globe each year (Kennedy, 2002). Even though the idea and concept of human rights has been widely accepted since it came into existence, formally in 1948, there have also been quite a lot of controversies and debates around it. Orend (2002) argued that the wide acceptance of the human rights movement itself in the modern century is something to

be concerned about because there is a considerable difference of opinion as to what human rights are, and there is the problem of how exactly to define the movement (Simmons, 2014).

In summary, the general consensus about human rights is that they are universal (Renteln, 2014). This gives moral grounds to define human rights as a universal concept that is held by all persons (Renteln, 2014). Linking it, however, with the social construct school of thought, I define human rights as a universal concept which can also be constructed to protect and prevent violations of the marginalized child, in the context of mega sporting events, and this study. This is in line with Brownell's (2012) definition of human rights being a socially constructed concept, to promote peace and enhance human dignity (Giulianotti, 2004). This is particularly applicable to sporting events. This means that, as mentioned in chapter one, sport is a tool for advancing the global movement of human rights. Even though sport and human rights have always been connected, sport being used as a medium to convey human rights ideologies can be traced back to the 1970s, but because advocacy organizations continue to promote the concept, the connection keeps getting stronger. Even though the concept is fluid and can be adapted to suit different narrative and context, there are arguments about how well this concept has worked well in countries where cultural values are perceived to be strong. This brings me back to the debate about human rights (westernized concept), conflicting with cultural values (Du Preez and Rouz, 2012). Particularly, because in the context of sport, human rights and culture have been used interchangeably to achieve the common goal of promoting peace and unity (Heindrichs, 2019). This means that in some instances, people have had to resort to their ethnic moral standards because they think of it as simple and clear (Du Preez and Rouz, 2012), and people have also had to turn to human rights because they feel that human rights is better than their culture (Du Preez and Rouz, 2012). Even though there is the natural tendency to protect culture from westernization, undoubtedly, human rights are still a force for good. This, however, does not change the fact that human rights being perceived as a western

concept can affect how human rights are accepted and modelled to co-exist alongside cultural values. According to Du Preez and Rouz (2012), questions of human rights attempting to change elements of culture to feed into the concept of human rights tend to arise in specific situations. This brings up the question of how then does human right construct fit into the concept of culture to produce a common result, particularly in relations to mega sporting events held in non-western countries such as Japan. This will be discussed in depth in the next section.

2.3 Human Rights: Culture versus Westernization

The notion of the rights of man, like revolution itself, opened an unpredictable space for discussion, conflict and change (Philips, 2018). While some human rights commentators assert that the human rights concept is a Western one, based on the changes and discussions around the concept and movement, others insist that it is universal. However, this thesis takes the approach of human rights being a universal concept, due to the fact that human rights, in its universality is able to accommodate some western and cultural values.

Philips (2018), citing Hunt (2007) argued that new ideas about human rights contributed to its movement, as it called forth more virulent forms of rights violations, which might continue in the coming years. Simmons (2014) noted that the human rights movement itself has now become intellectually fashionable and sensitive. This raises the question of what the future holds for the human rights movement. If the concept keeps changing to reflect modernism, then there is the probability that the movement is also fluid and might keep changing to reflect future modernism. At the core of this movement and future change to the human rights movement, as previously explained, are human rights activists who continue to construct human rights (Brownell, 2012), to reflect the present-day changes. Neier (2012) argues that interactions between the press and non-governmental human rights advocates has been an important element in the rise of the movement in many countries, as advocates keep promoting their cause by seeking media attention for rights

abuses, and media exposure of violations and of those responsible for these violations. Because of this interaction and media exposure, human rights discussions have found a place in strategic sectors worldwide like Universities and government sectors (Simmons, 2014). In addition, different organizations and sport committees like the International Olympic Committee are also beginning to include human rights in their policies.

While these are all indications of a progressive movement, there are still questions and debates about whether organizations and countries adequately follow the principles of human rights, especially since nations must sign treaties to be a part of the human rights movement, practically. According to Belina, Darbon, Sundstol and Sending (2009), supporting the fundamental human rights principle has the tendency to increase the popular acceptance of governments or state actors, however, it is routinely acknowledged that many states endorse human rights principles – for example, by ratifying human rights treaties, without putting those principles into practice. This calls for considerations about the usefulness of human rights treaties, and the purpose to which states sign them, especially in cities where mega sporting events are hosted. As explained in section 2.2, mega sporting events are influenced by different factors, one of which is culture. As explained further, “culture” and “human rights” are two different concepts in countries where culturalism is a major influence on how they live. This means that some ideas and ideals such as principles of the UNCRC might be termed western and thus unwelcomed. Example of this is “corporal punishment” in Japan before it was banned in 2020. Corporal punishment was a part of the Japanese culture, as is with some other countries who share similar cultural values with Japan. However, due to a published article (HRW, 2019) tagging corporal punishment as universally unacceptable in 2019, corporal punishment was banned in Tokyo. This was done prior to the Tokyo Olympic Games delivery. In addition, similarly, pertinent to note that in 2019, the UNCRC also demanded the Japanese government harmonize its existing legislation with the principles and

provisions of the UNCRC, indicating that the domestic laws are in discord with the CRC in essential aspects (Mizuoka, 2021). This is a classic example of tradition versus westernization. This also suggests that despite Japan being a non-western country, in some instances, it can be held to the same standard of human rights universality, and its ability to accommodate cultural factors.

In the context of the Olympic Games, some scholars have argued that both tradition and westernization influences how sport events are delivered from a human rights perspective. With the Olympic Games, it has been observed that host countries sometimes host the event in a way that appeals to both local and international audiences. This can be considered an act of diplomacy. In the case of Tokyo 2020, Heindrichs (2019) argues that Tokyo occupied a limbo between Western culture and Asian culture. In their observation, advertorials for Tokyo 2020 had to create an image of Tokyo that simultaneously offered a sense of Japanese essence to its national audiences, and fed into western interests and preconceptions of Tokyo and Japanese culture. Tokyo did not only feed into western interests through their strategic advertorials, they also fed into western interests by developing an after-thought document and policies (see Aina et al, 2021) that addressed human rights and sustainability. Adopting human rights specifics for the purpose of sport is a step in the right direction, but what happens after the delivery of the Olympic Games? According to Heerdts (2020), making a rights protection pact with organizers involved in staging the Olympic Games is a step in the right direction, however, these pacts are inconsequential if these rights are not enforced, or sealed with legal documents that ensure sustainability after such rights have been enforced. This speaks to the importance of treaties to human rights concepts, human rights movement, and sports, as they are binding agreements that legally enforce human rights protection in states and countries. In the next section, I discuss the importance of treaties in promoting the human rights concept through the human rights movement. While this study is not

a study about the human rights movement, however, the discussion around the human rights movements is important in setting the background for this study of sport and its linkage to human rights. Sport is an essential bit of the human rights movement, as sport has been discovered to be a tool for achieving human rights (Lang Fuentes, 2022) .

2.4 The importance of treaties in the human rights movement

The previous section discussed the concept of human rights as a western idea. In addition, the section also discussed how Tokyo strategically planned to deliver an Olympic Games that fed into the western idea by adding human rights specifics to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies. It was also noted in the section that host cities do not necessarily have an obligation to deliver sport events that lever on human rights if the human rights treaty have not been signed. This brings to the fore the importance of human rights treaties to the progress of the “human rights movement”. As defined by OHCHR (2018), a treaty is an agreement by states to be bound by rules. More explicitly, a state can become party to a treaty by ratification, accession, or succession (OHCHR, 2018). There are seventy human rights treaties that monitor implementation of the core international human rights treaties. Each of these treaties has established a committee of experts to monitor implementation of the treaty provisions by its state's parties (UNFPA, 2018). The main functions of the treaty bodies are to examine reports submitted by State parties and to consider complaints of human rights violations (OHCHR). International treaties make up the foundation of the global human rights system administration. Dissimilar to declarations, treaties are obligatory legalized documents and, according to Wotipka and Tsutsui (2008), these treaties can be considered as stronger instruments to promote global human rights. Although the UDHR asserts the inalienable rights of all human beings, the power of the declaration rests on the sovereignty of its signatory states, as it acknowledges in passing its introduction (Talbot and Carter, 2016). Without doubt, international treaties are crucial in setting the seal on human rights in signatory

states, but there are concerns about the effectiveness of the treaty in improving and promoting respect for human rights. Theorising the pillars of compliance, Cole (2012) championed the debate about the ineffectiveness of human rights treaties in some states. According to Neumayer (2005), after the non-binding universal human rights, many global and regional human rights have been concluded, critics argue that the treaties are unlikely to have made any actual difference, especially in non-democratic societies where it is difficult to even measure the human rights practices of governments (Orend, 2002). Cole (2012) argues that the human rights agenda might be better advanced if sanctions are placed on states who default, while rewards are dispensed for compliance. However, this would take away the importance of democracy, as many nations who have signed human rights treaties practice a democratic system of governance.

According to Neumayer (2005), democracy is a powerful influencing factor for human rights authorization, because without democracy, treaty implementation is fruitless. And according to OHCHR (2022), the state should be majorly responsible for ensuring that human rights are enjoyed and protected, in this way, states will also be responsible for protecting the basic human rights of individuals. Hence, in the absence of democracy and strong civil society, as mentioned earlier, treaty ratification has no effect and is possibly associated with more human rights violations (Neumayer, 2005). Morals and values, rather than inducements and sanctions, constitute the driving force of compliance (Cole, 2012). This suggests that human rights treaties work best in democratic states and nations. On the other hand, it can be argued that signing the treaty should help non-democratic nations enforce human rights principles. However, as mentioned by Neymar (2005), this might bring about more violations of rights, as people who are found violating human rights might also have their rights violated, which inadvertently defeats the purpose of the human rights concept and movement.

Arguing in the context of this study, as regards the role of the state in ensuring that human rights are adequately protected and provided for in sport, having the international human rights treaties signed is a sign that a state is willing to take up the responsibility for protecting human rights, on a state level. More so, in the delivery of mega sporting events, signing a human rights treaty is pertinent in the delivery of an Olympic Games which lever on human rights, as signing the treaty would mean that countries hosting mega sporting events are bound by it. As mentioned by Wotipka and Tsutsui (2008), unlike declarations, treaties are binding legal documents. According to Chappelet (2021), ratifying treaties and conventions commits states to incorporating the human rights involved into their national legislation, thereby creating an international human rights law. However, certain countries' reluctance to ratify some of these treaties negatively impact the universality of the human rights they describe. For example, Japan won the bid to host the 2020 Olympics, and as noted by United Nations (2011), it has signed and ratified most of the international human rights treaties, including the international bill of human rights, women's human rights, rights of the child. However, it has left human rights treaties such as employment and forced labour unsigned. Furthermore, even though Japan has signed the rights of the child treaty, as the United Nations (2011) noted, Japan left "the optional protocol to the convention on the rights of the child on communication procedure" section of the child right treaty unsigned. This, according to Auslin (2009) can be described as negotiating with imperialism, considering the hierarchical nature of the Japanese culture and the westernized nature of the treaties. This treaty provides guidelines and principles for child communication in events that concern them. Not signing this treaty might indirectly impact on the way children are communicated with or given a voice in the issues that concern them in Japan, especially in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, which is the focus of this study.

Sport can be utilized to achieve positive outcomes (Giulianotti, 2004); however, this depends on how human rights are approached in sporting events. There are different approaches to human rights such as universality and inalienability, indivisibility, interdependence and interrelatedness, non – discrimination and equality, participation and inclusion, accountability and the rule of law (Schmidt-Traub, 2009). As from many human rights definitions, human rights are presumed to be universal in nature, however, while Mutua (2004) has argued that universalism is not entirely possible if the core content of human rights is to be considered. Renteln (2014) also argued that the basis of human rights being universal is ungrounded.

This study argues that participation and inclusion, accountability and non - discriminatory approach to human rights in sport can go a long way to advance the cause of rights. Specifically, ensuring practical child inclusion in governance, while also holding governments accountable for human rights obligation (Schmidt–Traub, 2009). This approach to human right has been argued to be a pathway to development (see Cornwall, 2002; Kuruvilla, Bustreo, Hunt and Singh, 2012).

2.5. Conclusion

In this chapter, I have discussed the concept and movement of human rights while also stating the importance and usefulness of human rights, not only in the world of sports, but generally, by making comparisons between the practices and existence of a human rights movement across time and space. The chapter has also clarified that the human rights definition that is most applicable to this study is that of “human rights as a construct” based on the context of the study (sport), and the history of sport in relation with human rights. It was also argued that even though human rights has always been a part of sport, being constructed to be a tool to promoting human rights and addressing human rights issues started in the 1970s.

In this chapter, I have also outlined the history of human rights, while also noting the debates and arguments that surround it. As noted by McGee (2018), there is a need to move beyond advocacy for protection to considering a more general sociological approach to human rights in societies. I have also shown that the human rights concept and movement continues to grow rapidly, even though there is uncertainty about the future of the movement, because of modernism, so far, changes in the human rights concept have contributed to the movement being widely accepted in the modern day. In addition, I have also stated the importance of NGOs in the human rights movement, as they have been championing the advocacy of human rights protection through different means such as lobbying and protest. Generally, this chapter has argued that human rights have done a great deal of good by promoting a concept that protects individuals from harm.

There are still apprehensions about the effectiveness of human rights, especially in the aspect of treaties and states. Most of the concerns are with states signing treaties but not following the principles of human rights such as ensuring fairness, equality, and respect (regardless of age), thereby making the treaty non-effective in these states, as violations continue to happen. This concern also extends to organizational settings, and the international sport event terrain, especially when nations that signed the human right treaty record violations and abuse when they host mega sporting events. Relating the significance of signing the human rights treaties to my study, I note that Japan has not signed the communications aspect of the child rights treaties. This, I argue had an effect on the delivery of the Tokyo 2020 Games, as children were not communicated with in the events leading up to the Games, or during its delivery. Not signing the communications aspect of the treaty shows Japan's disinterest in communicating with children, giving them a voice, space, audience or influence in the decision making processes of issues that concern them, as stipulated by the UNCRC.

In the next chapter, I review literature pertaining to mega sporting events and their specific links to human rights. The chapter will also set out some examples of how the principles of human rights are being neglected in the planning and delivery of the Olympic Games.

CHAPTER 3: MEGA SPORTING EVENTS, THE OLYMPIC GAMES, AND RIGHTS

3.1. Introduction

As discussed in the introductory chapter, mega sporting events are enormous occasions that captivate attention and generate both negative and positive outcomes. While most academics focus on the reasons for bidding for the events (Essex and Chkley, 2008; Oliver, 2014), and the positive impact, especially economic, cultural, and social, there is also considerable literature about the negative impacts. However, other scholars have argued that the negative impacts of mega sporting events supersede the positive ones (Liu and Wilson, 2014). These negative impacts often fall under the social impact spectrum. This study addresses one of the negative social impacts of mega sporting events – child rights infringement. Both positive and negative impact arguments will be reviewed in this chapter because it sets a precedent for how child rights infringements will be discussed subsequently. The previous chapter provided insight into the concept and movement of human rights. This chapter will build on those debates but with a direct link to the context of mega sporting events, especially the Olympic Games while also analyzing the relationship between human rights and sporting events. In the final part of the chapter, the context of child rights in mega sporting events will be introduced drawing on examples from the last three Olympics and evidence of the International Olympics Committee (IOC) response.

3.2. Mega sporting events debates

As identified in chapter one, there is a significant obscurity about why events are called mega, with authors identifying different characteristics, such as its ability to generate media attention, its size factor and how it marks the dissimilarity between events and mega – events (Muller, 2015). Also, in chapter one, it was established that there is an ambiguity about size that needs to be unravelled (See Marris 1987; Hiller, 1995; Getz, 1997; Getz, 2008; Muller, 2015; Matheson and Baade, 2004; Fujak, Frawley and Morgan, 2016). In addition to this, it was also established that mega sporting events also have significant negative impacts. Negative consequences such as price

inflation, pollution and environmental concern, security and crime concern for the host city, region or nation in which they occur (Horne, 2007; Liu and Wilson, 2014). All of these factors categorizes the Olympic Games and FIFA as a mega sporting events. However, for the purpose of this study, more emphasis will be placed on the Olympic Games.

The past fifty years have seen sporting events being used as an instrument to maximize economic recovery, create social awareness, and advance cultural heritage. Marris (1987) argues that mega sporting events have become distinguished, particularly because they are reputable, widely viewed, and produce urban regenerations. More recently, Kobiereck and Strozek (2021) have highlighted the reputational advantages of hosting mega sporting events, arguing that they both generate income for host cities, alongside building soft power. While numerous scholars have concentrated on the positive affects of hosting mega sporting events, ranging from economic outcomes, regeneration purposes and media attention, Preuss (2007) has argued that undoubtedly, that economic impacts are not everything, other impacts such as cultural and social are important.

Another debate around mega sporting events is that of urban regeneration and their ability to foster redevelopment. For instance, FIFA requires that the World Cup host country provide sporting facilities of certain quality, and most recently, FIFA has required that everything from the planning to the delivery also has to be human rights oriented (Matheson and Baade, 2004; Sanctis, 2014; Kirschner, 2019; Duval and Heerdt, 2020). However, there is also the debate about why funding for sporting facilities have to come from public funds (see Andranovich, Burbank and Heying, 2001; Matheson, 2006; Siegfried and Zimbalist, 2006; Fourie and Santana – Gallego 2011). The general answer to why public funds are used to build facilities is that this is an investment which generates an economic turnover for the local economy. Such a justification, according to Siegfried and Zimbalist (2006), has little empirical evidence to back it up. However, as I discuss later, all

these infrastructures and buildings indirectly contribute to rights infringements through labour exploitation and displacement (Aina et al. 2021). Even though hosting these games seem lucrative, the fact remains that the advantage surpasses the costs (Jones, 2000; Fourie and Santana – Gallego, 2011), which has been the basis for the study of social impacts associated with mega sporting events. A foremost social impacts of mega sporting events, which is now being studied by organizations and academics, is the infringement of human rights. Specifically, in the Olympic Games, there have been several documentations of rights infringement, despite mega sporting events being promoted as a force for good (Adams and Piekarz, 2015).

Kesenne (2005) argued that some impact studies are sometimes used to show prove that mega sportine events are beneficial, thus justifying the deflection of public funds. While some studies focus on the benefits, some only focus on the respective negative occurences that make up the social impacts. Example is Waitt's (2003) who sought to investigate the social impacts of the Sydney Olympics, from the perspective of residents. In the analysis, he recorded the divergent reactions regarding the economic impacts versus social implications on the residents. While some residents felt that hosting the Games was worth it, others disagreed. As detailed below, Watt (2003) stated that:

The theme (social injustice) suggests that respondents felt that public monies could have been better spent on other welfare facilities, particularly transport, the homeless, and the public medical system (Medicare). For example "No. The Olympics is good for competitors, but the money could've been spent elsewhere, on hospital, schools or roads". These responses were particularly common among the elderly. The social injustice perceived among this subgroup perhaps reflects a personal vested interest in provisions of public health care facilities. The "no personal rewards" theme was clearly expressed by respondents who, from their experiences of the games, perceived only drawbacks either for themselves or for other Sydneysiders.. (Watt, 2003. Pg. 209).

The excerpt above is a classic example of how mega sporting events are anticipated to have positive effects on host countries, but most citizens disagree. Another argument is that mega

sporting events generate tourism (Ojima, Kurachi, Miura and Kawamoto 2016), as these events offer host countries an opportunity to utilize the Olympic to encourage national growth and development, foster an increase in social capital and increased tourism. While this study is not about tourism, it is however, pertinent to make a note that tourism is an integral part of mega sporting events which can produce negative social outcomes for host communities of mega sporting events. According to Postma, Albert and Schmuecker (2017), tourists can pose certain risks to themselves and residents of host communities, especially by causing discomforts for residents, and violating the rights of vulnerable populations in the host cities. This is described by Matheson's (2002) as the crowding effect of congestion that tourism causes. However, other than the negative effects, research evidence shows that sport and tourism also has a role to play in serving development and peace (see Beutler, 2008; Lindsey and Chapman, 2017; Sapkota and Neupane, 2021),

Recently, criticisms about sport having an ability to violate human rights have been on the rise. This is probably most applicable to mega sporting events, because of how a lack of human rights procedures may have resulted in violations in some events sponsored by the Olympic Games or FIFA (Henderson, 2016). There have, however, been denials as regards the extent of human rights violations in these events, but the denials of potential human rights impacts have not reduced the public criticism of human rights violations linked to the staging of mega sporting events. On the contrary, it has increased enormously as these Games continue to record instances of labour exploitation in building infrastructures, forced evictions of residents, exclusion and discrimination against vulnerable groups, excessive police violence or the use of child labour in the production of sporting goods (Lunacek, 2017). These violations are not in line with the Olympic and Olympism value. Especially because, in the past twenty four years, there has been a united front to rebrand

and use the Olympic for development and peace (Kidd, 2008; Darnell, Giulianotti, Howe and Collison, 2018), especially in the updated Olympic Charter.

In this section, I have established that the Olympic Games can be categorized as a mega sporting event based on a number of factors such as their ability to generate media attention, size and impact. As an important mega sporting event, with global participation and audience, the Olympic Games, in their policy, talks of non-discrimination and equality in sport, however, has not until recently recorded specificity about human rights. In the next section, I discuss in-depth the Olympic Games, concept, movement and the fundamental principles of Olympism, as it relates to my study.

3.3. The Olympic Games and the concept of Olympism

Historically, the Olympic Games began about 3000 years ago (Toohey and Veal, 2007). Originally designed for religious reasons, the Games have consistently celebrated physical excellence across all historical timeframe (ancient and modern). Even though the modern day Olympic is discussed more, of late, as noted by Miah and Garcia (2012), the Olympic Movement is made up of different elements, and the history of modern Olympic Games should be treated as just one part of these elements because the history of modern day Olympic is incomplete without the ancient Olympic Games. And understanding the history of ancient Olympics Games helps to understand the concept of Olympism, which is an integral part of the modern Olympic movement. In their word:

An overview of the history of the Olympics reveals why the Olympic Games must be treated as just one part of what is described as the Olympic movement, the work of which extends far beyond Olympic sports competitions, medal rankings or doping issues. Indeed, the work of the movement encompasses such areas as international diplomacy, peace advocacy, and developing strategies and programmes to address a range of social concerns such as gender equality and human rights in sports. Understanding the relationship between the ancient and modern Games provides an insight into the relationship between the Olympics and today's global society. In turn, this insight helps to explain why the Olympic Games have become the most important mega-event of all time (Miah and Garcia, 2012. Pg. 1)

Concepts of the modern Olympism were created and adopted by Pierre de Coubertin, at the end of the nineteenth century (Petrie, 2017). These fundamental principles are captured in the Olympic Charter. Principle 1 proposes Olympism to be:

A philosophy of life, exalting and combining in a balanced whole the qualities of body, will and mind. Blending sport with culture and education, Olympism seeks to create a way of life based on the joy found in effort, the educational value of good example and respect for universal fundamental ethical principles (Olympic Charter, 2020. pg 9)

According to Fundamental principle 2:

The goal of Olympism is to place everywhere sport at the service of the harmonious development of man, with a view to encouraging the establishment of a peaceful society concerned with the preservation of human dignity. To this effect, the Olympic Movement engages, alone or in cooperation with other organizations and within the limits of its means, in actions to promote peace (Olympic Charter, 2020. Pg.9).

A central component of events such as the Olympic Games is the idea that via the philosophy of Olympism, the Olympic Games promotes respect and world peace (Teetzel, 2012). However, there is the question of how the Olympic Charter and Olympism have, and continue to address and promote human rights, despite the Olympic Charter's emphasis on ethic principles Lenskyj (2004).

In examining how Olympism contributes to human rights, Brown (2009) highlighted the role and mission of the IOC to the tenets of human rights. Historically, in 1991 the IOC thoroughly made changes to the Olympic Charter, and the concepts were made to reflect important values befitting for the public, such as world peace, human rights, inclusion, education, sports and culture (Lopes dos Santos, Goncalves, Condessa, Nunes da Silva and Delaplace (2021). Present reviews show that the modern Olympic Games' relationship with human rights has evolved in step with society's evolving conception of human rights. This evolution is clearly illustrated by the Olympic system's attitude toward human rights, as it requires that human rights be considered in future editions of the Games (from 2024) given society's increasing concern for human rights (Chappelet, 2021).

More specifically, shortly before the Tokyo 2020 Games, the IOC had relaxed Rule 50 of the Olympic Charter with a focus on the right to freedom of expression (Goh, 2021).

According to the principles enshrined in the Olympic Charter, the Olympic Games aspire to contribute to social change on a mass scale, cutting across the interests of numerous stakeholders (Girginov, 2012), led by the International Olympic Committee (IOC). Since the IOC constituted itself on 23rd June 1894, it has been an integral part of the Olympic Movement. The Olympic Charter states that the Olympic movement, led by the IOC, stems from modern Olympism (Olympic Charter, 2020). As argued by Thorpe and Wheaton (2011), an important issue for the contemporary Olympic Movement is how to remain relevant to younger generations considering the diminishing numbers of viewers. However, Thorpe and Wheaton (2011), also note that the IOC overcame this concern by adding a selection of youth-oriented action sports into the Olympic programme, thereby encouraging physical youth participation in the Olympic Games. This was evident in how London 2012 introduced child/youth participation in the policies guiding the Games. As evidenced in the Olympic Charter, inclusion and youth participation is one of the ideals of the Olympism philosophy:

The goal of the Olympic movement is to contribute to building a peaceful and better world by educating youth through sport practiced without discrimination of any kind and in the Olympic spirit, requires mutual understanding with a spirit of friendship, solidarity and fair play (Olympic Charter, 2020. Pg. 15).

Despite the ideals in the Olympic Charter, the idea of Olympism being a philosophy has been widely critiqued. As stated by Culpan and Meier (2016), generally, criticisms of Olympism focus on its association with the Olympic Games. Given that the mandate of the Games is to celebrate the concept of Olympism, scholars argue that the Games have been so far removed from the ideals of Olympism. This was perfectly captured by Arnold (1996) who noted that even though the Olympism movement is a wholesome movement, the ideology of Olympism has been found to be

a manipulative ideology whose driving force is a search for power, prestige and profit. One of the major tenets of Olympism is to promote the concept of Olympism through sport worldwide. However, critics have also argued that the behaviours and practices of the IOC and the political economy of sport through its commodification are so far removed from this concept that such a mission now lacks authenticity (Lenksj, 2012; Wamsley, 2004; cited by Culpan and Meier, 2016).

Another argument against the philosophy of Olympism is that of generality and universality. According to Parry (2006), the concept of Olympism operates at a high level of generality. This means that the general ideas that make up its meaning enable contesting interpretations. As regards the universality of Olympism, Parry (2006:188) referred to it as “the universal pretensions of Olympism”. As argued by Parry (2006), the context in which the universal (a universalistic) pretension of Olympism could have made sense is in the context of globalization. This is because, according to Parry (2006), the concept of Olympism will find different expressions in time, place and geography, unique to itself and culture. This was the case in the Tokyo 2020 Games. According to Kohe, Aramaki, Sekine, Masumoto and Hsu (2021), there were discussions among Tokyo Olympic stakeholders regarding the need for a domestically appropriate programme version for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

Despite the criticisms of Olympism discussed above, Parry (2006) argues that one benefit of this philosophy is that it is all encompassing in the sense that it accounts for all facets of sociality and activity:

This philosophy has as its focus of interest not just the elite artist but everyone. Not just a short truce period but the whole life, not just competition and winning but also the values of participation and cooperation, sport not just as an activity but also as a formative and developmental influence contributing to desirable characteristics of individual and personality and social life (Parry, 2006. Pg. 190).

While speaking further on the concept of Olympism being encompassing, Parry (2006) also describes Olympism as a social philosophy that emphasizes the role of sport in global culture, international understanding, peaceful coexistence, and social and moral education. Drawing on the construction and enactment of Olympism fostering moral education. Example of this is the Tokyo 2020 organising committee's commitment to education (Kohe, et al. 2021). This, according to Dacosta (2006), speaks to the adaptability of Olympism. Parry (2006) argues that the ability for Olympism to be generalized is a good thing, as the theoretical aspect of Olympism must keep evolving for the practical aspect to uphold the Olympic values:

If the practice of sport is to be pursued and developed according to the Olympic values, the theory must strive for a conception of Olympism that will support the practice. The ideal should seek both to sustain sport practices and sports culture and to lead sport toward a vision of Olympism that will help deal with the challenges that are bound to emerge (Parry, 2006. Pg. 191).

Fundamentally, the principles of Olympism encourage human rights, participation, education and equality. However, there is the question as to whether Olympism and the Olympic Games have been committed to human rights.

The contemporary task of the IOC is to commit itself to organising the Olympic Games in alliance with the National Organising Committees (NOC) in such a way that the fundamental principles of Olympism are respected, including political neutrality. This connotes that each Olympic Games should be organised and delivered without discrimination, in line with Fundamental Principle's 4 and 6:

The practice of sports is a human right. Every individual must have the possibility of practising sport, without discrimination of any kind and in the Olympic Spirit, which requires mutual understanding with a Spirit of friendship, solidarity and fair play (Olympic Charter, 2020. Pg. 11).

The enjoyment of the rights and freedoms set forth in this Olympic Charter shall be secured without discrimination of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, sexual orientation, language,

religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status (Pg. 12).

There are concerns about how well this has developed in the past ten years, particularly because cases of infringements continue to be recorded in the Olympic Games. Furthermore, the principles of Olympism suggest that each Olympic Games should be organised and delivered with political neutrality, in line with Fundamental Principle 5:

Recognizing that sport occurs within the framework of society, sports organizations within the Olympic Movement shall apply political neutrality. They have the rights and obligations of autonomy, which include freely establishing and controlling the rules of sport, determining the structure and governance of their organizations, enjoying the right of elections free from any outside influence and the responsibility for ensuring that principles of good governance be applied (Pg. 11).

Again, there are concerns as regards politics in the Olympic Games, especially amongst the IOC, where members of the IOC have been influenced by political affiliations (see Matheson, Schwab and Koval, 2018). Finally, the Fundamental Principles of Olympism also recognizes the Olympic Movement and the leadership of the IOC. This is evident in Fundamental Principle 3 and 7. Fundamental principle 7 describes the Olympic movement as:

The concerted, organised, universal and permanent action, carried out under the supreme authority of the IOC, of all individuals and entities who are inspired by the values of Olympism. It covers the five continents. It reaches its peak with the bringing together of the world's athletes at the great sports festival, the Olympic Games. Its symbol is five interlaced rings (Pg. 11)

As evident in the quote above, the contemporary task of the Olympic Movement is to further the project of seeing clearly what the Games (and sport in a wider society) might come to mean (Parry, 2006), under the leadership of the IOC. One important aspect of setting out the context of the Olympic Games in relation to how human rights might be more effectively foregrounded in the bidding process. This process has been described by Booth (2011) as a complex set of power

relationships between the IOC and the candidate cities. In the next section I discuss the bidding process for the Olympics, in relation to human rights.

3.4. The Olympic Games: bidding through the lens of human rights

In chapter one, it was discussed that one of the factors that make events mega is the complexity in delivery, as well as in the planning. The Olympic, an example of mega sporting event, holds every four years, and can be described as complex, because of its dynamics, influence peddling and other activities (Roche, 2000). These activities, especially influence peddling, have become particularly strategic, over the years, given the importance of global engagement in the modern age. According to Rowe (2012), hosting the Olympic Games requires a substantial commitment, and a substantial engagement with global civil society because of the voluntary, high-mediated exposure of host cities and nations to the world. Much more importantly, the philosophy of Olympism requires ethical authority in demonstrating “fitness” to host the Games, so intensive strategic image management and global engagement is needed (Rowe, 2012).

The Olympic Games have been held for over one hundred years and have significant consequences for the host cities (Chalkley and Essex, 1999). Generally, the bidding process involves submitting bid documents to the IOC. However, Shimizu (2014) has argued that sometimes, the bidding process is more than merely document submission. This connotes that bidding for the Olympic Games can be political, even though the Olympic Charter stated that each society, sport organization within the Olympic Movement should apply political neutrality (see Olympic Charter, 2020. Pg. 11). For example, Ditcher (2021) observed that London 2012 and Tokyo 2020 had direct government involvement in the organizing committees. Similarly, in an article describing the Tokyo bid for the Olympics, Shimizu (2014) noted clear involvement of government officials in the bidding process to host both the 2016 and 2020 Olympics. As such, he argued that it is obvious that the various expectations of sport, recently, are political in nature.

As the highest profile genre among mega sporting events, the Olympic Games is virtually unassailable as an event of continuous public attention and discussion. Hiller and Wanner (2011) have attributed this to the Games being an intriguing mixture of sport, politics, and commerce (Hiller and Wanner, 2011). For different reasons such as how much public funds are invested in it, some host city members oppose their cities bid to host the Games. For example, in the case of Vancouver, some groups were opposed to the city bidding and hosting the winter Olympic Games.

As explained by Hiller and Wanner (2011):

Some organized groups (e.g No Games 2010, Olympic Resistance Network) and politicians were opposed to hosting the Games from the Outset (Shaw, 2008 cited by Hiller and Wanner, 2011). Criticisms ranged from anticipated displacement of the poor and a sense of misplaced priorities given other pressing government expenditures to aboriginal concerns, opposition to constructions projects such as the over-budget Convention Centre to house the media, and reaction to the heavy hand of the organizing committee (pg. 887).

Also, similarly, Canadian cities ceased to go ahead with bids due to protests (Macintosh, 1996 cited by Ribeiro and Correia, 2021), because of the intended impacts on residents. As evident in the observations by these scholars, most of the opposition arose because of the anticipated negative social impacts, which most governments tend to overlook in the bidding process.

MacAloon (2020) notes that the bidding crisis (cities pulling out from bidding) has forced the IOC to set out an agenda (Agenda 2020) for reforms to reduce the level of negative economic and social impacts on bidding cities and residents of bidding cities. MacAloon (2020) goes on to note that even though the Agenda 2020 reforms were applied to the Tokyo 2020 bid process, it is too soon to tell if the changes resulting from the Agenda 2020 has put an end to the bidding crisis. Pending the assessment of the Agenda 2020 reforms, significant negative outcomes in other sporting events continue to be highlighted by academics, especially as regards the unintended impacts of bidding and delivery, on host cities. Though unquestionably, the Games also have positive impacts on host cities, but as earlier discussed, human rights infringements still occur and according to Aina et al

(2021), to mitigate this, human rights should be foregrounded when bidding for the Olympic Games. One way this can be actualized is by embedding human rights and child rights specifics in the host city contract. According to Heerdt (2018) in November 2017, FIFA publicized the changes to their bidding requirements for 2026, which clearly introduced clauses of human rights protection. Bidding is an important aspect of mega sporting events because it is the stage where contractual obligations are developed, hence, if rights, especially child rights, are not mentioned at the bidding stage, then it will be more difficult to follow through on both human rights and child rights expectations later.

3.5. Child Rights and the Olympics

The issue of child rights has become prevalent in the Olympic Games in the past 20 years, as the Olympic Games and other mega sporting events have had allegations of human rights and child rights abuses levelled at their organizers, in recent decades (Talbot and Carter, 2016). As mentioned in chapter 1 (Section 1.5), children are particularly affected by the planning and delivery of mega sporting events. Evidence show that there were violations connected to the planning and delivery of mega sporting events (Aina et al. 2021). According to Aina et al. (2021), many a times, organizations indicate children to be principal recipients of several motivating outcomes of the Olympic Games, although this is not necessarily always the case. As evidenced by Wong (2011), children can be violated and abuses at all stages of the Olympics planning and delivery. To illustrate this, it was evidenced that the London 2012 had instances of child labour (Wong, 2011). Despite recent efforts to blend sport and human rights, activism for children's rights in mega sporting events have historically been marginalised because the positive "social legacy" of sport events frequently masks more problematic issues, including child exploitation (Brankenridge, Rhind and Palmer – Felgate, 2014. Pp. 237). According to Dowse et al (2018) the impact of rights marginalisation on children as a particular stakeholder group reflects a knowledgeable gap. This

is probably why campaign groups have called on the IOC to urgently change its host city contract to place human rights and child rights at their heart, after the Rio 2016 Olympics (Gibson, 2016). The study of safeguarding children in sport continues to see an increase in scientific study. Furthermore, there is also an increasing emphasis on how child rights protection needs to be well represented in policies. Rodriguez, Van Blerk, Fernandes, Mendel, Rizzini, McEleavy and Fyfe (2016) argue that bidding and hosting processes should also specifically require children's rights in the bidding process (pp. 80), thus providing a framework, through policies, that ensures that child rights are adequately provided for. However, when child rights protection in sporting events is viewed in the light of the IOC being specific about child rights protections in their policies, there arises the issue of compliance by event workers and organizers. It is one thing to provide a policy that addresses child rights protection and develop a framework for event organizers to follow in making sure that child rights are safeguarded, but it is another thing for the necessary stakeholders to practically stick to the framework. The prevalence of child rights violations in mega sporting events, goes beyond violence, sexual harassment and abuse (Brackenridge et. al, 2012), which is why there needs to be a level of proactiveness. There are also issues of forceful removals and child labour (Dowse et. al., 2018) which, sometimes, accompany preparations for the Olympic Games. The IOC has been blamed for the violation of human rights including child rights violations associated with the Olympic Games, because it has not been intentional about these rights, especially when it comes to the policies guiding the Games. The IOC has responded to criticism by ensuring that human rights specifics are now being added to the host city contract by embedding human rights specifics in the Paris 2024 and Los Angeles 2028 Olympic Games. However, prior to 2017, the IOC had been criticised for not directly engaging with human rights and child rights issues. These include failure to involve children in decision-making, while also failing to formalise child rights in the blueprint of the Games (Aina et al. 2021). As for the IOC's engagement and

response to child rights issues, all indications point to the need for more engagement and responses to issues that have been raised in the past, and issues that might come up in the future. The IOC's engagement and response to some rights issues is important to discuss as this sets the background for the theoretical discussion of child rights in chapter five. The next section will discuss this in-depth.

3.6. The International Olympic Committees' response and engagement with child rights

The IOC has had its fair share of controversies and scandalous stories (Chappelet, 2018), and when it comes to the Olympic Games and child rights issues, the involvement of the IOC has always been questioned (Chappelet, 2018), especially in the aspect of child involvement in decision making processes. As earlier mentioned (section 1.5), as noted by Mountjoy et al., (2016), children in sport can experience all forms of harm including psychological, sexual/physical harassment and abuse, as well as neglect implemented through the same mechanisms experienced by adult athletes. This suggests that there is a need for them to be a key part of the governance structure of those events they might be involved in, including sporting events.

Lately, the IOC has made moves to prevent further rights violations in, or related to, the Olympic Games by introducing revised contracts which require that host cities respect and protect human rights. With these two guiding documents: The Olympic Charter (2013) and the Movement Medical Code (2009), Mountjoy et al., (2015) argued that the IOC is being active in its mission to protect the athlete, especially the child athlete. More broadly, agenda 2020 makes numerous recommendations intended to improve the sustainability of the Olympic Games, many of which are relevant to human rights (Talbot, 2022). Similarly, one bold stride for human rights seemed to be made in 2017 when the IOC announced changes to its host city contract, however, since the introduction of the human rights clause in the HCC, there has been limited concrete action from the IOC on human rights (Talbot, 2022). Being active in its protection of rights, however, as

argued (Human Rights Watch, 2019) is more than just writing documents to reflect changes. As stated by Human Rights Watch, (2019), “words on paper would not change practice: implementation and monitoring are essential”. To corroborate this argument Buchanan (2016) notes that there were several records of child rights abuses in Rio, and Beijing Olympic Games (Human Rights Watch, 2019), which took after the revised contracts were introduced. This brings about the question as to how serious the IOC is about assuring that rights violations are avoided in the Olympic Games. According to Buchanan (2016), achieving human rights success is dependent on the level of rights protection activities of the IOC, and the seriousness of the IOC in fulfilling its promises, taking full responsibility for guaranteeing human rights protection, and responding to violations.

Recently, the IOC has noted its commitment to addressing rights issues, albeit, without noting how this might be done. At the 2018 Youth Olympic Games, the IOC raised awareness about its toolkit and directly addressed child athletes to ensure that they were aware about their rights and what constitutes abuse (Ohchr.org, 2019). Also, speaking at the Sporting Chance Forum (SCF 2019), (Bach, 2019) iterates their commitment to human rights ,

The IOC is committed to improving the protection, promotion and respect of human rights, in particular, as these relates to the Olympic games organization. Human rights are in fact firmly anchored in the Olympic Charter, therefore, our mission to put sport at the service of humanity goes hand in hand with human rights. In Olympics sport, all people are equal, regardless of their race, gender, sexual orientation, social status, cultural background or belief. This principle of non-discrimination allows sport to promote peace and understanding among all people because the same rule applies to everybody”.

While human rights are firmly anchored in the Olympic Charter, the aim is to have child rights anchored in the Olympic Charter as well as have child rights recognized as a major part of the Olympism and Olympic value. Studies from chapter two show how the IOC and other sport event committees work in partnership with Human Rights Organizations to develop right protection

policies. However, more still needs to be done if human rights and child rights infringements are to be completely eradicated in mega sporting events.

3.7. Conclusion

A lot has been said about the relevance and impacts of mega sporting events, especially the Olympic Games on residents and host communities (Ritchie, Shipway and Cleeve, 2009). In setting the context of mega sporting events, this chapter has highlighted the common debates around the definitions of mega sporting events. In addition, as this chapter has shown, the impact of these events goes beyond economic impact. Even though major debates about these events tend to centre around economic impacts and the urban regenerative abilities of mega sporting events, I have established in this chapter that there is a direct link between mega sporting events and negative social impacts such as human rights infringements and child rights infringements. Despite the fact there is an increasing awareness about the dimensions of rights infringements, there is also a need for further exploration on the dimensions of rights infringements in mega sporting events, as this will help to reduce potential violations.

As discussed in this chapter, the history of the Olympic Games go way back, and the concept and movement has recorded significant changes over the year. The concept and movement has not been without criticism with most of the criticism being linked to Olympic athletes and the IOC. One of the arguments against Olympism which has gained traction, over the years, is that of generality and universality. Despite the arguments against this, Parry (2006) has noted that it allows different nations form an expression that is unique to their culture, history and projected future, and also enables education processes. An example of how this is beneficial to nations, as evidenced in this chapter, is the Tokyo 2020 Games. As observed by Kohe et al. (2021), the Tokyo 2020 stakeholders designed Olympic Games that were domestically appropriate. This shows that the Olympic Games owners can be flexible enough to accommodate positive changes, as regards

embedding adequate human and child rights protection measures in the policies and principles guiding the Games. Much concern remains with the leadership of the Olympic Games (the IOC) and their willingness to proactively take the lead by making changes to the bid process. Evidently, the planning stage of any mega sporting event should not be neglected, if positive outcomes are to be recorded during and after the delivery of each mega sporting event. Much more than an intensive strategic image management, sport enjoyment and global engagement, human rights/child strategies should also be an important factor while bidding for the Olympic Games.

The next chapter will focus on this unintended impact of child rights infringements issues in the Olympic Games, it will also highlight the different occurrences of child rights infringements, while also discussing relevant theories and frameworks on how child rights can be adequately provided, and protected in the inception stage of each Olympic Game. This remains a need for children to be safeguarded against abuse in mega sporting events, especially the Olympic Games. The next chapter will discuss how child rights can be provided for, theoretically.

CHAPTER FOUR – CONCEPTUALIZING CHILD RIGHTS: PROTECTION, PROVISION AND PARTICIPATION

4.1. Introduction

Building on the discussion of the Olympic Games and its social impacts in the previous chapter, here I focus on the context of child rights as applicable to the Olympic Games before outlining the factors that have inspired the protection of child rights, so far, in the context of mega sporting events. The discussion of child rights infringements and issues in sport is necessary because it sets the scene for a discussion of theories and frameworks for child rights protection in mega sporting events, especially the Olympic Games. The aim of this study is to assess child rights in mega sporting events, and as evident in the literature review section (chapter two and three), there is a gap in how children are being represented in mega sporting events, especially the Olympic Games. Mega sporting events have the potential to infringe children's rights in diverse ways, hence the need to develop an adequate protection framework. Over the years, there have been several child rights protection mechanisms developed, stemming from the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). While children's rights have been described as an under-theorized field (Freeman, 2012, Quennerstedt, 2013), the (UNCRC) has laid the foundation for how children can be protected. This is evident in the way academics like Lundy (2007) have developed frameworks and participation models that foreground the rights of the child, building on the UNCRC.

Before the conceptual framework guiding this study is outlined, I discuss the history of child rights and the Olympic Games while highlighting instances of child rights infringements. Following this discussion, I outline the frameworks and models that form the conceptual basis of this thesis and inform the presentation and analysis of findings. First, I reflect on the importance of protection and provision as provided by the UNCRC. This is important because the UNCRC is the basis upon which other models and frameworks are built. Second, I discuss the significance of formalizing

child rights agendas in mega sporting events through the development of policies. This will be done using McGillivray et al's (2019) proposed framework for progressive human rights outcomes in mega sporting events. Finally, I discuss strategies for child participation in the Olympic Games, building on Lundy's (2007) participation template.

4.2. Child rights and the Olympic Games

The first part of the UNCRC describes the child as anyone below eighteen. In addition to defining the age group of the child, the UNCRC also stipulates directions as to how children might be properly protected in all sectors (Akinola, 2018). Even though Articles 3 and 12 of the UNCRC set out provisions and inclusion measures (Aina, McGillivray, Carnicelli and McPherson, 2021), there is evidence that marquee sports events continue to generate rights violations or exacerbate existing ones, with children particularly vulnerable. Specifically, with each preparation for the Olympic Games, there is the tendency for child rights violations. As detailed in the introductory chapter (Chapter 1.6), several advocacy organizations including Amnesty International, UNICEF and Terre Des Homme have strongly advocated for children's rights to leisure and play, while also maintaining that every child's rights need to be upheld in all sectors, especially in the sports terrain. Even though the terrain of child rights still calls for more research, previous studies of child rights show that children continue to be exposed to different kinds of violence such as exploitations, child labour, within sport (Brackenridge et al, 2012). Statistically, data from Brazil's hotline for reporting abuse suggests that the number of reported violations against children increased by 17% in the 12 FIFA World Cup host cities during the 2014 competition, compared with the same month in 2013 (The Guardian, 2019). The Rio 2016 Olympic Games also recorded child rights infringements. Citing Terres des Homes (2019), Davies (2019) provided details of how young people were detained despite being innocent of any crime that would justify their internment. Similarly, there were reports of cleaning the streets of homeless children at Rio 2016, and

numerous effects resulting from the eviction of 22,000 families between 2009 and 2015 to clear space for the Games (BBC Sport, 2019). Children that faced forced evictions missed out on school places, moved to dangerous areas, and lost contact with friends and the social fabric of their previous communities (Childrenwin.org, 2019). In the context of mega sporting events, children’s rights can be impacted both directly and indirectly through how their parents or caregivers, their community, or their societies are affected. This is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Range of impacts that can occur on the child before, during and after an MSE. Source: (Sportaide.ca, 2017)

Figure 1 shows that violations can occur at all stages of a mega sporting event. Analysing Figure 1 in the context of child rights, violations to child rights can be in various forms, including economic, environmental, social, structural and cultural. Even though these violations are important and relevant, for the purpose of this study the focus is on the structural form of violation. These are

violations that occur because of neglect in the bidding and planning phases, specifically, because of lack of legal protection and provision of child rights in the planning phase of mega sporting events. According to Aina et. al (2021) child rights commitments have not been fully enshrined as parts of the plans and strategies in the documents guiding the delivery of the Olympic Games. They went further to assert that the reason why there's a lack of child rights agenda developed in respect of the Olympic Games is because the IOC has not made it a bidding requirement before the Tokyo 2020 Games. According to Aina et al. (2021), despite the fact that child rights protection guidelines were stipulated in the UNCRC, as far back as 1989, organizations and appropriate signatories still struggle to completely follow the guidelines. The violation of child rights in the Olympic Games is an ongoing issue that needs to be addressed from a holistic point of view. Considering the potential child rights impact of mega sporting events, especially in the Olympic Games (as seen in Figure 1), is of particular importance for children (Sportaide.ca, 2017). Several scholars have argued that expanding the embedding child rights specifics in the policies and principles of the Olympic Games would help champion the cause of child rights protection (see Aina et. al, 2021; Dowse et. al, 2018). Similarly, the *Children's Rights in Sports Principles* published by UNICEF in 2018 recommended that sport organizations, such as organizers of mega sporting events and the IOC, should work out and develop child rights compliance mechanisms, specified for the Olympics, as this would hold host cities accountable to ensuring child rights protection before, during and after hosting mega sporting events. In engaging and responding to rights issues in the Olympic Games, there are very limited reports of the IOC taking action. As for the IOC's engagement and response to child rights issues, all indications point to the need for more engagement and responses to issues that have been raised in the past, and issues that might come up in the future. The IOC's engagement and response to child rights issues is discussed in the next section.

4.2. The IOC and child rights

When human rights infringements are reported in and around the Olympic Games, it is usually the IOC that gets scrutinized and criticized. According to Kidd (2010), the IOC continues to appear complicit on human rights violations, which sets them up for constant scrutiny and criticism. For example, in Beijing 2008, the IOC rather than China, received the harshest criticism in the build up to the Games (Kidd, 2010). Frequent media criticism and calls for greater human rights protection have improved the IOC's intentionality about human rights protection in the Olympic Games. In the past five years the IOC has been noticeably more intentional towards human rights, though more can still be done. For example, in March 2019, the IOC commissioned a strategic framework on human rights to be developed over the course of a year that would include human rights strategies. To effectualise this, the IOC executive board consented to:

Establish a Human Rights Unit with expert leadership to elaborate and drive the detailed strategy in practice, in close collaboration with key departments that will be essential to delivering the IOC's commitment (IOC, 2020).

For protection of rights and abuse in sport, the IOC has also agreed to implement an approach that will continue to strengthen human rights due diligence. This will take place using leverage and engagement with affected stakeholders in existing areas of work, including the IOC's efforts on the prevention of harassment and abuse in sport, engagement with Olympic Games Organizing Committees on human rights impacts and in the organization's own procurement processes (IOC, 2020).

Tarrant (2018) notes that at the conclusion of a two-day executive board meeting in Tokyo, IOC President Thomas Bach stated that all Games host city candidates beyond 2024 will have to meet strict human rights criteria. This commitment is corroborated by Terre Des Hommes (2020), who commended the IOC for adding human rights criteria into the 2024 (Paris) and 2028 (Los Angeles) Olympic host city contracts. However, they also expressed concerns as to how these criteria will

be implemented, and criticized the absence of dialogue from the IOC on human rights and how child rights were neglected in the official bids by Paris and Los Angeles. It is also worthy to note that the new host city contracts do not apply to Olympic Games which have been previously awarded, including Tokyo 2020 (Terre Des Hommes, 2020). As a result, the IOC has less influence over Tokyo 2020 in the sphere of child rights protection than it will for future iterations. There has also been criticism that the IOC's statements committing to safeguarding human rights are insufficient and has not followed due diligence (Willett, 2020). This criticism aligns with Terre Des Homme's (2020) concerns as to how human rights promises would be implemented (Terre Des Hommes, 2020).

While the IOC's move to strengthen its commitments, including human rights requirements in host city contracts is commendable, it is also inadequate as there are no requirements for child rights protection measures, nor are their efforts to enforce human rights requirements. To enforce the Olympic Games host city's human rights obligations, Willett (2020) notes that the IOC needs an independent monitoring body for its rights issues. Based on Terre Des Hommes' call for the IOC's need to focus on human rights in Tokyo 2020, they argued that now the IOC have taken this important initial step, it is time to specifically focus on human rights around mega events in South Korea, Japan and China (Terre Des Hommes, 2020).

As stated on (Olympic News, 2020) as part of the Olympic Agenda 2020 reforms, human rights standards have already been reinforced in the operational requirements of the *Host City Contract*. Setting out its role to advance respect for human rights as the leader of the Olympic Movement, the IOC is also aiming to work closely with the National Olympic Committees (NOCs) and the international Federations (Olympic News, 2020).

However, it is still unclear where the IOC stands with respect to child rights protection. In 2005, the IOC released a consensus statement for child athletes. The consensus, amidst other things, made recommendations for training child athletes in favourable environments and situations:

Elite child athletes deserve to train and compete in a suitable environment supported by a variety of age-appropriate technical and tactical training methods, rules, equipment, facilities and competitive formats.

Elite child athletes deserve to train and compete in a pleasurable environment, free from drug misuse and negative adult influences, including harassment and inappropriate pressure from parents, peers, health care providers, coaches, media, agents and significant other parties (IOC, 2005).

Even though this consensus did not cover child volunteers or child viewers, the consensus marked the start of greater intentionality towards child athletes in the Olympic Games. The consensus being a recommendation, rather than a legally binding document for host cities, is a move towards elite child rights protection in the Olympic Games. The entire sports process for the elite child athlete should be pleasurable and fulfilling (IOC, 2005). Similarly, three years after releasing the consensus on training the child athlete, the IOC also released a consensus statement on sexual harassment and abuse in sport. In this statement, the IOC recognized that sexual harassment and abuse occurs in sporting events. In an article detailing the consensus statement (Ljungqvist, Mountjoy, Brackenridge, Arrington, Blauwet, Carska-Sheppard, and Budgett, 2008) stated that prevention strategies must “include policies with associated codes of practice, education and training, complaint and support mechanisms, as well as monitoring and evaluation systems” (p.445). While the consensus statement did not speak specifically to children, it noted that sexual harassment in sport is not limited to age, gender, race, sexual orientation and cultural backgrounds. More recently, in response to Human Rights Watch’s report about child abuse in Japan, the IOC said in a statement:

We acknowledge the Human Rights Watch report. Harassment and abuse is unfortunately part of the society and also occurs within sport. The IOC stands together with all athletes, everywhere, to state that abuse of any kind is contrary to the values of Olympism, which calls for respect for everyone in sport (BBC, 2020).

As evident in this section, the IOC is aware of the debates around child rights and violations in the Olympic Games, However, there has been insufficient commitment from them to ensure that host cities adhere to the UNCRC in the delivery of the Games. In addition, there has been no requirement by the IOC to ensure that host cities include child rights safeguarding measures in the Olympic Games planning documents. As noted by McGillivray et. al. (2019), transparency and inclusiveness of structures before and during the bidding stage would go a long way to ensure that child rights are safeguarded. They proposed that the IOC and event organizers adopt specific models in addressing potential child rights infringements in the Olympic Games. Even though there are different conceptual frameworks that could be used in planning the Olympics, two of these models have been found to be more suitable for this study and the general child rights context because they are developed from a rights perspective. These conceptual models are discussed in-depth below.

4.3. Conceptual model for leveraging child rights in the Olympic Games

Mega sporting events are known to be one of the environments where people and their rights, especially children, are violated . More specifically, there are proofs that past Olympic Games have recorded child rights violations (see Wong, 2011; Caudwell and McGee, 2018). Specifically, records have it that children suffer violations, from the inception of each Olympic Games through to the delivery (Wong, 2011) Wong (2011) cited an example of children being used for mascot productions in preparations for the London 2012 Olympic Games. This is similar to HRW's (2019) assertion that violations to children in the Olympic Games can also include children being the objects of child labour with elite child athletes and child volunteers being objects of corporal punishment. In contrast to the general human rights provisions now evident in policies guiding

mega sporting events, children continue to be relatively invisible when it comes to their rights being adequately embedded and formalised in mega sporting events policies and principles. As Dowse et al. (2018) argue, the fact that children are inconspicuous within mega sporting events organization procedures speak to the thoughtlessness and incomplete nature of some of these processes. The lack of provision for protection is one of the reasons for the ongoing child rights violations in mega sporting events. This brings to fore the question of “who should be responsible for keeping the child from being violated in the planning stages of mega sporting events?”. While some of the child rights abuses experienced in mega sporting events are related to inadequate provisions for rights protection, according to Heerdt (2018), most of the remaining challenges of access to remedy for mega sporting events rights abuses seem to relate to the enforceability of provisions. These challenges come to the fore when more detailed questions are asked about what provisions for child rights protections are in place for the Olympic Games, whether these provisions are formulated in a way that they can be enforced, which actors can act based on these provisions, and finally what mechanisms are provided to enforce these provisions.

The UNCRC has laid out certain assumptions as regards child protection. Article 19 details the significance of safeguarding the child from being violated. However, as evident in policies and mega sporting events guidelines, the UNCRC expectations and UNICEF principles for child rights protections are yet to be fully embraced. Brackenridge, Rhind and Palmer-Felgates (2015) in an article about mitigating risks to children in mega sporting events, while detailing the risks associated to children, identified that child protection is still a political blind spot for most organising committees and host communities. Thus, there is pressing need for action by those responsible for commissioning and staging mega sporting events, including FIFA, the IOC, governments, and civil society, to anticipate, prepare for, and adopt risk-mitigation strategies and interventions in relation to children Brackenridge et. al (2015).

It is important to acknowledge that mega sporting events can also have positive impacts on children (Dowse, Powell and Weed, 2018), but the way they are planned often enhance the possibilities of child rights encroachments. According to McGillivray et al (2019), in mega sporting events such as the Olympic Games, it is essential for the IOC to include rights protection fundamentals in the blueprints of the Olympic Games, while also seeing to it that partners act on these principles. This would also have the effect of raising human rights up to the level of other Games prerequisites. To help conceptualise mitigating human rights risks in mega sporting events, McGillivray et al. (2019) developed a conceptual model for delivering sport events that lever human rights.

McGillivray et al's (2019) model presents four pathways to actualize a rights-based mega sporting event (Figure 2). This model will be adapted for this research, as the pathways provide a guiding structure as to who and when interventions are necessary to ensure child rights are foregrounded.

Figure 2: Conceptual model for rights-based MSE governance. Source: McGillivray et al. (2019).

Figure 2 presents the conceptual model for how positive human rights outcomes may be obtained through the implementation of four specific pathways. McGillivray et al (2019) argue that if these pathways are followed, then the potential for progressive social change will be higher compared to a situation in which these factors are not considered. First, the model proposes that organizers need to ensure that the rights of vulnerable groups are recognized and protected – starting from the vision stage onwards, as has been the case recently for general human rights. In January 2017, the IOC made a commitment to incorporate human rights principles in its Host City Contract (HCC), a binding agreement between the awarding body and the host city. Not only did the IOC make a commitment to incorporate human rights, it included an explicit reference to the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGP) and enshrined these within the HCC

(McGillivray et. al, 2019). This implies that human rights measures have to be adhered to, by host cities, by obligation. Even though the new IOC policies and adapted HCC covers human rights which would, by extension, cover child rights these are not often explicitly mentioned in the general human rights context. In corroboration of the recommendation to recognize and protect rights of vulnerable people from the planning stage, Aina et al (2021) argued that this is needed if positive child rights outcomes are to be recorded in the delivery of subsequent Olympic Games.

Second, McGillivray et. al (2019) propose that developing practices of democratisation and voice provide the best environment to protect and advance the cause of child rights in mega sporting events. An idea well aligned with Lundy's (2007) model of participation, where she argues for affected stakeholders being given a voice in the decision-making processes governing the organization of the Olympic Games. In their conceptual model, McGillivray et. al (2019) highlight the importance of stakeholder engagement. They argue that meaningful stakeholder engagement can help advance the democratisation of the mega sporting events planning process and improving levels of public participation in the decision-making process, informed by a rights-based agenda. This also supports Donnelly's (2013) argument that a normalization of sport where athletes participation in governance is encouraged can be productive.

Third, McGillivray et al's (2019) conceptual model proposes the formalisation of the rights agenda in the guidelines of the Games, clarifying and strengthening the accountability of host cities and other stakeholders for delivering human rights-leveraged events. Formalisation, according to Leifsen (2008), infers a kind of cooperation between state actors, lawyers and citizens. This has become a key issue in development policies between governments, law and policy makers, the judiciary and civil society (Ikdal, Hellum, Kaarhhus and Benjaminsen, 2005) to secure human rights, or child rights in sport, especially in the context of the Olympic Games. As noted by

Donnelly (2008), children should be significant enough to have their rights stated in the policies of the Olympic Games if violations towards them are to be avoided.

Finally, the model proposes a change management plan. This model argues that it is important for mega sporting events organizers develop initiatives to safeguard their underaged populations. Even though there is a lack of a holistic children's rights agenda that increases the likelihood of improved outcomes in legal practices and in sport (Eliasson, 2017), there are existing rights-based models and frameworks which can be adapted to fulfil child rights provision and protection requirements. An example, as stated in section 4.3 is the McGillivray et al (2019) conceptual framework. In order to achieve a holistic human rights outcome, this conceptual framework model can be combined with Lundy's (2007) model of participation. More importantly, there is a need to develop a holistic child rights framework which host cities and event organizers can adapt when planning the Olympic Games. The ambition, based on the argument and conceptual framework adopted by this study, is to approach child rights in sport from a rights perspective. In the next section I discuss Lundy's (2007) participation model and its relevance to this study.

4.4. Children's rights-based participation model for planning the Olympics

While McGillivray et al (2019) model emphasizes the importance of formalising rights in policies and documents guiding mega sporting events, another conceptual standpoint that aligns with this commitment to foregrounding rights is Lundy's (2007) child participation model. The UNCRC is a landmark in the history of child rights, and has become the crucial framework upon which child protection and child participation is built. Despite the succinct outlined principles showing the pathway to a "supposed" holistic approach to child protection, there have been debates about how holistic the UNCRC is about child participation. According to Pais (2000), the UNCRC, while acknowledging that the child is a vulnerable human being that requires protection and assistance from the family, the society and the state, the UNCRC also envisaged the child as a subject of

rights. More aptly, the UNCRC recognizes that a child can form and express opinions, participate in decision-making processes and influence solutions, intervening as a partner in the process of social change and in the building up of democracy. Lansdown (2010), on the other hand believes that even though the UNCRC's model of child protection is encompassing, the idea of participation (decision-making) reflected in Article 12 needs more clarification and reflection, as the UNCRC did not specifically outline the many different dimensions of child participation. In Tisdal's (2015) view, child participation in the UNCRC is not limited to Article 12, a range of UNRC articles are grouped together as participation rights. These include Article 13 (freedom of expression), Article 14 (freedom of thought, conscience and religion), Article 15 (freedom of association and peaceful assembly) and Article 17 (access to information), and Article 12, which encourages freedom of decision-making (Tisdall, 2015).

Child participation in mega sporting events has been an important aspect of hosting mega events, such as the Olympic Games. While a great deal of effort has been spent on developing fun, engaging ways of encouraging children to physically participate in projects and events, without addressing wider contextual issue (Tisdall, 2015) such as their inability to be a part of the decision-making processes of the events they will be physically participating in. Different models have been developed to address some of the lack of clarity in Article 12 as regards child participation, as highlighted by Tisdall (2015) and Lansdown (2010). Shier's (2013) pathway to participation proposed five levels of child participation that should be considered by organizations and event organizers. In order of hierarchy, the pathways arranged from level one to five (listening ears, support, action, involvement and power) reflect different participation factors. Although Shier's model presents a hierarchical structure like Hart's ladder, it identifies, at each level of participation, what adults and organizations need to do to involve children in the process by performing the following stages: openings, opportunities and obligations (Duramy and Gal, 2020). Shier (2020)

also noted that one of the criticisms of this model is that its hierarchical nature suggests that some of the factors hold more importance than others. Similarly, Johnson (2011) proposed a change-scape model/framework, with special reference to factors such as communication, institutions, culture, policies, environment and collaboration as things that may influence child participation. According to Tisdall (2015), this model is overly complex.

Article 12 of the UNCRC, uniquely within the international law, gives children the right to express their views but also have those views taken seriously in all matters affecting them. A simple, but effective way of understanding how this is obtainable has been conceptualised by Lundy (2007). As evident in Shier (2013) and Johnson's (2011) models, child participation models have been developed from different perspectives. The former proposed their model from an organisational point of view, while Johnson's (2011) model was proposed from a socio-cultural point of view. Evidently, both models are not rights based, as they do not address the fact that it is the right of a child to be heard, as highlighted in the UNCRC and argued by Lundy (2007). Lundy, McEvoy and Byrne (2011) argued that acknowledging children as rights-holders has significant implications for research processes. They also note that the distinctiveness of a children's right informed approach to research is a focus not only on safe, inclusive and engaging opportunities for children to express their views but also on deliberate strategies to assist children in the formation of their views. According to Howard and Madrigal (1990), it is not unusual for parents to be called upon to give their inputs about issues that concern their children; however, there is also a need to give the child a chance to speak for themselves, if they can (Aina et al., 2021). Lundy (2007) designed a model for conceptualizing Article 12, which captures its two elements of children's right to express their own opinions and their right to have such opinions consolidated (Duramy and Gal, 2020). A perfect illustration of this is seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Conceptualising Article 12: Lundy (2007)

The Lundy model of participation (2007) was developed to aid practitioners to meaningfully and effectively implement child’s right to participate by focusing attention on the distinct but interrelated elements of Article 12 (Kennan, Brady and Forkan, 2019). For full realization of the principle of child participation, decision makers need to consider the following four factors and their relationship with the two elements of Article 12 and the four provisions below: Space, Voice, Audience, and Influence.

Space suggests that children must be given the opportunity to express a view, even though it has been argued by Bae (2009) that official documents are no guarantee that children will be allowed space to take part on their own terms and meet respect for their various expressions. However, Lundy (2007) has suggested that the child’s ability to speak, and not fear for his safety, on issues

concerning them is a step in the right direction. In addition, it is in the best interest of the child. Voice means that children must be facilitated to express their views. According to Zumbachi, Saini and Koglin (2021), historically children's voices have been largely absent from scientific investigation, as well as within legal decisions affecting their lives. Results of a study conducted by Lundy, McEvoy and Byrne (2011) suggest that an explicit UNCRC informed approach of giving the child a voice has great benefits. One of the primary reasons for the development of the Lundy Model was to drive home that voice is not enough. Lundy sought to stress that children and young people have a right to audience (Kennan, Brady and Forkan, 2019)

While audience imposes the obligation that views of children must be listened to, in matters that concern them, influence implies that these views must be acted upon, as appropriate (Duramy and Gal, 2020). The use of the term influence in the Lundy model encapsulates the concept of "due weight" as expressed in Article 12 of the UNCRC (Kennan et al, 2019) which opines that the child's view be given due weight in accordance with their age and maturity. According to Allan and Luders (2021), children need to be recognized as participants. Further, in this study, the McGillivray pathway provides guidance on pathways to how children can be effectively included temporarily, while Lundy provides a detailed guide to how children can be involved in participation and decision making.

4.5 Conclusion

Despite the growing importance of different approaches to mega sporting events, limited research has been carried out to understand how children participate and can be involved in the decision-making processes associated with planning and delivery of the Olympic Games, especially since they are the firsthand recipients of rights violations. As there is the possibility that with each preparation for the Olympic Games, child rights abuse intensifies, there is a need for a sustainable approach by organizers to ensure that children have their rights protected at all costs.

One of the objectives of this research is to identify and compare the environment of child rights violations in past sporting events of the. Hence, In this chapter, I have highlighted some of the instances of child rights violations that have taken place historically in the Olympic Games. Thus, establishing that despite the calls by human rights organizations and academics, coupled by the IOC's attempt to ensure child rights protection by introducing two revised documentations which specifies the importance of the child protection in sporting events, violations of rights in mega sporting events continue to occur. This suggests that not enough is currently being done to protect the child from abuse in the Olympic Games. It is one thing to specify the importance of protecting the child in policies, however, it is another thing to take practical steps to protect the child. Producing revised documents which specifies the importance of child protection shows that the IOC has come to the awareness of how important it is to protect the child. However, it is not enough to document the importance of protecting the child, the IOC also need to introduce revised documents detailing specific protection measures for children in subsequent Olympic Games, starting with the Olympic Charter. This chapter has established that while there are instances of the IOC engaging and responding to instances of rights violations, the responses do not specify how the IOC plans to ensure this.

In achieving the overall aim of this research, the preceding chapters have reviewed various subtopics, setting the scene on the general human rights landscape, mega sporting events and human rights, the Olympic Games as mega sporting events, child rights violations in sport, and theoretical approaches to providing for child rights. The purpose of the literature review was to identify the important debates around mega sporting events, the Olympic Games, human rights and child rights. Furthermore, the literature review was conducted to lay a background for the remaining aspects of the study. By having a thorough awareness and understanding of current work and concepts in the key areas of child rights and mega sporting events, as previously mentioned, I

am able to position this research clearly on the academic map of knowledge creation (Ridley, 2012), especially in the conceptual dimension of child rights in relations to mega sporting events. Although all the models and conceptual frameworks discussed in this chapter expressed the importance of children having a voice, none of these concepts was developed specifically for mega sporting events. This presents a limitation for how participation and provision for protection can be understood, conceptually, when applied to this study. The Lundy Model, on the other hand, is preferred for this study because of its in-depth exploration of child participation factors – Voice, Space, Audience and Influence. In addition, this model has been previously applied to studies with a focus on child rights in sporting events. Despite the fact that the Lundy model was preferred and applied, the model is not holistic. As an offshoot of this, this study proposes an holistic participation, protection and provision framework for assessing child rights. This will be discussed later on in this study.

Now, the methodology chapter will discuss in detail the philosophical approach adopted for this research, the research strategies and the respective methodological approaches undertaken to carry out this research before the findings and analysis are then presented. As mentioned in the introductory chapter, the research aims to assess child rights in mega sporting events, contextually, in the case of Tokyo 2020 Games. The research also aim to answer these questions: (a) What are the dimensions of child right infringements associated with the Olympic Games? (b) What measures are in place to mitigate children’s rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games? And (c) What are the roles of stakeholders, event organizers, advocacy organizations and event owners in ensuring that the Tokyo 2020 Games are delivered in compliance with the UNCRC?. The next chapter will detail the methodological approaches to answer these questions.

CHAPTER FIVE: METHODOLOGY

5. 1. Introduction

Mega sporting events can produce positive outcomes for cities and countries. As I illustrated in chapter three, the aftermath of hosting the Olympic Games often goes beyond positive outcomes, especially since there are human rights issues associated with hosting these events. Because there has been little focus on child rights in the mega event literature to date, there is a research gap that needs to be addressed by host governments and organizers. Mega sporting events present opportunities to foreground child right issues as they are powerful platforms to promote and advance these agendas (Petry and Müller-Schoell, 2016). However, they also present risks because they can lead to a range of negative impacts for children and their rights (see Florence, Meier and Ignacio, 2016; Rodriguez, Blerk, Fernandes, Mendel, Rizzini, McEleavy, and Fyfe, 2015). The issue of child rights infringement continue to be a topic of discussion by academics and human rights activists, and this study aims to contribute to knowledge in that regard.

Having set the background for human rights and its assessment in relation to child rights protection in chapter four, in this chapter I provide an in-depth discussion as to how the study's research questions will be answered, in addition to how the research aims and objectives will be met. This introduction, which also doubles as a statement of rationale for this methodology chapter, leads into an examination of the philosophical basis of this study: ontological, epistemological and methodological debates, followed by a detailed explanation of the research approach. Then, I discuss the main research strategy and methods, while also giving a background and justification for the selected case study. Finally, I conclude by noting limitations and ethical considerations, including how each has been addressed when conducting the research.

5.1.1 Research Questions

As argued by Yin (2017), the form of the study questions, in terms of “who”, “what”, “where”, “how” and “why” provides an important clue regarding the most relevant research method to be used. The questions guiding this study are stated below.

1. What are the dimensions of child right infringements associated with the Olympic Games?
2. What measures are in place to mitigate children’s rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games?
3. What are the roles of stakeholders, event organizers, advocacy organizations and event owners in ensuring that the Tokyo 2020 Games are delivered in compliance with the UNCRC?

These questions were identified, and shaped, to enable me come to a logical conclusion about the nature of child rights infringements in the context of the Olympic Games.

5.2. Research Philosophy

When undertaking research, it is effective to be clear about the philosophy (Lochrie., et al. 2014) especially when new knowledge is about to be developed (Saunders et al. 2007). This development of knowledge, noted by Saunders et al. (2007), may not necessarily be as comprehensive as developing a theory of human motivation. In research, developing knowledge is often built on addressing clear research questions (Uddin and Hamiduzzaman, 2009), and at every stage of this process, there are assumptions and beliefs that shape the way the research is understood, framed and carried out. These assumptions and beliefs are what Saunders et al. (2007) refer to as research philosophy. In this study, I aim to produce meaning through the interpretation of various approaches to upholding child rights in mega sporting events from the subjective perspective using

a single case study, drawing on techniques of document examination and semi-structured interviews (emails, video interviews, and phone interviews).

There are three principal modes of thinking in research philosophy. While these three modes - epistemology, ontology and axiology - are quite important in their different spaces, according to (Moon and Black, 2014), ontology and epistemology are the two main branches of philosophy used in the natural and social sciences. Ontology studies what already exists, while epistemology is concerned with the way knowledge is acquired, validity and scope for acquiring knowledge Moon and Blackman (2014). This development and extent of applicability, as noted by Creswell (2007) cited by Khan (2014) solely depends on the relationship between the researcher, the researched, and how the researchers perceive the reality surrounding the research. Based on literature and previous research in the field of mega sporting events and child rights, there is a perception that child rights are infringed. Moreover, there is a gap in literature about the relationship between child rights infringements and the absence of a specific child right focus in the guiding the policies of mega sporting events. In the quest of knowing what counts as knowledge, and filling the gap of knowledge as explained above, this study has adopted the epistemology philosophy. This approach was adopted because, as explained by Moon and Blackman (2014), the epistemological approach enabled me acquire more knowledge in the field of interest - assessing child rights and mega sporting events in the context of Tokyo 2020. Undoubtedly, an appropriate philosophical approach aids the reasoning process of adding to knowledge, and as noted by Breukers and Hoekstra (2004), epistemology is a framework concerned with reasoning. Epistemology is more suitable for the topic of study (child rights and mega sporting events), alongside an appropriate paradigm – interpretivism.

Paradigms are an important aspect of research philosophies. Paradigms such as pragmatism, positivism, realism and interpretivism, can be adopted depending on the kind of research that is being carried out. They are particularly helpful for researchers to narrow down their enquiries to arrive at meaningful conclusions. The choice of paradigms has traditionally represented a major point of debate. While the interpretivist and positivist paradigms are more popular than pragmatism and realism, over the years, the latter paradigms have also gained more popularity. In discussing the appropriateness of these paradigms, scholars have argued that some of the paradigms are more like methods than philosophies. For example, Guyon, Kop, Juhel and Falissard (2018) argue that pragmatism is distinct from a static conception of reason. The pragmatist and realist philosophical paradigms have been argued to be more suitable for science and psychology, especially for mixed methods, scientifically inclined studies (Allmark and Machaczek, 2018). The interpretivist and positivist approaches, on the other hand, are more popularly adopted for social science research. The interpretivist and positivist paradigms, according to Khan (2015), help to identify or illuminate a problem, and give some reasonable direction to solve it, providing results and justifications that are acceptable for further reference. In the context of this study, the interpretivist approach helped illuminate the problem of the absence of child rights provision specifics in the Tokyo 2020 Games, while giving reasonable direction in helping to solve the problem. In contrast to the positivist paradigm which depends more on statistic (Alharahsheh, Helmi and Pius, 2020), the interpretivist approach was more suitable for this study, as it helped me gain further in-depth insights on the research problem through examining Tokyo 2020 policies and interviews with stakeholders (Alharahsheh, Helmi and Pius, 2020). In addition, because this study explores an issue that is difficult to quantify as is often about power and interests (that is, organizers, abusers, lack of empowerment), and child rights as a topic, it was important to frame

this methodology in a more interpretivist paradigm. A core belief of this paradigm is that known reality is socially constructed (Leitch, Hill and Harrison, 2017).

The positivist approach was considered for this research but was not adopted because the positivist paradigm and approach to conducting research does not fit the scope of this study. Unlike the positivist approach, adopting the interpretivist approach allowed me to consider factors such as cultures, circumstances, as well as times leading up to the development of different social realities (Alharahsheh, Helmi and Pius, 2020) of child rights infringements in the Olympic Games, considering Tokyo 2020. This is usually done by getting close to the participants or stakeholders, penetrating their internal logic in order to interpret their subjective understanding of reality (Shaw, 1999). As further explained by Alharahsheh, Helmi and Pius (2020):

There are several common qualities the research would adopt through following the interpretivist paradigm which can be summarised as the following: Firstly, the research would focus on the whole experience rather than considering certain parts of it. Secondly, questions and problems identification development of the research would be mainly influenced by the researcher in terms of interest, involvement as well as commitment. Thirdly, would enable researchers to explore further depth of individual experiences through in formal discussions and interviews. Fourthly, exploration of humans' experiences in depth through adoption of qualitative designs and methodologies. Fifthly, it would enable usage of experience as a highly important aspect and contribution to support scientific research. Sixthly, it would enable researchers to further explore in depth throughout individual experiences rather than considering generalised measurements or expectations as given in the positivist paradigm (Pg. 42).

The above excerpt captures the paradigm and rationale for the interpretivist paradigm applied to this research, including the process involved in carrying out the research – (a) focussing on child rights experiences in the Olympic Games, (b) identifying problems and gaps in policies guiding the planning of the Olympic Games, and (c), exploring further depth of experiences through interviews with stakeholders.

5.3. Research Approach

Research is a process of enquiry and investigation that is systematic, methodical and increases knowledge (Amatunga, Baldry, Sarshar and Newton, 2002). In developing a body of knowledge through research, there are different approaches that can be adopted (Cavaye, 1996) such as qualitative and quantitative (Overmars and Verburg, 2007). The qualitative approach is typically used in conducting social science research while natural scientists and specific social scientists such as psychologists most times adopt the quantitative approach. That said, there are debates that suggest that both qualitative and quantitative approaches can be used interchangeably. However, Soiferman (2010) argues that the quantitative approach is mostly adopted by social scientists when the usage is based on the premise that the research requires the use of statistical analysis in making the connection between what is known and what can be learned (Soiferman, 2010). Thus, in line with the premise of Overmars and Verburg (2007) that the choice of approach should be based on the research being conducted, this study took a qualitative approach. Even though this study is investigating a social phenomena (child rights in mega sporting events), this investigation will not be done using statistical or numerical data (Watson, 2015). Hence, the quantitative approach was not a fit for this research.

As mentioned in chapter one, the aim of this study is to assess child rights in mega sporting events, and one of the objectives is to identify and explain child rights infringements in the Olympic Games, using Tokyo 2020 as a case study. The study also aims to identify what measures are in place to mitigate children's rights from being infringed in mega sporting events. Adopting the qualitative approach allowed me to identify and evaluate this objective by focusing on child rights in the context of the mega sporting events within a real-life context – the planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. As explained by Amatunga, Baldry, Sarshar and Newton (2002. Pg. 21), one of the major features of qualitative research is that it focuses on naturally occurring, ordinary

events in natural settings, so that there is a view of what “real life” is. Furthermore, as mentioned in section 5.2, the research paradigm (interpretivist) applied to this study fits into the qualitative approach. In addition, since the qualitative approach is multifaceted, requiring insight and creativity, this approach allowed the researcher to define their information and theory by interaction which could be defined by environment, phenomena, particular types of participants, or by perspectives or theories (Tjora, 2018).

By choosing the qualitative approach for this study, I worked with the concept of child rights in the Olympic Games, I then used stakeholders (e.g. advocacy organizations, Japanese Organising Committee members, independent child right lawyers) views and document analysis to build broader themes and generate a theory connecting these. This helped me become more experienced with the phenomenon of my research (Trochi, 2006). In addition, by adopting the qualitative approach for this study, I aimed to become more experienced in the phenomenon of child rights protection in the terrain of mega sporting events (the Olympic Games) by embracing and understanding the contextual influences on the research issues (Hennink, Hutter and Bailey, 2020).

5.4. Research Strategies and Methodologies

The use of strategies and methodologies in conducting research are quite like each other in that they both offer step-by-step plans of action that give direction to the researcher’s thoughts and actions, enabling the researcher to conduct research systematically and on schedule to produce quality results and detailed reporting (MacKenzie Corporation, 2020). While a research strategy is an overall plan for conducting a research study which also guides a researcher in planning, executing, and monitoring (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014), only using appropriate methodologies and methods of research applied with rigour can the body of knowledge be established and advanced with confidence (Amaratunga, et al., 2002). For this research, based on the qualitative nature of the questions guiding the study, two alternative strategies were considered - the survey

and case study approach. However, I decided on the case study approach. This approach was chosen because, according to Johannesson and Perjons (2014), the case study is the right choice for investigating complex social relationships and outcomes in a specific setting, which perfectly describes this study's aim of assessing child rights in mega sporting events.

The overarching approach for this research is the case study approach. Within the case study approach, I also carried out interviews and examined documents. In the past few years, the horizon of research strategies and methodologies have broadened, as researchers no longer restrict themselves to a specific set of methods. The use of these methods (documentary analysis and interviews) for this study is acceptable because, as noted by Johannesson and Perjons (2014), the research strategy was suitable for my research, as it helped me to find answers to my research questions. One of the research questions of this study is to find out the dimensions of child rights infringement associated with mega sporting events like the Olympic Games. To support empirical literature about child rights infringements in the Olympic Games, one of the ways to answer this question is by conducting interviews for stakeholders including child rights NGOs who have had first-hand affiliations with the Olympic Games. Furthermore, the second research question focuses on determining what measures were put in place to mitigate children's rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games. Again, this question was answered by examining documents and policies in place for the Tokyo 2020 Games and conducting semi structured interviews with stakeholders and NGO affiliates. These are contexts with specific issues and specific sampling strategies and analysis techniques (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). Going by this statement, the suitability of strategies can be measured by how best the stakeholder answers a study's questions, and how best they help to achieve the aims and objectives of the study.

5.5. The case study approach

In the previous section, a variety of methodological approaches were considered in the process of conducting this research. The case study approach was deemed the most suitable based on the context and nature of the study being carried out, which is to investigate child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic. The case study approach has been considered by most researchers as one of the most appropriate approaches to employ for qualitative studies and research, as it allows cases explored in - depth (Crowe, Creswell, Robertson, Huby, Avery and Sheikh, 2011). Complex issues can be described as situations which consist of several parts that are sometimes difficult to understand. Some of these issues, if looked at, in relation to global affairs and human relations can be that of social conflicts, religious conflicts, educational misrepresentations, corruption in government parastatals, poverty, inequality, and so on. In the context of this research which aims to assess one of the negative impacts of mega sport events, the complex issue of child rights has been identified as one that can be hard to understand, considering the delicateness of the people who are being directly impacted and how they are being impacted. Researchers, using the case study approach, however, with different aims and objectives, have also conducted similar studies. Eliasson (2015) used the case study approach to study the gap between formalised children's rights and children's real lives in sport. Timms (2012) conducted a study on the Olympic Games as a platform for protest, using London 2012 as case study for fair play campaign for workers' rights. Studies of this kind, which impact on people socially, are important, and best undertaken in a real-life setting. The case study approach helps me study child rights in mega sporting events from a different perspective, and in a real life setting (the Tokyo 2020 Games). However, as noted by Richards, Brito and Wilks (2013), it is also necessary look at the whole lifecycle of the event under study, including the context within which it takes place, because context provides many reasons for the need to focus on the social impacts of those events (Richards, et al. 2013).

It is noteworthy to say that this approach is popular in these fields because they have some things in common. They deal directly with humans, make decisions and frame policies that are specifically aimed to furthering the betterment of people (Yin, 2011). This is in line with one of the objectives of this study, which is to develop a framework to facilitate the protection and promotion of children's rights in the Olympic Games, which will in turn influence policies. Even though there are debates about the case study approach been viewed as lacking rigour and objectivity when compared with other social research methodologies (see Rowley, 2002). In contrast to the arguments about the seeming confusion and sceptics of the case study usage, Rowley (2002) noted that despite skepticism about case study approach, they are widely used because they offer insights that might not be achieved by other approaches. The case study approach was chosen for this study because it helped me understand the behavioural conditions surrounding child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. In addition, the case study approach was chosen because it allowed for multiple use of strategies in the research being conducted, using different methods. As noted by Scholz and Tietje (2002), in principle, the case study should use multiple sources of information.

All methods should employ direct and participant observations, structured interviews, and surveys, and they can also include experimental design, focused interviews, open – ended interviews, archival records, documents and scientific data from field and laboratory (pg. 15).

As described above, these methods can be applied regardless of the kind of case study being carried out – single or multiple. A single case study was chosen, for this research, because this study aims to study one specific group of people (children). According to Yin (2003), if the researcher only wants to study one single thing (for example a person from a specific group) or a single group (for example a group of people), a single case study is the best choice. In addition, choosing a single case study helped me focus on child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games in – depth, thereby providing

a level of detail and understanding, thorough analysis of child rights in the Games, unlike most general and superficial multiple case-study methods (Willis, 2014).

5.5.1. Tokyo 2020 Olympics Games case study

This research seeks to examine the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a single case study for investigation. Initially, previous Olympic Games were considered, including the 2010 Vancouver Winter Olympics, Beijing 2008, and Paris 2024. The first two case studies were considered because several studies have been done about the Olympic Games, and the trickle-down effects of hosting the games on the host communities. Many studies have been conducted on these case studies, hence, there would be limited potential to contribute new knowledge. Beijing 2008 had the most cases of human rights infringements among the two case studies. In a study done by Brownell, there was an in-depth discussion about the Beijing Olympics and the coalition of NGOs in ensuring that the human rights issues in China were not hidden. She noted that Human Rights Watch (HRW) targeted forced evictions and school closures, labour rights abuses, repression of ethnic minorities, controls on religious freedom, use of house arrest system, and China's ties with rights violators (such as Sudan). Compared to the Beijing Olympics, Canada had fewer studies with mentions of human rights. However, there was an attempt to ensure that the then existing problem of human trafficking associated with Canada was not exacerbated by the 2010 Olympics (Perrin, 2007).

The Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games promised a fresh insight into assessing child rights issues in relation to the Olympic Games. Also, this case study was chosen because when I embarked on this study, the Games were yet to take place. This gave me the opportunity to observe the focus of study from different perspectives and in different scenarios – before, during, and after the event.

In addition, observing the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games allowed me to generate insight into how the International Organising Committee (IOC) and the Japanese Olympic Committee (JOC) created structures and frameworks around the delivery of the Games. As noted by Aina et. al. (2021), it is important to have structures, frameworks or standards in place from the bidding stage onwards if organizers are to be held to account for child rights issues. Hence, to critically scrutinize and assess the level of provision and protection measures available for children and their rights in the bidding and planning of the Olympic Games, I decided to focus on the Olympic Game being planned during my study period. This means that my study centred on the timeframe between 2011 (when the bid process started) and 2020 (when the Games was initially planned to be delivered). Though this study could have compared Tokyo 2020 to previous Olympic Games, however, I decided to focus on a single case study to enable depth of analysis. Looking at a single case study helped me to develop a Focusing on a single case also enabled me to develop substantial understanding of my research topic (Hennink, Hutter and Bailey, 2020).

5.6. Justification for mixed methods

Within the case study approach, there are several choices of methods to explore. The preceding sections noted, while also justifying why I conducted semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and active players in the child rights terrains both in and outside of the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committees. In addition to conducting interviews with stakeholders, I also examined and analyzed documents and policies that have information about child rights, in light Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and the wider Olympic Movement. By examining information collected through both methods, I was able to corroborate findings across data sets and thus reduce the impact of potential biases that can exist in a single study (Bowen, 2009). As explained by Bowen (2009), the rationale for document analysis lies in its role in methodological and data triangulation, the immense value

of documents in case study research, and its usefulness as a stand-alone method for specialized forms of qualitative research (pg. 29).

5.7. Research Design: Methods of Data Collection

5.7.1. Documentary Analysis

As defined by Bowen (2009), document analysis is an organised plan of action for evaluating relevant documents (Bowen 2009). Hence, to answer the research questions and achieve the aims and objectives of this research, I systematically examined the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games documents and published guidelines, looking for child rights specifics. These documents consisted of child related procedures, plans and strategies published online (see Table 1).

Table 1: List of documents reviewed		
HUMAN RIGHTS DOCUMENTS		
Document name	Author	Year of Publication
Sporting Chance White Paper	Terre Des Hommes & UNICEF	2017
Child Rights in Sports Principles	Japan Committee for UNICEF	2018
Human Rights Watch Report	Human Rights Watch	2020
OLYMPIC BID DOCUMENTS		
Candidature Acceptance Procedure for Host Cities	IOC	2011
Reports of the IOC evaluation commission	IOC	2013
Tokyo 2020 Joinder Agreement	TOC	2013
Tokyo 2020 Sustainability Plan Versions 1 & 2	TOC	2017, 2018

Host City Contract - Operational requirement	IOC	2017
Host City Operational requirement	IOC	2018
Japan human rights commitments and pledges	Japanese Government	2019
Japan 2020 Olympic Guidebook	TOC	2019
The Olympic Charter 2019	IOC	2019
HOST CITY CONTRACTS		
Host City Contract	IOC & JOC	2013
Appendix 1 and Addendum to the Host City Contract	IOC & JOC	2017
Addendum No 2. To the Host City Contract	IOC & JOC	2017
Addendum No 3. To the Host City Contract	IOC & JOC	2019

Bowen (2009) suggests that when conducting document analysis, the process of examining documents includes skimming (when necessary), reading (thorough examination) and interpretation. Even though he noted that document analysis is an integral part of qualitative research – “a rich source of data” (pg. 33), he also notes that documents should not be treated as necessarily precise, accurate, or complete recordings of events that have occurred. Therefore, interviews were also conducted with key stakeholders. The interviews complemented the findings from the document examination. I also analyzed the interview transcripts and other documents using Nvivo 12, 64 - bit version. Some of the downloaded documents were scanned copies, which means that they could not be highlighted, and coded on Nvivo. To solve this problem, I read these

documents in pdf format, wrote the relevant sentences out on word documents, and uploaded to Nvivo.

As a standard procedure for analysis, according to (Green, Willis, Hughes, Small, Welch, Gibbs and Daly, 2007), I read the transcripts and documents severally, to certify that I fully understood the data. After multiple readings, the transcripts and documents were analyzed thematically (Braun, Clarke and Weate, 2016), using Nvivo 12, 64 - bit version to create theme nodes (Hilal and Alabri, 2013). Figure 4 outlines the theme nodes generated and extracted from Nvivo.

An open and inclusive coding approach was adopted (Smith and Firth, 2011). This means that I identified and labelled all segments that were relevant to my study, while also labelling every segment of interest and relevance within the dataset, and everything of relevance within those segments (Terry, Hayfield, Clarke and Braun, 2017).

Figure 4: Coded Nodes

Figure 4 shows the segment of interests and relevance created from the dataset. Relevant texts were highlighted, and colour coded into these theme nodes. Some of the nodes had sub nodes. For example, participation had sub nodes of voice, space, audience and influence. Provision for child rights had sub nodes of safe space, hotlines, and policies. Representation had sub nodes of government, advocacy organizations, organizing committee members, lawyers and parents. Finally, child rights concerns in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games had sub nodes of child labour and exploitation, and trafficking. Some of these words are captured and reflected in this study's dataset word cluster map (see Figure 5 below), as generated and downloaded from Nvivo.

These word clusters were generated from documents reviewed, as listed in Table 1. These documents were uploaded to Nvivo individually and assessed while also looking out for sentences that suit the generic predetermined themes of violations, government structures, advocacy organisations, change management plans, representations, provisions, child protection, and leadership structures. Words that fell within these themes were initially colour coded. However, based on the need to narrow down these broad codes to specific themes, for the purpose of this research, the codes were categorized appropriately, and given encompassing titles.

(2011), it is flexible and more importantly, capable of disclosing important and often hidden facets of human and organizational behaviour:

Because it has its basis in human conversation, the semi structured interviews allow the skilful interviewer to modify the style, pace and ordering of questions to evoke the fullest responses from the interviewees. Most importantly, it enables interviewees to provide responses in their own terms and in the way that they think and use language (Pg. 246).

The ability to decipher hidden facets of behaviour in the process of interviewing most often happens during the face-to-face interview. Even though face-to-face approaches have long been the dominant interview technique in the field of qualitative research, in the last two decades, online interviews have become more and more common due to the growth of new communication forms (Opdenakker, 2006).

5.7.3. Conducted Interviews

For this research, a total of seven semi-structured interviews were carried out with actors of interest. Some of these actors, all based in Japan, were identified and approached by me through their organization websites, social media platforms (such as Twitter), while the others were referred by actors I had already interviewed. These actors have expert opinions on child rights, especially in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games terrain. Five out these seven actors are senior advocates from five child rights advocacy organizations while the remaining two actors are members of the organizing committee and an independent human rights lawyer, respectively. Even though one of the objectives of this study is to evaluate child participation strategies in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the decision not to interview children for this study was based on ethical considerations and the overall aim of this study. This study aimed to assess child rights in mega sporting events from the perspective of policies, event owners and stakeholders such as advocacy organisations and organising committee members. Hence, interviewing children was not necessary.

Due to the restrictions on travel caused by the coronavirus pandemic, interviews were conducted using remote video-call platforms, with each interview lasting between 45 and 60 minutes. The decision to conduct interviews on video calling platforms was made based on the preference of the interviewees. Interviews were conducted with a focus on themes arising from documentary examination of Tokyo 2020 documents, in addition to observations from Lundy's (2007) participation framework and McGillivray et al's (2019) study on delivering mega sporting events from a human rights perspective. Interviews were conversational, to enable flexibility and depth (Raworth, Sweetman, Narayan, Rowlands, and Hopkins, 2012; Qu and Dumay, 2011). Questions focussed on the themes of provision for protection and child participation in the decision-making processes of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Depending on their area of expertise, interviewees were asked slightly different questions. For example, those with legal expertise were asked to comment on the effectiveness of planned measures to protect child rights. Those advocating for child rights from NGOs and CSOs were asked to comment on the extent to which Games planning (from government and the Organizing Committee) adhered to international standards and whether they were consulted in the process. Finally, organizers were asked to narrate what child rights procedures and pacts were part of their planning horizons and what challenges they encountered in their bid to embed child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, if ever they tried to. The interview schedule comprised of introductory questions, direct questions, follow up questions and probing questions. The interviews were scheduled and recorded both on my laptop, and on my mobile device. This mobile device is only used for recordings. The recordings were later transcribed.

5.8. Study Propositions and Case

For this study, the focus is on the rights of children which are constantly overlooked and not adequately provided for in mega sporting events planning and delivery. Furthermore, there is the

proposition that child rights are not adequately provided for in mega sporting events because children are not invited to the table of decision making proceedings, related to the Olympic Games. Finally, there is a sense that children in host communities, as well as participants (elite child athletes and volunteers) are the immediate subjects of infringement in mega sporting events.

5.8.1. Logic linking data to proposition

As highlighted in the “study propositions” paragraph, three propositions have been developed for this study. Documents would be analyzed and then linked to the relevant propositions that have been stated in the “Study proposition” section. Already, based on empirical literature and highlighted propositions, there is a potential pattern of data findings: First, provisions for child rights might not been adequately documented in Tokyo 2020 policies and bid documents, second, there is a possibility that NGOs would influence whatever changes there might be to the formalization of human rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games procedures. Third, child rights infringements in the Olympic Games is directly linked to a probable lack of governance structure as regards child rights in the host city of mega sporting events. Finally, the fourth pattern would be that the decision-making processes of the Tokyo 2020 Games only involved children in the capacity of participants and volunteers, as opposed to participation (children being given a voice, space, audience and influence) as proposed by Lundy (2007).

5.8.2. Units of Analysis

According to Sedwick (2014), the unit of analysis is defined as the “who” or “what” for which information is analyzed and conclusions are made. For this research, the units of analysis are: child rights, mega sporting events and Tokyo 2020 Olympics.

5.8.3. Data Analysis

Approaches to qualitative data collection and analysis are numerous, representing a diverse range of epistemological, theoretical, and disciplinary perspectives (Guest, McQueen, Namey, 2011). As

mentioned in the previous two sections, primary data was collected through a mixture of interviews with stakeholders and examination of documents written in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games child and human rights. The sections also presented maps of coded nodes and prevalent themes and nodes developed on Nvivo. The data collected by both methods was analyzed thematically (See Figure 6 for processes of thematic analysis).

Figure 6: Phases of Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006. Pg. 87)

As mentioned earlier, analysis of documents and interview transcripts was undertaken using the qualitative software tool, Nvivo 12, 64 - bit version. As explained in the quote above, thematic analysis focusses on identifying themes (see Figure 7 for prevalent themes identified for this study)

while content analysis allows the researcher to interpret meaning from the content of text data (Hsieh and Shannon (2005).

Figure 7: Thematic Analysis Conceptual Framework as generated on Nvivo

Chapter 4 highlighted the conceptual frameworks that guide this study. Hence, in analysing the findings of this study, the themes identified from the findings (Figure 7) were analyzed based on the requirements and explanations of the frameworks adapted for this study. For example, McGillivray et.al’s (2019) conceptual pathways to leveraging mega sporting events to uphold human rights will be used in presenting the documentary analysis. This is suitable for the findings and analysis because this conceptual framework is concerned with policies and has proposed ways through which policies can adequately reflect human rights/child rights. Lundy’s (2007) model for participation will also be used simultaneously to structurally present and analyze the semi-structured interview findings.

5.9. Research Ethics and Considerations

Ethical issues in research can come up in different dimensions in every study (Miller, et al, 2019; Orb, Eisenhaur and Wynaden, 2000). In a study about ethics in qualitative research, Miller et al

(2019) argued that ethical decisions in qualitative research can be made right from the conceptualization and design of the research, data gathering and analysis, report, and literature on the topic being researched. Orb et, al (2000) noted specifically that while the research process generally contributes to ethical issues. sI was fully aware of the different ethical issues that might arise in this research. As a result, I ensured that that every ethical guidelines that apply to this research were followed. There were no underaged interviewees, hence this study was deemed low risk by the University's Ethics Committee. However, there was a consciousness of the sensitivity of human rights studies. This made adhering to research ethics even more important.

Participant information sheets were provided for interviewees in advance of their interview. This explained to the interviewees everything they needed to know about the research. This also allowed them to decide if they wanted to be a part of the research or not. Research informed consent forms were also prepared for all interview participants, and I ensured that the forms were filled appropriately before the interviews began. Research informed consent form contained these information:

- Confirmation that participant has read and understood the information sheet provided alongside the consent form.
- That participants had the time to consider the information, asked questions and had satisfactory answers to their questions.
- Participation in interviews or other data gathering methods for this research is voluntary, and participants are free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
- That data collected will only be used for purposes explained to the participant, and all information collected will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

- Consent to have the participant’s voice recorded.
- Agreement to participate in the study.

After each interview, participants asked to be represented anonymously in the findings and analysis. This issue of confidentiality was addressed appropriately by using identifiers (e.g. Interviewee A) in place of participant’s real names and organizational affiliations (see Table 2).

Table 2: Interview list

IDENTIFIER	ROLE
Interviewee A	Representative of the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee
Interviewee B	Child rights lead at an International Human Rights Organisation
Interviewee C	Child Rights Advocate and athlete protection lead
Interviewee D	Child Rights Lawyer / coalition member of an international human rights organisation
Interviewee E	Policy developer for a Child Rights Charity Organisation
Interviewee F	Child labour chair for an international Child Rights Organisation
Interviewee G	Child trafficking representative for an international Child Rights Organisation

5.9.1. Limitations of the Study

One of the limitations of this study is in the number of interviews conducted. I planned to visit Tokyo for a month, for the purpose of observation. Going to Tokyo, Japan would have given me

first hand information about my subject of study – child rights in Tokyo 2020 Games. This would have given me the opportunity to conduct a face to face interview with the actors that I interviewed via video calls. Covid – 19 pandemic disrupted the plan, hence it was impossible to gather data in Japan. This limitation was overturned by reaching out to, and liaising with appropriate Japan-based stakeholders, either through referrals or by searching on official organizational websites.

Another limitation that I encountered in conducting this study is in the sample size. The interviews conducted were limited. This study was conducted during the pandemic, hence, I was unable to conduct as many interviews as I would have wanted. Also, some key stakeholders that I reached out to for interviews, such as advocacy organization members from HRW, were either unavailable or declined my request for an interview, based on the sensitivity of the topic of discussion. In addition, prior research studies that are relevant to my thesis, in the context of documentary analysis of child rights in previous Olympic Games, are limited.

5.9.2. Conclusion

In this chapter I have explained, in–depth, the research methodology and methods that guided the primary research conducted on child rights and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The chapter started with a discussion of the research philosophy that guided the research, justifying the philosophical decisions made. As this is a qualitative study, I addressed the aims and objectives of the research from an epistemological philosophical perspective. As mentioned in previous chapters, the research aims to assess child rights in mega sporting events. In lieu of this, I acknowledged that the epistemological approach is the main approach which would allow me to explore the social phenomenon under investigation from the perspective of the people involved: the stakeholders and affiliate NGOs like UNICEF and the Centre for Sport and Human Rights (Yilmaz, 2013).

As noted by Lochrie., et al. (2014), a good philosophy determines the research methodology and methods that are used in conducting a research. Once the philosophical approach had been determined, I then went ahead to list out and explain the research strategy, design and methods for this research. In this chapter I explained that a variety of methodological approaches were examined for this study, and after careful examination of examined methodological approaches, the case study approach was found suitable based on the context and nature of the study being carried out.

I also outlined the research methods utilised, while explaining and justifying each methods applied. For example, it was mentioned in this chapter that documents which had specific contents of child rights for the Tokyo 2020 Olympics Games were examined carefully. This method was appropriate because I believe that examining of documents would complement interview data. In this chapter has specified the modes and techniques through which the data were analyzed while stating the limitations of the research. More interviews would have been conducted for this study, but for lack of access. However, it is pertinent to note that the inability to interview further actors for this study does not negatively affect the outcome. The actors and stakeholders interviewed had enough knowledge about child rights, especially in the context of Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

The next chapter in this study will focus on presentation of findings.

CHAPTER 6: FORMALISATION OF CHILD RIGHTS PROTECTION IN OLYMPIC GAMES POLICIES

6. 1. Introduction

In order to assess child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, it was necessary to examine and document findings from the policies and principles that guided the games during the bidding and planning phases. This was necessary because assessing the issue of child rights in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games from just one point of view (conducting interviews) would be insufficient to address the context of child rights in full. Focusing on one data source also risks the research lacking depth and being one-dimensional. The analysis of the documents was undertaken before conducting the interviews. Document analysis alone would not have produced enough depth in this study's data set because even though documents can provide access to information that may be useful for the study, data from documents alone may not be adequate and may have been created to present a particular view of events - in this case, the Tokyo 2020 Games (Fitzgerald, 2012). In lieu of this, interviews were conducted to enable me assess child rights in Tokyo 2020 Games also from different stakeholders' perspectives.

The first objective of this study was to examine what policies are in place to foster the protection of child rights in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. As discussed in chapter four, within case studies, a range of methods can be utilised, including participant observation and document analysis. Addressing my inability to be a participant observer in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was deemed necessary to adapt practice and explore, in depth, key policies and guidelines published locally (Tokyo), nationally and internationally (the IOC specific documents) that influence the conception, planning and design of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, from a child rights perspective. This process helped to triangulate the research findings. As argued by Patton (1999), it was important to triangulate the research findings in order to develop a comprehensive understanding of the child rights landscape in the

context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The documentary analysis is complemented by findings from interviews with major stakeholders and affiliate human rights NGOs operating in and around the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

In this chapter I present data generated from published strategy documents, media reports and related documents charted over the nine-year period since Tokyo bid for the Olympic Games in 2011. Documents were collected and collated from when the bid for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games commenced (2011), through to the Games delivery period (2021). An analysis of key human rights and child rights related documents in place over the same period was also conducted to check how the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games Organising Committee and the Japanese Government adhered to international standards of human rights and child rights. As detailed in the methodology chapter, the assessment focused on documents between the period of 2011 through to 2020. The analysis documented references to human rights and, specifically, child rights in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Specifically, I explored references to issues that would affect children by looking at various types of documents such as sport policies, Olympic-related documents (IOC policies/guidelines including the Host City Agreement, Bid book, Organising Committee policies) and wider governmental policies on human rights in Japan. For ease of examination and analysis, documents have been divided into two: Human Rights Organizations related documents (NGOs) and Tokyo 2020 Bid Documents.

Focusing on the bid and planning stages, McGillivray et al's (2019) conceptual model for bidding, planning and delivering mega sport events that lever human rights will be used as a means of structuring the presentation of findings. Four main themes are presented: transparency and inclusiveness of governance structure before the bid period; democratisation and voice to protect and promote human rights; formalisation of the child rights agenda in Tokyo 2020 policies; and,

change management plan (CMP). The change management plan theme details the development of inclusive (or exclusive) public spaces to ensure that child rights are not negatively affected by the construction of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games event venues, transport infrastructures and other development changes to the urban realm. These themes build on McGillivray's pathways to delivering a rights-focused mega sporting event. Through the pathways, I will develop a deep knowledge of how child rights have been addressed in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies. As a result of this, I will also develop a framework of an holistic approach to delivering an Olympic Game from a child rights perspective.

6.2. Transparency and inclusiveness of governance structure before Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games delivery

Using mega sporting events to produce a beneficial human right end result originates from a intentionality of leadership plans to front human rights initiatives (McGillivray et. al, 2019). Contextualising this to child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games, progressive child rights outcomes in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games should have begun with the quality of governance structures in place. Governance, as noted by McGillivray et al (2019), includes the International Sport Organizations (ISOs), Hosting Organisation stakeholders (HOS) such as the JOC, advocacy organizations and affected individuals. Specifically, for Tokyo 2020, organizers needed to have adhered to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Child (UNCRC) standards to ensure that the rights of children were recognized and protected, starting from the vision stage onward. Although Japan ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Child in 1994, Japan still recorded high instances of child mistreatment until 2013 (Tanaka, Suzuki, Aoyama, Takaoka and MacMillan, 2017). According to Kadonaga and Fraser (2015), the number of reports of child maltreatment, including both child abuse and neglect, rose from 17,725 in 2000 to 59,862 in 2011, a significant increase for a country that had ratified the UNCRC and put in a bid to host the 2020

Olympic Games. The period of 2011 to 2013 was when Tokyo made a bid to host the Olympic Games. Surprisingly, there was no governance structure in place for child rights before the bid period, which explains why there were no child rights protection measures mentioned in any of the bid documents. The child rights structures that were in existence only started to come into place after the bid to host the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games had been won. These structures and commitments were detailed in the *Japan's Human Rights and Commitment Pledges* document, published in January 2019, six years after winning the bid to host Tokyo 2020.

An analysis of *Japan's Human Rights Commitments and Pledges* document, published in 2019, revealed that Japan had invested in several right protection agencies before the delivery of the Tokyo 2020 Games;

Based on its commitments to dialogue and cooperation, Japan has been steering efforts to resolve human rights issues of concern to the international community and to improve human rights situations through both international fora, such as the United Nations and bilateral dialogues (p. 1)

However, there was no evidence that these commitments were in place before bidding to host the Olympic Games in 2011. The JHRCP document was the only available detailed document showing the Japanese government's child and human rights commitments before the Olympic Games. While the document had specific mentions of the Tokyo 2020 Games, it also detailed the human rights memberships and several NGOs that Japan has affiliates with. Addressing child rights in Japan, the JHRCP document described the efforts of the Japanese government to protect children from some of the common crimes registered in Japan against children. As noted:

Japan is taking the initiative in efforts to end violence against children as a Board Member and a Pathfinding Country of the Global Partnership to End Violence against Children (GPeVAC) in cooperation with the UN children's Fund (UNICEF) and non – governmental organization. Also, actively collaborating with and contributing to the activities of relevant organizations which lead the protection and promotion of human rights (e.g. OHCHR, UNHCR, UNICEF and UN women) (JHRCP, 2019. p. 3, 6).

In addition, more generally, in the context of the Olympic Games, the JHRCF tried to address human rights protection issues. The rights section focused more on Japan's culture and value of sports, and the way the country has been promoting the Olympic and Paralympic movement through the Sport for Tomorrow (SFT) programme. However, as stated in the JHRCF document, the Japanese government pledged to manage the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games in accordance with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, as stated in the JHRCF. The document also noted that "this is the first time for the Olympic and the Paralympic Games to be organised under the guiding principles" (JHRCF, 2019. p. 8), as these principles only came into place in 2011. While the JHRCF promised to host the Olympic Games in line with UNGPHR, there was no explanation in the JHRCF as regards what it would mean in practice for the IOC and Japanese government to organise the Tokyo 2020 Games in accordance with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights.

As noted above, the JHRCF document highlighted the Japanese government's initiatives to curb child rights infringements in the country. Considering the Tokyo 2020 Games, the JHRCF document also attempted to address child rights protection in the Olympic Games through the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee (TOCOG) sustainability sourcing code. As evident in the document, in addition to proposing to manage the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games in accordance with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, the TOCOG also formulated a sustainable sourcing code (JHRCF 2019, p. 8). These sustainable codes, which were designed by the TOCOG, would serve as a tool to ensure sustainability throughout the supply chains of procured, and licensed products. Among other things, these sustainable codes will ensure that the rights of children are not violated.

The Tokyo Organizing Committee of the Olympic has formulated the Sustainable Sourcing Code. Respecting international agreements and codes of conduct for sustainability, the Code defines standards and operating procedures to ensure procurement in which sustainability issues such as the environment, human rights and labor are taken into consideration[...] suppliers will be required to comply with and respect international human rights standards, eliminate discrimination and harassment, prohibit violation of local residents' rights and respect the rights of women, persons with disabilities, children and social minorities (JHRCP, 2019, p. 8).

This excerpt from the JHRCP is evidence that Tokyo 2020 Games did put in place some governance structures before the delivery of the Olympic Games in 2021, however, it is noteworthy that having governance structures does not guarantee implementation. It is also noteworthy that Japan had consistently made efforts to ensure that children's rights are protected in Japan. On page 7 of the JHRCP, findings show that Japan has some existing measures to eliminate child pornography, as well as Child Sexual Exploitation:

In addition to existing measures to eliminate child pornography, Japan formulated the Basic Plan on Measure against Child Sexual Exploitation in 2017, which is a national basic plan expanding coverage to all aspects of the sexual exploitation in 2017, including child prostitution, in order to eliminate child sexual exploitation. Japan has promoted various measures for raising public awareness, protecting and supporting victimised children and strengthening crackdowns in accordance with the plan. Furthermore, in the same year, Japan revised the Penal Code and strengthened the penal provisions against sexual offenses, such as creating a crime of sexual intercourse by a person having custody of person under the age of 18. Through these measures, Japan deals with sexual offenses more strictly than before (p. 7).

Not only did the Japanese government and the TOCOG come together to develop some measures in advance of the Games, but there is also evidence that there was an inclusiveness of governance structure, as the Japanese government had partnered with some specific NGOs including UNICEF. There is no evidence, however, as to whether there were actions to back the structures and commitments up. For instance, since Japan had a standing affiliation with UNICEF, there should have been some child rights commitments in the bid documents. There were none.

Evidently, from the 2020 Evaluation Commission Report released by the IOC in 2013, the child rights commitments and pledges stated in the JHRCP were not considered when awarding Tokyo 2020 the rights to host the Games. The Tokyo 2020 Evaluation Commission Report had a section for rights consideration, but it made no mention of human rights or child rights at all.

6.2.1. Inclusiveness of governance structures – advocacy organizations

According to McGillivray et. al (2019), how well the mega sporting events host organiser, and its public and private partners engages NGOs and vulnerable populations often subjected to human rights abuses, is likely to determine the likelihood of success for attaining rights goals. While there is no evidence, in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies and NGO documents analyzed, that TOCOG engaged with vulnerable populations, it was evident in the JHRCP that Japan engaged NGOs in 2019 by partnering with them to provide a new approach to manage the Games in accordance with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights(UNGPHR). By affiliating with human rights NGOs, Japan provided an avenue for affiliate NGOs, and prospective affiliate NGOs to be involved in the planning of the events. This took different dimensions, including monitoring, conducting workshops and targeted research. As noted by Caudwell and McGee (2018), “even where it means policing the state, protection of fundamental freedoms demands concrete actions, the responsibility for this increasingly falls on NGOs and CSOs (p. 5). Similarly, Horne (2018) argues that advocacy organizations have consistently been responsible for monitoring violations (Horne, 2018) in mega sporting events, as well as holding host governments and event owners accountable for cases of human rights neglect and abuse.

A review of *The Children’s Rights in Sports Principles (CRSP)* authored by UNICEF Japan, and published in 2018, revealed that UNICEF Japan created a structure for child rights protection measures in the context of the Olympic Games. The document outlined different ways that child rights can be protected in sport. It also outlined the importance of sport in protecting child rights

and the need for elimination of all forms of violence against children in the Olympic Games because it is well known that this mega sporting event has infringed on child rights in the past:

Sport is universally shared across human culture, based on voluntary participation. Lifelong participation in sport can promote prosperous living and cultural development, and is integral to the pursuit of health and well-being including for children. Unfortunately, diverse cases have been observed, of sport adversely affecting children's rights, such as corporal punishment, bullying and allowing children to over train the course of sports instruction, practice, and matches (Children in Sport Principles, 2018. p. 4)

In section 5 (p. 15), the document proposed measures to better develop governance systems to protect the rights of children in sporting events. These included the need to:

- a. Formulate and publish basic principles to protect the child, while publicizing the policy inside and outside of the organisation.
- b. Identify and assess risks and adopt appropriate measures according to the level of risks.
- c. Establish specific rules, guidelines, and codes of conduct to implement the policies for respecting and supporting the rights of children set out in Principles 1 to 4 and ensure that they are followed by all persons involved.
- d. Monitor regularly whether violence, overtraining and other issues that adversely affect the rights of children occur in the course of sport instruction, practice, and matches.

Continue to review and improve the status of efforts to respect and support the rights of children based on the results of monitoring. And finally,

- e. Ensure that children have access to services to report and consult safely and confidentially on violence, overtraining and other issues that adversely affect their rights. Provide children with information about their rights and about how they can report and discuss their concerns. Prepare mechanisms that allow third parties or anyone who is worried, to report or make their concerns known on issues that might adversely affect the rights of children. Ensure access to effective remedies that are appropriate to the needs of

children by placing top priority on the best interest of the child when receiving concerns or complaints. Ensure that remedy channels are accessible to children and that children are able to participate in them meaningfully.

Further to proposing measures to better protect children, the CRSP also made mention of the fact that understanding, and development of systems related to the protection of rights of children is currently inadequate. This document was developed by UNICEF Japan in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and can be considered as a means of influencing the Japanese government to provide adequate measures to protect children within the planning process for the event. This document was published in 2018, three years before the Tokyo 2020 Games were eventually hosted. However, there is little evidence that this document influenced TOCOG to develop child rights structures and policies ahead of the Games. In fact, Human Rights Watch, while referring to the JHRCP noted that the JOC, TOCOG and the IOC were not doing enough to ensure that child rights were being adequately protected. A review of a report published by HRW in 2019, titled “*I was hit so many times I can’t count*” documented several cases of ongoing abuse against child athletes in Japan including abusive coaching techniques, corporal punishment and physical violence in the lead up to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games:

Abusive coaching techniques documented in this report include, but are not limited to, hitting children with bats and bamboo kendo sticks, slapping children across the face, and holding children’s heads underwater to simulate drowning. While abuse of a child includes harms such as physical and sexual violence, verbal abuse, and neglect, this report is primarily focused on physical violence, as that was the experience current and former child athletes reported to Human Rights Watch most frequently. Experiences of verbal and sexual abuse are also documented (Human Rights Watch, 2020).

Partly due to its frustration with the Japanese government and TOCOG, HRW used a blaming and shaming strategy (McGillivray et al, 2020) to highlight its concerns through the media. The shaming strategy adopted by HRW has been used in past Games too. For example, it submitted a

proposal to the IOC's Copenhagen Congress in 2009, proposing that a permanent mechanism be put in place to monitor human rights in host countries before, during and after the Olympic Games:

To avoid Olympics-related human rights violations in all future host countries, Human Rights Watch has proposed creating an IOC standing committee to monitor human rights in host countries. This committee would help set and apply human rights benchmarks for potential Olympic hosts, in particular with regard to media freedom, labour rights, freedom of expression and civil liberties. Most important it would be staffed with experts and tasked monitoring abuses before, during and after an Olympics (Human Rights Watch, 2020).

By “staffed with experts”, HRW were referring to experts in human rights including on child rights to ensure that protection measures are adhered to. Crucially, HRW (2019) made it clear that words on paper will not change practice - implementation and monitoring are essential.

6.2.2. Transparency, Responsiveness and Accountability

An analysis of a document published by Centre for Sport and Human Rights titled “*Sustainable Sourcing, Grievance Mechanisms, and Human Rights at Mega Sporting Events*” revealed that on September 13, 2017, CSHR held a workshop in Japan focused on making respect for human rights a reality in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. This was done as a form of influencing factor to ensure that the TOCOG come up with a structure for rights protection at the Games. As argued by McGillivray et al (2019), expectations for mega sporting events to achieve the protection and promotion of right outcomes are dependent on good governance of the mega sporting events (including transparency, responsiveness and accountability). As evidenced in JHCRP document, the Japanese government had shown accountability by pledging to deliver the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games in line with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights. Furthermore, the governance of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games was also responsive and transparent about the structures in place for the Games by contributing to the CSHR workshop. The “*Sustainable Sourcing, Grievance Mechanisms, and Human Rights at Mega Sporting Events*”

document detailed the attendance at the workshop to include most of the TOCOG As detailed in the report:

On September 13 (Wed.), 2017, IHRB on behalf of the Mega-Sporting Events Platform for Human Rights (MSE Platform) organised, with the support of the Swiss Government and together with Caux Round Table Japan, its first workshop in Japan, towards making respect for human rights a reality in the Tokyo Olympic and Paralympic Games. The workshop was attended by 76 persons from 41 organizations, including the International Olympic Committee (IOC), the Tokyo Organising Committee of the Olympic and Paralympic Games (TOCOG), the Olympics headquarters in the Cabinet Secretariat, and other related organizations of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games, sponsor companies, NGOs from Japan and abroad, athletes' organizations, Japanese Government organizations (the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Justice, and Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare), and embassies in Japan - the U.S. Embassy and Embassy of Switzerland (Pg. 4).

The document also revealed that the aim of the workshop was to identify and share among the participants, key points and issues surrounding the implementation of sustainable sourcing policies and grievance mechanisms – towards the goal of making respect for human rights a reality in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Speaking on leveraging the Olympics to address human rights situation in Japan, Executive Director of Games Operations, TOCOG, at the workshop stated that they hoped to make Tokyo 2020 the most innovative in history that will bring positive reform to the world. As stated in the document:

With slightly more than 1,000 days remaining until the opening, we are drawing ever closer to Tokyo 2020, we hope to make Tokyo 2020 the most innovative in history that will bring positive reform to the world. The “Legacy” contained in the Games Vision relates not only to sports, but also to many other fields. TOCOG has drawn up the Action & Legacy Plan to promote action in building this Legacy, and one of the pillars of the Action & Legacy Plan is “Sustainability”. Based on the Olympic Agenda 2020, which recommends “inclusion of sustainability”, TOCOG is developing the second version of our sustainability plan, which will contain concrete numerical targets (CHHR workshop report, p. 8)

While there was no express discussion of child rights at the workshop, the chief of Information & Public Affairs, Japan Committee, UNICEF, however, noted that TOCOG’s sustainable code referred to the UNCRC and to the Children’s Rights and Business Principles (CRBP) while

reiterating that mega sporting events have both positive and negative impacts on children. Speaking further on the potential harm of mega sporting events on children, he stated that the risks of adverse impacts in child rights at mega sporting events are, but not limited to disruption, child prostitution and abuse of athletes and children aspiring to become athletes or Olympians by coaches and overexposure to media (p. 15). In a quote, on the same page, CSHR mentioned the current “undervalue” of child rights in Japan, attributing this to the inability of Japanese to differentiate child rights from human rights:

Perhaps because of the word “child rights”, in Japan there is a tendency to see them as different from “human rights”, and maybe because of this, children’s rights are by far still undervalued vis-à-vis the rights of adults (CSHR, 2017. Pg. 18).

The CSHR report emphasized the need for clear distinctions between human rights and child rights, if child rights are to be recognized in Japan. Speaking about general human rights protection measures for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the promotion and compliance team stated that similar to TOCOG’s sourcing code, which monitors labour and employment for the Tokyo 2020 Games, “we prohibited employment of children under the age of 15” (p. 25). This illustrates progress towards the minimisation of child labour. As noted by Donnelly (1997), the problems associated with children’s involvement in high performance sport are often equated to the issue of child labour.

Even though the policies and guidelines for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games did not have precise child rights violations deterrents plans at the initial stage (between the period of 2011 to 2013), advocacy organizations such as UNICEF, HRW and CSHR took it upon themselves to point out the inadequacies of the Japanese government in the planning of the Games. After the CSHR workshop in 2017, the TOCOG started to show responsiveness and accountability towards child rights. An example of this is the publication of JHRCP in 2019, which included details of child

rights commitments. NGOs (Human Rights Watch, Centre for Sports and Human Rights, UNICEF) ensured that Tokyo 2020 had a rethink about their approach to international human rights, and child rights standard by conducting targeted research, thereby revealing the aspect of child rights that needed to be addressed before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. They also recommended structures and strategies that articulate clear responsibilities for each actor and ensure that the rights of vulnerable groups are recognized through strategic workshops. There was no initial documentary evidence such as policies and principles, except the *Tokyo 2020 Sustainability document* (which was an afterthought document) to suggest that Tokyo 2020 planned to enforce or monitor child rights of volunteers or child athletes in the Tokyo 2020 Games.. These will be discussed in-depth section 6.3 and 6.4 below.

6.3. Practices of democratisation and voice to protect and promote child rights

In addition to good governance, how institutions delivering mega sporting events engage with local stakeholders to ensure democratisation of goals and practices is critical to ensuring the efficacy of rights agenda (McGillivray et al. (2019). As explained in the sections above, in the context of this study, meaningful stakeholders of the Olympic Games are inclusive of children. McGillivray et al. (2019) argue that meaningful engagement could help advance the democratisation of the mega sporting events planning process and improve levels of child participants in the decision-making process would inform a child–rights agenda. This is like Lundy’s (2007) participation strategy proposal. Lundy (2007) suggested that giving the child (an affected stakeholder in the Olympic Games) a democratic vote in the issues that concern them can potentially lead to an adequate child rights protection outcome. As explained in section four, while the IOC has evolved its approach to human rights in the past ten years, their approach to child rights remains deficient. This is reflected in the Tokyo 2020 bid selection processes. While the Japanese government had ratified the UNCRC, there was no evidence to suggest that the Japanese government had acted on their child

rights principles and commitments. While the 2020 bidding documents exchanged by the IOC and the host city (Tokyo) did not have child rights protection strategies in them, what the documents did have were “participation strategies”. These participation strategies have been found, by this study, to lack democratisation and voice. Upon in-depth examination of the bid documents, there was no evidence to suggest that the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee had involved any of the affected stakeholders (especially participants and volunteers), either to provide them with a clear understanding of how the Games might impact them, or to give them a chance to input into the process and know where and how they can access remedy if required (Platform 2018, cited by McGillivray et. al. 2019). The participation strategies that were evident in the Tokyo 2020 bid documents were found to be like that of the London 2012 Olympics. Just like the London 2012 bid, which promised to use the Olympic Games to promote sports participation for all groups across the UK (Girginov and Hills, 2008), Tokyo 2020 organising bodies also seemed to adopt the same strategy for the Tokyo 2020 Games. While there were no specific protection measures for child participants in the bid documents submitted by Tokyo, there were several mentions of general guidelines and strategies to ensure participation in the Tokyo 2020 Games. This can be said to be in line with the principle of the Olympic Charter, which states that the practice of sport is a human right (p. 11), also reinforcing that participation in the Olympic Games is considered free for all. This means that everyone, including children, can participate in the Olympic Games. The TOCOG applied this participation principle of the Olympic Charter to the Tokyo 2020 Games.

First, The Tokyo 2020 *Candidature File* (bid book) stated specifically that Tokyo 2020 would encourage participation in the Games in a way that participants (both young and old) will enjoy the Games. As stated in the *Candidature File*, Vol 1:

Tokyo 2020 will see Japan and the world renew and reinforce their relationship through sport. East will meet west. Ancient and modern will be shared, and enjoyed by young and old (p. 006)

Second, as reflected in the Tokyo 2020 vision, children would be included:

The basis of “Tokyo Vision 2020” is to realise the evolution of Tokyo, into an ideal city of the 21st century. The power of sport has been recognized as essential to achieving “Tokyo Vision 2020” with one of its 8 goals being to “Create a society where everyone can enjoy sports and children are given dreams” (Candidature File, Vol 1, p.18)

This is like what London 2012 proposed in their bid book. The Olympic Charter also mentions that participants have to respect and comply with the Olympic Charter and World Anti-Doping Code (p. 76). According to Chen (2012), participation in mega events is found to be the most important factor for children. In the introduction part of the *Candidature File, Volume 1*, the Tokyo 2020 bid committee described Tokyo as a city powered by a culture of continual innovation and a “dynamic youth population” (p.6). However, while stating promises and reasons for bidding for the Games, there was no major evidence to suggest that young people were given a voice, even though “youths” were stated to be an integral part of the Tokyo community.

Starting with “If Tokyo is awarded the honour of hosting the 2020 Olympic and Paralympic Games” the document highlighted that Tokyo would use the Games as leverage for basic things. Among the list is urban regeneration, values, as well as “provide a new platform to renew and reinvigorate the Olympic values”. Then, the last three lines were dedicated to “help connect young people in a new, fast – changing world with sport and the Games, providing a lasting legacy for a new generation” (p. 8). The closest to promises of protection and inclusion in the *Candidature File* was stated in the Vision, Legacy and Communication section which stated:

One of the main programmes – part of the overall sports development community programme – will focus on seven Olympic sports (Archery, Boxing, Canoe-kayak, Cycling, Rowing, Weightlifting and Wrestling) to encourage young athletes to achieve at an elite level and will include a talent identification and support scheme for these sports (p. 14).

It was not made clear what kind of support would be given to participants. Neither was there any evidence to suggest that child participants had been given a chance to recommend how they should be supported in the Games. Just as the Olympic Charter referred to youths and educational programmes, Tokyo 2020 also promised to introduce educational programmes for youth. More specifically, it promised to enhance the anti-doping education programme for participants:

The Jigoro Kano Memorial International Sport Institute will also contribute to the promotion of Olympism by educating youth through sport and encouraging international sport exchange. An anti-doping education programme will be enhanced, led by the Japan Anti-Doping Agency (JADA) and in collaboration with sport organizations, and education and research institutions (p. 14).

In addition, as part of the participation strategies proposed in the *Candidature File*, Tokyo 2020 promised to support the IOC and the UN to develop a sport support programme for athletes:

Tokyo 2020 will fully support the IOC in its international initiatives such as ‘Sport for All’ and its activities in partnership with the United Nations, and work closely with the IOC and IPC to develop a sport support programme, and new and extended sports development programmes, building on the London 2012 “International Inspiration” and Rio 2016 programmes. (p. 14)

These strategies have been termed innovative by Kolotouchkina (2018). However, they do not address the fact that there were inadequate human rights commitments in the bid documents analyzed. When compared with Lundy’s (2007) model of participation, the participation measures included in the policies are deficient. The policies revealed detailed strategies for physical participation, while Lundy’s four models of participation (i.e. voice, audience, space, and influence) were non-existent. The education strategy in the bid documents could have been an avenue for children to contribute to how they want to be protected or “supported”. However, there was a lack of detail as to what these initiatives actually mean for children’s participation. Furthermore, the proposal to “fully support the IOC in its international initiatives such as ‘Sport for All’ and its activities in partnership with the United Nations” (Candidature File Vol 1, P. 14)

could be understood as an inclusive strategy, but again there was a dearth of detail on what exactly this would entail.

According to Giulianotti (2004), sport and recreation are vital for all children. There is a recognition in the policy documents directed at Tokyo 2020 Games that organizers understood the importance of sport for children and young people. This is reflected in the detailed participation strategies included in the policies and bid documents. As evidenced by Aina et al (2021), in the Candidature File, the Tokyo 2020 bid team identified a series of initiatives to encourage children to participate in the Games, mainly as spectators through socially-geared education programmes. These initiatives targeted children from areas impacted by the Great East Japan Earthquake, and those attending special needs schools, funded by the Tokyo Metropolitan Government:

One of Tokyo 2020's objectives is to promote Olympism to young people by encouraging them to participate in the Olympic and Paralympic celebrations and Tokyo 2020 will adopt successful policies such as London 2012's lower charge for children (Candidature File, Vol 1, p.100)

In this section, it is established that the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee had included a meaningful participatory opportunity for children, even though this opportunity was strictly for physical participation. The TOCOG had not formalised "voice" as part of the bidding strategy. Evidently in the bid documents, Article 12 of the UNCRC which suggests that children should be given a voice in events that concern them, was not taken into consideration in the planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

While Article 12 supports the democratisation of children in events that concern them, Article 19 of the UNCRC states that governments must do all they can to ensure that children are protected from all forms of violence, abuse, and neglect (Lundy, 2007). One of the ways this can be done is by making provisions for protection, formalising these strategies, just like for participation in mega

sporting events policies. This might be in the form of contracts (law binding) or guidelines. In this section I have presented findings on participation strategies in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies. In the next section I discuss the formalisation of provision for protections in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

6.4. Formalisation of child rights protection for provision strategies in the Tokyo 2020 Olympics policies

One of the concerns expressed by child rights activists is that child rights protection seems to be non-existent at the initial (bidding) stage for the Olympic Games. Drawing on examples of rights infringements in the Olympic Games, Gurgis and Kerr (2021) argue that despite the increased attention on safe sport initiatives in numerous countries around the world, advancements have been challenging, especially for children. They argue that the need to create a safe sport environment for children is crucial, especially in the planning phases of the Olympic Games. The UNCRC sets out very specific expectations relating to the protection of the child. Article 19 speaks of the importance of protecting children from violence, abuse and neglect (Aina, et.al. 2021). However, this study findings suggests that there were little or no evidence of child rights protection in any of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games documents. A review of documents guiding the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid (see Table 1) revealed no evidence of explicit child protection strategies incorporated during the bidding process for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The absence of explicit child rights policies for the Tokyo 2020 Games can be traced to the Olympic Charter. The Olympic Charter, which is the principal document that guides the selection process of Olympic host cities, contains all kinds of rights protection requirements, except for those referring to child rights. The Olympic Charter did not specify child rights protection as part of the host city selection criteria. On critical evaluation of the 106-paged Olympic Charter, the word “child” or “children” was never mentioned, even though the word “youth” was mentioned six times. In addition, it is

noteworthy that while the word “youth” was used six times, it was used primarily in the context of education–related guidelines, as opposed to human rights. While youths are categorised as humans between the ages of 15-24, Article One of the UNCRC categorized children differently:

For the purposes of the present Convention, a child means every human being below the age of 18 years unless under the law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier. (UNCRC, p.4)

To improve sustainability performance and avoid age-demographic confusion, specifying age groups in policies guiding mega events could make a difference to how child rights are addressed in mega sporting events. This is especially true in the context of child rights in the Olympic Games where child rights are, most often generalised under the “youth” or general “human rights” umbrella. As stated in the Olympic Charter, the practice of sport is a human right, and “every individual must have the possibility of practicing sport without discrimination of any kind and in the Olympic spirit” (p. 11). By “everybody”, it is assumed that children are included. While the Charter does not include specific guidelines for protecting human rights, it places the responsibility of maintaining the values of the Olympic Games on the IOC:

As leader of the Olympic Movement, the IOC is responsible for enhancing the values of the Olympic Movement and for providing material support in the efforts to organise and disseminate the Olympic Games, and supporting the IFs, NOCs and athletes in their preparations for the Olympic Games. The IOC is the owner of all rights in and to the Olympic Games and Olympic properties described in this Rule, which rights have the potential to generate revenues for such purposes. (p. 22).

This suggests that if child rights were to be handled effectively in the Olympic Games, the IOC would be responsible for “enhancing the values”, and by extension, child rights. According to Tur (2020), the IOC’s responsibility for “child protection in sports” is based on the Olympic Charter. This generates tension between the Charter and the IOC, drawing attention to who should be responsible for child rights in the Olympic Games. Going by the Olympic Charter, the responsibility falls on the IOC. However, there is, as yet, no formal document showing that the

IOC has embedded child rights practices in its policies and guidelines developed to guide the selection processes of host cities, or beyond. As noted by Rowe (2012), much has been written criticizing the IOC regarding the process and rationale for host city selection (Rowe, 2012). The Olympic Charter places the responsibility of ensuring that host cities adhere to its principles on the IOC, and the *Candidature Question and Answer* document developed by the IOC also holds the IOC accountable for ensuring that basic requirements are followed by host cities:

The IOC is responsible for accepting and refusing any file which does not comply with the presentation requirements (Candidature Question and Answer document (Candidature Question and Answer, 2019. p 206.230).

While recognizing that the IOC has a duty to enforce the Olympic Charter principles, host cities also have a duty to close the child rights accountability gap in the Olympic Games. For example, China leveraged its human rights infringement controversies to win the bid for Beijing Olympics 2008, by promising to use it to enhance human rights - even though this promise was broken (Kidd, 2010). In the case of Tokyo 2020, however, despite the well-documented occurrences of child rights infringements in the country (Ikeda, 1995), during the bidding process there is no evidence in bid documents of child rights being mentioned as strategic priority.

Just as the Olympic Charter and the IOC's *Candidature Question and Answer* document did not have child rights specifics, the official bid documents (Candidature file) presented by Tokyo did not address child rights either. The *Candidature File* did address general human rights obligations as specified by the Olympic Charter. Section 4.1 of the *Candidature File Vol. 1* titled "Fulfillment of obligations under the Olympic Charter and Host City Contract" had subsections for established systems to protect human rights from the Olympic Charter. These were guidelines such as "measures to counteract intellectual property rights infringements" (p. 038), as well as repercussions for anyone found infringing these rights. If child rights were obligatory in the

Olympic Charter, the Tokyo 2020 Games would have been required to address the issue in their bid document and provide detailed strategies as to how they were going to ensure child rights protection in the organization of the Games.

The *Candidature Acceptance Procedure* is another important document in the bidding process, as it is provided by the IOC to applicant cities in the first phase of the bid process. It contains explanations about the various steps in the application phase until the selection of the candidate cities by the IOC Executive Board. Examination of this document revealed that child rights were not specifically mentioned in the document, thereby undermining the importance of child rights. The *Candidature Acceptance Procedure* consisted of three parts: Part 1 detailed procedures, rules and deadlines to be respected by applicant cities. Part 2 detailed an IOC questionnaire that provides the structure of the Application File to be submitted to the IOC, while part 3 contained precise instructions on the presentations of an Applicant City's submission to the IOC. The only reference to rights was in section 1.4 where applicant cities were directed to the Olympic Charter, stating that host cities are obligated to comply with its regulations:

Each Applicant City has the obligation to comply with the Olympic Charter and with any other regulations or requirements issued by the IOC Executive Board, as well as with all the technical norms issued by the IFs for their respective sports. (*Candidature Acceptance Procedure*, p. 24_111).

Under the criteria for assessment of applications section, the *Candidature Acceptance Procedure* also stated that compliance with the Olympic Charter, amidst other documents, would be the basis of selection.

Compliance with the Olympic Charter, the IOC Code of Ethics, the Rules of conduct applicable to all cities wishing to organise the Olympic Games, the World Antidoping Code, this *Candidature Acceptance Procedure* and all other rules, instructions and conditions which may be established by the IOC (p. 31_111)

Virtually all the documents, policies and guidelines required to bid for the Olympic Games referred potential host cities to the Olympic Charter. Similarly, in the *Host City Contract*, the IOC entrusted the planning, organising, financing and staging of the Games to the city and National Organising Committee (NOC) with a reminder that these stakeholders have undertaken to fulfil their obligations with full compliance with the provisions of the Olympic Charter (p. 9). The ultimate decision to embed child rights protection measures in the guiding policies of the Olympic Games lies with the IOC and is then disseminated to organizers. Over the years, the Olympic Charter has evolved to include international human rights guidelines (Abeza, 2020). but there remains a lack of specificity about human rights and child rights in this important guiding document.

Brackenridge and Rhind (2014) have recommended making sport a safer space for children by building in protection measures in policies as early as possible. In the context of mega sporting events, the protection of child rights is more efficient at the planning phase, as host cities would then be required to develop strategies to protect and preserve child rights, right from the bidding phase. Referring to the conceptual model of applying rights-based approach to mega sporting events, McGillivray, Edwards, Brittain, Bocarro and Koenigstorfer (2019), argued that preservation starts with the bid and preplanning stage. More specifically, pathway three of the pathways to an embedded rights-based approach to mega sporting events presented the need for a formalisation of the human rights agenda, that is, commitment from awarding bodies to formalise policies that intentionally target positive human rights outcomes (McGillivray et al., 2019). Relating pathway three to the Tokyo 2020 context, having explicit child rights principles in the Olympic Charter would have made a difference to the delivery process of the Olympic Games. This would have produced greater accountability from both the IOC and prospective host countries because host cities are perceived as franchise holders obligated to acquiesce to the IOC requirements (Hiller, 2012). The Tokyo 2020 *Host City Contract*, contained no rules or laws to

ensure that host cities make provisions for rights protection of general athletes, never mind child athletes. The document made provisions for many forms of rights, ranging from rights of documentations, media and broadcasting rights, while also setting some conditions and principles against things that can be considered as acts against both human and child rights. In the context of child rights protection, the closest right in the *Host City Contract* is anti-doping protection rights. This is also like statements in the Olympic Charter and *Candidature File*. Although this right was generalised in the contract, it can also apply to children and young people as there would be some young people participating as athletes in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Section 24 of the Host City Contract states that:

The city, The NOC and the OCGC shall ensure that the Government upon request of the IOC shall provide its full cooperation and support for the implementation of the IOC Anti – Doping Rules applicable to the Games. Such cooperation and support shall, inter alia, relate to investigations and procedures regarding athletes’ support personnel or any other persons involved in trafficking, or in assisting in any way in relation to the use of prohibited substances or prohibited methods (Host City Contract, p. 24).

While Section 24 specifically requires that this right be upheld and everything done to ensure that provisions are made to ensure that section 24 of the Host City Contract is implemented, section 66 of the Host City Contract, on the other hand, suggests that failure to implement the rule shall incur a consequence of probable termination of contract:

Contract binding states that the IOC shall be entitled to terminate the contract and to withdraw the games from the City of there is a violation by the city, the NO or the OCGC of any material obligation pursuant to the contract, the Olympic Charter or under any applicable law (p. 72)

Given the severity with which the IOC can deal with failure to adhere to the Host City Contract, it can be assumed that were human rights commitments included then compliance would also have been a priority for the host city. This is especially the case since Human Rights Watch detailed child participation in Tokyo Sport as violent and abusive.

Participation in sport should provide children with the joy of play, and with an opportunity for physical and mental development and growth. In Japan, however, violence and abuse are too often a part of the child athlete's experience. As a result, sport has been a cause of pain, fear, and distress for far too many Japanese children. (Human Rights Watch, 2020).

As stated in the 2020 Candidature Acceptance Procedure (CAP) of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the general purpose of the host city contract is to:

Set out legal, commercial and financial rights and obligations of the IOC, the Host City and the NOC of the host country in relation to their specific Olympic Games. In case of conflict between the provisions of the Host City Contract and the charters, the Host City Contract shall take precedence (p. 7).

While the candidature acceptance procedure sets out the procedures expected of the host community, these are just 'expected procedures', as there are no guarantees that these procedures will be followed. Although both contractual documents (HCC and Candidature Acceptance Procedure) presented an overview of initiatives for children, however, these were not child rights protection initiatives.

6.5. Tokyo 2020 Change Management Plan

Mega sporting events have been known to have regenerative abilities. While some cities use mega sporting events for urban regeneration, others use these events to correct existing social vices, and change their world image. As Paton, Mooney and McKee (2012) suggest, the capacity of mega sporting events to regenerate cities is evident in the UK with the 2012 Olympic Games. Smith (2014) has argued that event-themed regeneration is not reliant on, or necessary for, staging an event. Instead, programmes are developed to "lever" the event to achieve wider policy objectives and reimagining. This was the case with Beijing (Gong 2012), and with Japan (Duignan, 2021). While there is no evidence that Japan bid for the Olympic Games to address social issues (human rights) like China did for Beijing 2008, there were pre-existing child rights issues in Japan which the government tried to address after winning the bid to host Tokyo 2020. As regards implementing child rights principles in planning and development approaches as part of the Tokyo 2020 Games,

there were no specific child rights principles and approaches in the planning and development approaches as part of the Tokyo 2020 Games. However, there were developments of strategies to ensure safety in the Games, generally. This was evident in the plan for a safe and low-risk Games security plan mentioned in the *Candidature file Vol 1* and the plan for sustainability in the *Tokyo 2020 Olympic Guidebook*. Regarding planning the Tokyo 2020 Games to enable the development of more inclusive (or exclusive) public spaces in enabling greater dialogue in relation to sensitive issues and the effects of urban development on most vulnerable. Tokyo 2020 stated in the *Candidature File* that alongside situating the Olympic Village in the re-invigorated Bay area of Tokyo, will also put the Games sport and spirit in the heart of the city.

The Olympic Village, the centre of the Games, will be situated in the re-invigorated Bay area of Tokyo, along with 21 of the competition venues and celebration sites. Twenty-eight of the 33 competition venues in Tokyo will be within eight kilometres of the Olympic and Paralympic Village. The highly compact Venues plan, fast and efficient public transport system and close accommodation will bring the Games and the community together and minimise athletes' travelling time (Pg. 006).

In the *Candidature File Vol 1*, the Tokyo 2020 organising committee promised to ensure that the Tokyo 2020 Games were a safe and secure celebration. According to the *Candidature File Vol 1*,

the renowned technological and operational excellence of Tokyo, combines with the compact venue plan, and efficient transport and accommodation plans, will make Tokyo 2020 a very low-risk Games for the Olympic movement" (Pg. 004).

Further to this, Tokyo 2020 proposed that in addition to employing their renowned technological and operational excellence, there would be a strong Games security plan to ensure that the Tokyo 2020 Games were a safe and secure celebration. Again, these are commitments to safety, alongside commitments to utilise public spaces to foster community engagement. However, the bidding documents of the Tokyo 2020 did not mention anything about commitments to ensure that construction of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic venues, transport infrastructures and other developmental changes did not have an adverse effect on the vulnerable populations, such as children.

The plan for sustainability, on the other hand, was explored in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Guidebook. While this document did not have a management plan strategy for child rights and venues in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, it did include plans for sustainability which included human rights. This document was developed by the TOCOG and in the document, it was noted that Japan is currently confronted with sustainability – related issues such as climate change, the depletion of natural resources, discrimination and human right issues (p.12). On the same page, it was also noted that for the Tokyo 2020 Games, under the plan to achieve their Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), the city would strive to realise a sustainable society and communicate their efforts as a model for the resolution of various issues across Japan and the world (p. 12). Further to the SDG plan, in the area of international cooperation, Japan announced at the United Nations High-Level Political Forum (HLPF) in 2017 that it was going to focus on issues pertaining to children and young generations and provide one billion U.S. dollars in assistance mainly for education, health, disaster risk reduction and gender by 2018 (p. 5). The plan for sustainability was further explored in the *Tokyo 2020 Sustainability Plan*. This plan includes human rights, and measures for human rights protection, in general:

The delivery of the Olympic Games is a great opportunity to progress respect for human rights, and diversity and inclusion in particular. We especially hope that the Tokyo 2020 Games will have positive impacts on the supply chain involved in procurement of a large volume of products and services, so that they will respect human rights in the process of procurement. Moreover, with the Tokyo 2020 Games as an impetus, we would like to promote diversity and inclusion inside and outside Japan, make real progress in human rights, and establish a meaningful step (Tokyo Sustainable Plan, p. 12).

As with the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Guidebook, there was no specific mention of child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan document, however, the commitment to SDG 2020 was prevalent. This has been argued by Sighinolfi (2019) to mean that Japan is promoting its nations’s ability to create a sustainable plan for the 2020 Tokyo Olympics. The Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan also

made general mention of plans to ensure that human rights are protected in all ramifications, including those who will be involved in the Games, starting from the preparation stage:

In Tokyo 2020 Games, we aim to firmly incorporate diversity and inclusion into all areas of the Games preparation and operation, with a view to respecting the human rights of all those involved in the Games (p. 15).

Similarly:

The Tokyo 2020 Games aim to avoid causing or contributing to any discrimination such as race, colour, sex, sexual orientation, never encourage any issues of child labour and excessive labour through the entire Games – related activities, even indirectly (p. 74).

Throughout the document, there were repeated mentions of child labour, and different plans to ensure that child labour infringements did not happen in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. The document noted, child labour is an ongoing issue both in and outside of Japan, hence, the need to actively address it and put measures in place to prevent its occurrence in the Tokyo 2020 Games.

As stated in the document:

In working environments, such as sites of resource extraction and production, we also have issues of child labour and forced labour inside and outside of Japan. In our nation, we are facing problems of excessive labour and working poverty.... (Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan, p. 74).

The Plan goes on to state that Tokyo 2020 aimed to spread the word about diversity, and provide training opportunities for staff, cooperation with stakeholders, secure accessibility (develop and implement guidelines), and promote actions at Games facilities and operations (p. 75). Some of these guidelines and measures are also stated in the Olympic Charter. While all these documents and strategies were developed before the Olympic Games, their influence and accountability has been debated by NGOs. It is one thing to put measures in place before hosting Games but it is another to ensure the implementation of the measures. Going by reports from NGOs and advocacy organizations, these commitments and pledges have not been implemented around the Tokyo 2020

Olympic Games. This has led to NGOs calling for the Japanese government to be more accountable to their commitments and pledges.

The Tokyo 2020 sustainable plan goes further than other documents in addressing rights, including child rights. However, this document was developed in 2017, around the time that IOC began to change its emphasis on rights. As detailed by Aina et al. (2021),

after the IOC strengthened its human rights requirements for the Paris 2024 Olympic Games edition, Tokyo 2020 organizers were asked to respond. Though not contractually obliged, organizers introduced limited additional commitments to respecting human rights, labour and business practices in the Tokyo 2020 Sustainability Plan, Version 2.

Under the “consideration of human rights” section of this Plan, this increased focus on human rights was associated with the IOCs adoption of Olympic Agenda 2020:

The Olympic Agenda 2020 also states that the host city contract should include clauses with regard to the Fundamental Principle 6 of the Olympic Charter as well as to environmental and labour-related matters and Host City contracts after Paris 2024 includes compliance with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (The Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan Version 2, p. 74).

Additionally, the Sustainable Plan Version 2 document noted that Tokyo 2020 aimed to avoid causing or contributing directly and indirectly to discrimination and human rights abuses through the entire Games-related process. As a form of provision to prevent these infringements from happening at the Games, the Sustainable Plan Version 2 proposes that organizers would “prepare a communication system and properly understand the situation of human rights consideration issues” (p. 75) and in the event of infringements occurring it would “proactively request correction to abusers and protect victims” (p. 76). Evidently, rights were strengthened in the lead up to the Tokyo 2020 Games delivery. Furthermore, in the revised edition of the Tokyo Sustainable Plan (Sustainable sourcing code), version 3, there were specific mentions of compliance with the convention on the Rights of the Child. As stated on the document,

Throughout the production, distribution and other processes of procured products, suppliers should respect children's rights, and give due consideration to ensuring safety in providing products and services for children and supporting parents and guardians who take care of children, in addition to stopping child labour, in order to encourage children's healthy growth (Tokyo 2020 Sustainable plan Version 3, pg 7.)

Although, these initiatives were not originally included in the Tokyo 2020 bid documents, however it was evident that the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee gave thoughts to their change management plan, and how it could inadvertently affect children, especially in the context of child labor. Not only did they consider children, they also made plans to ensure that safety is ensured when providing products for children and their guardians.

6.6. Conclusion

The documentation analyzed in this chapter suggests a lack of focus on child rights in the bidding and planning documents for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. In the documents examined, there were few references to child rights and general human rights provisions which can be traced to a similar absence in the Olympic Charter and the bidding requirements provided by the IOC prior to 2017. When children were the focus of discussion, the emphasis tended to be on participation and intent to leverage the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games for the purpose of regeneration and exposure. While sport participation, inclusion and leveraging can be beneficial to children, concerns still exist about how hosting the Olympic Games can proactively improve child rights. The bidding documents referred to the London 2012 Olympics, stating that Tokyo would adopt the London 2012 Olympics strategies of inclusion. However, there is evidence that Tokyo 2020 also replicated the mistakes of the London 2012 Games by prioritising event-associated developments, while forgetting the implications for inclusion (Dowse, et al, 2018). In the case of Tokyo 2020, the implications for inclusion might also manifest in the neglect of child participants protection.

In this chapter, I have also shown that the Japanese government and Games organizers did begin to think about child rights through the Japan Human Rights and Commitment Pledges document

and the Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan. I argue that these changes came to be because of advocacy organisations' influence. For example, in the period between 2011 and 2019, there were no mentions of child rights protection strategies in the Tokyo 2020 documents. Child rights mentions in the policies only started to peak, and became prominent between 2019 and 2020, after several advocacy organisation intervention. However, while these commitments were welcome, NGOs like HRW and the charity UNICEF have indicated that these plans were not enough. The problem of child rights abuse in Japanese sport was consistently mentioned in the NGO documents examined, including the inadequacy of protocols around Tokyo 2020 to address these effectively. Moreover, there was little evidence that children had a voice in the planning and delivery stages of the Tokyo 2020. Tokyo 2020 organizers only made plans for physical participation, while neglecting the other aspects of participation proposed by Lundy (2007) – voice, space and audience. There was no evidence of children being consulted in the planning stages of the Tokyo 2020 Games even though there was an opportunity to do so through the educational initiatives mentioned in bid and planning documents. This could have provided an avenue for meaningful engagement and consultation with children.

Examining published documents is only one element of the planning of a mega sporting event. It is also important to subject these published commitments to critical scrutiny through engagement with strategic stakeholders and affiliates of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Interviews were conducted to address some of the shortfalls of the documentary analysis. These findings and discussion are presented in chapter seven.

CHAPTER 7: BEYOND PROVISION AND PROTECTION: MAKING CHILD INCLUSION A STRATEGY

7.1. Introduction

Chapter six focused on an in-depth assessment of child rights documentation and policies that have influenced the planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games mainly from the perspectives of provision for protection. The findings showed that despite identifying generic support for human rights at national government level, there were little or no detailed provisions for child rights protection evident in relation to the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games in the policies and principles considered. I discussed the structures and governance plans put in place before and after the bid. In doing so, I addressed research question two. This built on research question one which was addressed in the literature review section, albeit in the general mega sporting events context. In order to further assess the child rights situation in preparation for the Games, triangulating data sources, it was important to explore other forms of data to complement the findings generated from document analysis. Therefore, seven semi-structured interviews were conducted with stakeholders involved in either child rights advocacy, Games organisation or government policy. These included five NGO stakeholders, one policy developer and one member of the TOCOG. Interviews focused on themes relating to child rights protection provision, participation, inclusion, and management plan to leverage on child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games.

As mentioned earlier, the literature review section addressed research question one, in the general context of mega sporting events. Chapter 6 also addressed research question two. However, before addressing research question three in this chapter, there was a need to address research question one, from the perspective of respondents. Exploring the respondent's knowledge on the dimensions of child violations expected in the Tokyo 2020 Games helped in assessing their understanding of their roles, as stakeholders, in ensuring that the Tokyo 2020 Games were delivered in compliance with the UNCRC in the context of Article 12 (child participation). In

addition, the discussion of the negative and positive impacts of mega sporting events also highlights the importance of research question two, which focuses on the importance of having measures in place to mitigate child abuse in mega sporting events.

Structurally, this chapter provides an overview of the impacts of mega sporting events on children. Following the positive and negative impacts, I then present the theme of provision for protection, and participation drawing on Lundy’s model of child participation: space, voice, audience, and influence. Due to the sensitivity of the topic of discussion and ethical considerations, as mentioned in Section 5.9, all interviewees have been anonymised, and given identifiers (see Table 2 below).

Table 2: Interview list

IDENTIFIER	ROLE
Interviewee A	Representative of the Tokyo 2020 Organising Committee
Interviewee B	Child rights lead at an international human rights organisation
Interviewee C	Child rights advocate and athlete protection lead
Interviewee D	Child rights lawyer / coalition member of an international human rights organisation
Interviewee E	Policy developer for a child rights charity organisation
Interviewee F	Child labour chair for an international child rights organisation
Interviewee G	Child trafficking representative for an international child rights organisation

7.2. Positive participation impacts of mega sporting events on children

Before focusing specifically on child rights issues around Tokyo 2020 it is important to understand more about respondents’ general perceptions of mega sporting events and their impact on children,

whether in the role of volunteer, resident, or athlete as this is also pertinent to answering this study's first research question. As outlined in section 4.5, the first research question is to find out the dimensions of child rights infringement in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Before the discussion about the negative impact, there was a general discussion about the positive and negative impacts of the Games with the respondents.

Each interviewee had been part of mega sporting events in one way or the other and witnessed or experienced the negative impacts of the event on children. However, they were also keen to note the positive impacts on children arising from the planning of the Games. Overall, all respondents spoke positively about the potential impacts of hosting mega sporting events like the Olympic Games. Similarly, various NGOs have carried out independent studies on the impacts of hosting mega sporting events. While some of these independent studies (see Chapter 5 documentary analysis) have commented on the negative social impact of hosting the Games such as human and child rights infringements, NGO interviewees for this study noted that mega sporting events have positive impacts on children. A representative of one Human Rights Organisation mentioned that a positive impact not talked about sufficiently is the "sense of belonging" and "pride" that child athletes feel when they participate in mega sporting events. Due to the significant media coverage of the events, child athletes are usually proud of themselves, and "sometimes, this also boosts their self-esteem" (Interviewee B). Commenting further on the positive impact of hosting mega sporting events on child participants, one respondent mentioned that "regardless of whatever organizations say about the negative impacts of hosting mega sporting events, there is no denying that child athletes feel joy when they participate in mega sporting events" (Interviewee B). One of the values of Olympism is to make sport enjoyable for children, so that both child athletes and child spectators find it enjoyable to participate in the Olympic Games. Interviewee C, a child rights lead and advocate at a renowned human rights organisation noted that having spoken to child athletes and

volunteers, “we usually find out that they never forget that they were a part of events that big. It’s a lifelong legacy for them”. This recognizes that lifelong legacies also include intangible social impacts, even though these are especially difficult to measure and need to be periodically examined in the years to come (Wise, 2019).

7.3 Negative impacts of mega sporting events on children

In the past five years, academics and human rights advocacy organizations have been actively drawing attention to the negative impacts of mega sporting events on host communities. In interviews conducted for this study, most respondents spoke of the negative impacts of hosting mega events on children’s rights. Recent studies have suggested that sometimes hosting mega sporting events can result in considerable negative socio–psychological impacts (Barreda, Zubieta, Chen, Cassilha and Kageyama, 2017). Corroborating this view, Interviewee B, a child rights organisation representative, suggested that in terms of harms and violations of children around mega sporting events, it is a long list including “displacements, sexual abuse, child labour and psychological impacts”. Interviewee C, a child rights advocate, suggested that the psychological impacts of these events are often neglected. Speaking from their experiences of past mega sporting events, Interviewee B said that:

We have had to look at what happens to elite child athletes in terms of violations of their rights. In terms of harms and violations, it is a long list. However, the aspect that is least spoken about alongside the physical abuse is psychological abuse (Interviewee B)

The negative psychological impact of mega sporting events can be examined in the context of two categories of children - child athletes and children who want to participate as volunteers and athletes but have been restricted based on their parents’ preferences or medical issues. While children who participate in mega sporting events feel a sense of belonging and pride in their sport (Lau, Fox and Cheung, 2004), children who cannot be participants but want to, feel differently. There is evidence that they feel left out or discriminated against. This was confirmed in an

interview with an Independent Human Rights Organisation, speaking about those unable to participate:

These children feel left out and discriminated when they see children of their age participating in the Olympics while they only get to watch on their TVs (Interviewee B)

In the context of Tokyo 2020, Interviewee A mentioned that:

Psychological abuse is anticipated. Stress might be taken out on kids that are participating in terms of harassment and body shaming. There might be talks like “You did not do well”, “you should do better”, and so on, which might have adverse effects on the mental health of children participating in the Games. Unfortunately, this kind of impact is hard to measure (Interviewee B)

While Interviewee B suggested that it is hard to measure the psychological impacts of mega sporting events on children, they also suggested that adequate provisions for child rights could reduce the level of impacts of mega sporting events on children. In their words:

Speaking about child rights and impacts, measuring the risks on children are proportionally limited. Especially the psychological impact. Hence, constant monitoring and making provisions for children, to prevent them from being psychologically impacted, in these events cannot be overemphasized (Interviewee B)

This reinforces McCullough, Orr and Watanabe’s (2019) argument about the importance of monitoring and measuring social impacts in order to manage subsequent potential risks on children in the context of mega sporting events. Interviewee F stressed that the effect of hosting mega sporting events on child rights should “not be taken with levity”. Supporting what Interviewee B said about making adequate provisions for children in mega sporting events, Interviewee G submitted that there must be some form of provision made by host cities, organising committees, and NGOs before hosting the Olympic Games. This supports McGillivray et al’s (2019) argument about the roles that advocacy organizations must play in ensuring that provisions are made to protect human rights in mega sporting events. Speaking about the roles they have been playing in ensuring that there are no negative impacts in the Tokyo 2020 Games, a high percentage of

advocacy organizations interviewed were concerned about the issues of child labour, exploitation and trafficking in Tokyo, Japan. These concerns are discussed in sections 7.3.1 and 7.3.2 below.

7.3.1. Child labour and exploitation

The issue of child labour and exploitation came up frequently in chapter 6 (documentary analysis) and this was further highlighted in interviewee responses. Several documents related to the Tokyo 2020 Games mentioned that child labour is an ongoing issue in Tokyo. For example, *Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan* documented that child labour is an ongoing issue both in and outside of Japan, hence, the need to actively address it and put measures in place to prevent its occurrence in the Tokyo 2020 Games. As stated in the document:

In working environments, such as sites of resource extraction and production, we also have issues of child labour and forced labour inside and outside of Japan. In our nation, we are facing problems of excessive labour and working poverty (Tokyo 2020 Sustainable Plan document, p. 74).

Interview respondents corroborated this by stating that child labour exploitation and child trafficking were high on the agenda of potential harm caused by mega sporting events for children. Speaking about their concerns for children at the Tokyo 2020 Games, Interviewee A, a member of the organising committee corroborated the findings about child labour in the documentary analysis as “correct information”. He confirmed that child labour in Japan is an ongoing issue and that “children are abused and made to participate in labour in exchange for money, child participants in mega sporting events are especially exploited as the income generated from their participation in elite sports go to their guardians or representatives” (Interviewee A). Speaking further on the dimension of child labour and exploitation, he mentioned that:

Some children get paid for working in Olympic sites, while some do not get paid. The Japanese government is aware of this, they actually highlighted the issue and the last I know they were trying to intervene or eradicate the issue of child labour in the context of the Olympics, specifically in the supply chain department (Interviewee A)

Evidently, the supply chains have been problematic in the past, considering the attention the issue of child labour has received, and is still receiving. For example, in 2012, the London 2012 Organising Committee (LOCOG) had to adopt the Ethical Trading Initiative Base (ETIB) Code of Conduct as a contractual obligation for suppliers of licensed Olympic goods for the London 2012 Olympic Games (Dowse, Powell and Weed, 2018) to mitigate child labour in the London 2012 Olympics. Linking this to the situation in Japan, Interviewee F, an independent Human Rights NGO based in Japan, also noted that there has been a case of ongoing exploitation and child labour in Japan.

Most respondents also articulated the need for the Japanese government to do more in order to reduce child labour to the barest minimum in Japan. First, there was a recognition from most respondents that acknowledging the issue is not enough, “there needs to be an adequate plan in place to address it effectively” (Interviewee D). Interviewee D, while articulating the need for an adequate plan to address child labour violations in the country also noted the importance of intensifying measures against child labour associated with the Tokyo 2020 Games, especially for child athletes. They mentioned, “If adequate care is not taken, some child athletes might be exploited for commercial purposes at the 2021 Games and made to do free labour in exchange for being in the Olympics”. They went further to note that:

Many of the child athletes are working very hard to be able to play in the Olympic tournaments and of course, some of these athletes are not paid. Based on the structure, we can say that high school elite athletes have been continually exploited for commercial purposes. And it’s really bad that these kids do not know what is being done to them, they never think of the economic aspect of playing in the Games, and that is the reason why there are being exploited (Interviewee D)

This supports Donnelly’s (1997) argument that the problems associated with children’s involvement in high – performance sport are related to the issue of child labour. As a way of curbing this, Donnelly (1997) suggested that child labour laws should be enforced in elite sport. Also speaking

to the importance of enforcing child labour law to combat child labour and child athlete exploitation in the Olympics, Interviewee B mentioned that including child labour laws in the policies, rules and regulations binding the Olympic Games would be an effective way of delivering a child rights conscious event. Explaining why labour laws have not been introduced by the government in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games, Interviewee F suggested that “we have few entities which represent the child in this regard” (Interviewee F). However, according to Dowse, Powell and Weed (2018), until event owners require adherence to specific labour standards as conditions of hosting child labour, exploitation is unlikely to be completely eradicated in the Olympic Games.

7.3.2. Child Trafficking

Child trafficking was another issue of concern for interviewees. According to Brackenridge, Rhind and Palmer-Felgate (2015), previous Olympic Games editions have experienced an increase in the risk of child trafficking with evidence of cases of human trafficking for sexual exploitation affecting children. Interviewee G suggested that child trafficking is a feature of staging mega sporting events. Based on their experience from being based in Japan for some months in advance of the planned 2020 event, some human rights organizations confirmed cases of child trafficking, albeit they suggest that there is little that the government can do about it. As Interviewee G mentioned in relation to the Tokyo 2020 Games:

What we have previously studied for Japan is that Japan, on our list, is one of the leading countries for trafficking and sexual exploitation. There are loads of cases of trafficking and exploitation of minors (children under 18) that is currently being handled by our partner organisation. And it is so bad that the parents and the police aren't helping either (Interviewee G)

Interviewee F also confirmed that “trafficking does exist in Japan. It is just not spoken about”. Responding to the question of identified trafficking issues in Japan, which might be exacerbated during the Olympic Games, two respondents suggested that NGOs need to take over some of the

responsibility for monitoring child trafficking that might come up during the Tokyo 2020 Games. In their words “There is only so much that the government can do about this trafficking while the Games are on” (Interviewee G) and “that’s why there needs to be NGOs who would be willing to champion this cause” (Interviewee B). Interviewee B also suggested that.

NGOs are duty bearers. They would be perfect to handle trafficking cases in the Games, as they do not rely on the Government. It is just that some of these NGOs sometimes need to be careful in the way they report their cases. Sometimes, they are too critical of the host government (Interviewee B).

While both Interviewee B and Interviewee G argued that NGOs could play an important part in how trafficking associated with the Olympic Games are addressed, Interviewee A and Interviewee D argued that making initial provisions in the planning stage would be the most efficacious approach to protect children from harm before and during the Games. All respondents agreed that putting in place specific provisions is important, but also acknowledged that timing is crucial if they are to have any meaningful effects. Interviewee G specifically suggested that education and training about indicators of trafficking being embedded in policies ahead of the Games would go a long way. “This would make it so that host cities do not have a choice but to carry out the requirements” (Interviewee G).

As mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, this study is focusing on one of the negative impacts of mega sporting events on children – child rights. As noted by the interviewees, child rights infringements is a recurring occurrence in mega sporting events which needs to be addressed. The sections above have highlighted specific ways through which these rights infringements occur, mainly on child participants. As noted in chapter 6, the bid documents and policies of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games encouraged physical participation, while leaving out other important aspects of participation, such as giving children a voice in the decision-making

processes. Because the bid documents and policies encouraged child participation, albeit without provision for protection strategies for participants, interviews were conducted to explore whether there were measures in place to mitigate child rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games, from a participation model perspective. As evidenced by respondents, documented in section 7.2, children benefit psychologically and inspirationally from mega sporting events. However, to mitigate the negative impacts from these events, a lot needs to be done in the aspect of child inclusion (Aina et. Al, 2021). The following sections will now present interview findings on participation in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, using Lundy's (2007) participation model.

7.4. Lundy's model of space

The previous sections have given insights into the importance of having provisions for protection measures in place in advance of the Olympic Games. As evident from interviews, as regards the potential positive and negative impacts of hosting mega sporting events on children, especially participants, provisions for protections being formalised in policies before the delivery of mega sporting events will prevent wider harms to children in mega sporting events. According to Aina et al (2021), amongst other places, abuses occur against children in mega sporting events, and this calls for child rights protection practiveness. Using Article 12 of the UNCRC as foundation, Lundy (2007) proposed models of child participation for events. Even though the study conducted by Lundy (2007) was titled "models for participation", these models cover basic provision measures for children. The model reflects the fact that provision and participation are interrelated. According to Lundy (2007), if stakeholders are really interested in engaging the child, then making room for them to actively get involved is essential. As explained by Dolev – Cohen, Ricon and Levkovich (2020), making room for dialogue is essential because many violated minors do not have a choice but to take responsibilities of their violations alone because they don't feel safe enough to talk

about their experiences. The documentary analysis chapter (chapter 6) examined the policies in place for child rights protection in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, highlighting that there was no evidence in the policies as regards provision for child involvement, especially in the aspect of giving children space to express their views without fear of rebuke or reprisal. The closest to “space” in the documentary analysis was found in the *Candidature file* where the TOCOG promised to introduce educational programmes for youths through sport and encouraged international sport exchange (pg. 14). Speaking about the proposal for educational programmes, as stated in the policies of the Tokyo 2020 Games, Interviewee G, attested to the fact that the Tokyo Metropolitan Government developed an educational curriculum to educate children about their rights in school, and this was adopted ahead of the Tokyo 2020 Games through the socially geared education programme. While this initiative appears to be a positive and proactive development that could have been beneficial for children, Interviewee G also went further to comment that “there is an uncertainty as to how substantial the provisions are, as well as the effectiveness of this education programme for the 2020 Games” (Interviewee G).

As regards providing a safe space for children to report and express their views, interviewees confirmed that it was often left to advocacy groups to set up provisions that were subsequently deemed effective. For example, according to Interviewee E, TOCOG had tried to install hotlines as a child reporting mechanism. These hotlines were installed in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games as a proactive measure to encourage cases of child rights abuse to be reported. These proposed safe space hotlines were in line with the protection measures stated in the *Tokyo Sustainable Plan Version 2*. In the document, it was proposed that organizers ‘would prepare a communication system and properly understand the situation of human rights consideration issues’ (p.75). However, there were some concerns expressed by interviewees as regards the effectiveness of this mechanism since its inception. Interviewee D highlighted that while the Japanese Government

should be commended for creating a hotline, there was ‘ineffectiveness in the reporting system because there is no way to extract abuse data if at all any child calls in to report an instance of rights abuse’. Furthermore, Interviewee D also stated that the hotlines were inaccessible and only available at limited times (between 1pm and 5pm). Further to noting the unavailability of the reporting mechanism, Interviewee D also mentioned that there were some discrepancies among the federation that set up the hotline, in the sense that, “any person who is not authorised by the federation cannot use the reporting system”.

In addition, Interviewee F also noted that the reporting system is not friendly for child athletes which corroborates Interviewee D’s specific research finding about the hotlines. In Interviewee D’s words:

After seven years of hotlines provision, “we have no statistics about the usage of each hotline” (HRNGO, interview). Because the national hotline was inaccessible to both elite athletes and child athletes, JOC provided a specific hotline to address the inaccessibility issue. The JOC also restricts the number of people who can use the hotline, “only athletes at the national level can use it” (Interviewee D).

Corroborating the reporting mechanisms’ ineffectiveness, Interviewees F and G also independently stated that all the reporting hotlines in Japan one year before the Olympic Games suffered from inadequacies that needed to be remedied. Some of their concerns about the hotlines had to do with the communication system automatically programmed into the call lines. As observed by Interviewee F, despite that the hotlines were created for international purposes (the Tokyo 2020 Games), for an international audience, the hotlines could only be heard in Japanese language. This means that foreign persons who had knowledge of the Japanese language, or Japanese representatives of the child would only have access, while other with no knowledge of the Japanese language would have no access to the hotline. This defeated the purpose of why the reporting mechanism was created in the first place. According to Interviewee F:

We realised that the hotlines were provided in advance of the Games so that abused children can report. We also realised that when we attempted to call these lines, the only available language was Japanese. This means that child athletes, possibly from other nations, who do not understand the Japanese language cannot report (Interviewee F).

In addition to this, while also noting that the hotlines could only be heard in Japanese, Interviewee G and their organisation also corroborated that calls placed to these hotlines were not free as advertised by the federations that created the hotlines. Interviewee F, while commenting on the hotlines explained, “We had to pay to speak to someone on the hotline. How are minors expected to get the funds to be able to report? (Interviewee F). Thus, in order to remedy the situation, Interviewee F stated that their organisation, in alliance with another human rights organisation, came up with an initiative to set up an alternative hotline, which would solve the problem of accessibility, data accountability and language barriers that the government hotlines had. They said that:

Our hotline is entirely free. We have been in works with our current partners in Tokyo. We want to be ready, we want to have something in place for the children who will be involved in the Games. Moreover, this is not exclusive to child athletes and children in the host communities; we are also concerned about child athletes and visitors who will be attending the Games from other parts of the world (Interviewee G).

The coming together of these advocacy organizations to provide a substitute hotline speaks to the important work advocacy organizations undertook to implement some standards of child rights provisions in advance of the Olympic Games. According to Bloodgood (2011), advocacy organizations cannot compete with states in terms of coercive capability or money, but they can provide solutions to some issues that the government cannot immediately provide solutions for. Alternatively, they can hold governments accountable to some standards (Clark, 1995).

Two representatives from human rights organizations mentioned that they held meetings with the Japanese government at least twice in 2019, in advance of the planned 2020 Games. These meetings provided opportunities for them to raise their concerns about child rights and submit

child rights protection proposals to the Japanese government. “Some of the measures that we presented to them were added to the *Sustainable Plans* document of the Tokyo 2021 Games” (Interviewee E). There, however, remained some concerns as regards the implementation of the sustainable plan. Interviewee D was concerned as to whether the plans are enough to combat child rights abuses. They were also concerned that some of the plans were not clear enough. Referring to the article “I was hit so many times I can’t count”, published by HRW in 2019. Interviewee D agreed, “there is indeed a high record of child rights abuse in the sporting system in Japan, and the lack of clear and accurate safe space provision for imminent child abuse reporting is one of the reasons why child athletes in Japan get abused” (Interviewee D). This also correlates with the Human Rights Watch’s report about child athletes’ abuse in Japan and the need for ‘clear and comprehensive reform’ to eliminate abusive coaching techniques and protect children (HRW, 2020). Ideally, the hotline provided would have been a good approach to getting an insight into how children are being abused, while also using the data generated from the incoming calls to create a protective strategy, however, Interviewee D suggested that perhaps things are not seen from that perspective because “sometimes, the way everybody goes about child rights protection differs”. In addition to providing reporting mechanisms, which other interviewees argued to be ineffective, Interviewee A commented that, the TOCOG had plans to create a safe space institute for children who would need help as a result of hosting the Olympic Games. In their words “the Organising Committee of Tokyo 2020 proposed to create an institution called *The Centre for Safe Sport* for children in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games” (Interviewee A). This initiative was a joint effort of the JOC, TOCOG and the Japanese government. “Even though unofficial, this institution would provide adequate protection for children, as employees at this institution would most probably be lawyers” (Interviewee A). While noting the difference it would make both to

child athletes and to Japanese children in general, Interviewee A believed the institution has the potential of being a lifelong legacy institution for the Japanese people:

I think it would make sense to establish a child athlete protection centre whose main purpose is to advocate for children and children who will be involved in the Games. Based on the current report by Human Rights Watch, the government has gotten curious about doing something in the new legislature about the child/child athlete. One of the ideas we came up with is to establish a child safe sport centre for child athletes during the Olympic Games, and then we can enhance the idea to include purposes for it to become a legacy for child athletes in a broader way (Interviewee A)

Evident from the statement, Human Rights Watch was able to put pressure on the IOC, the JOC, the TOGOC and the Japanese Government through their findings and report to create the safe space. This institution, even though yet to be actualised, was recognized by Interviewee D to be a move in the right direction, “This institution would be an inclusive one; I believe the JOC would be creating measures based on the recommendations in the United Nations Convention of the Rights of Child (Interviewee D). Working alongside the JOC to create this institution, Interviewee D described their vision and mission for the institution to be a centre with the authority to investigate abuse in sport. In addition:

The centre will have the authority to investigate abuse in sport, and it will also have the authority to enforce sanctions on abusive coaches, and also publish their position and gather statistics about their case so that they do not have the liberty to coach child athletes anymore (Interviewee D)

Speaking of the probability of the centre being ready in time for the 2020 Olympic Games, Interviewee A stated that their plan was to get the institution up and running before then. “It’s still a long way to go, but of course before the 2020 Olympic Games is the target” (Interview A). However, based on information from HRW after the Games, the center for safe sport was not established before the Tokyo 2020 Games, neither has it been established since the Games ended. In a letter published by HRW in October 2021, titled “Japan Safe Sport Joint Letter” HRW requested for the Tokyo sport organization to establish the safe sport centre.

Interviewee A mentioned that since the Japanese Sport Organisation's hotline yielded little to no results, the institution was meant to "help further with reporting should help further with reporting" (Interviewee A). While the proposed safe space proposal had commendations from advocacy organizations, it also sparked "displeasure and opposition from conservatives and coaches" (Interviewee A):

There have been many oppositions, from of course, all the conservatives and passionate coaches who have been saying 'is this necessary?', and 'we can solve these issues by ourselves', or 'no new legislation/institution is needed' and things like that (Interviewee A).

In terms of dialogue between the JOC, TOGOC and the Tokyo 2020 child athletes coach there was little evidence to suggest that the organising committee members had any meeting with the coaches and prospective child athletes to discuss all the proposed safe sport centre. While highlighting the proactivity of the organising committee in developing substitute plans for the failed hotline reporting mechanisms, Interviewee D highlighted that "it is still not enough to make provisions to prevent negative impacts in the Tokyo 2020 Games, there should be an assurance of the sustainability of the provisions before, during, and after the Games" (Interviewee D). Sustainability in this context means, "having documents to back up the actions" (Interviewee B). In the documentary analysis, it was noted that Japan had a sustainable plan to limit child rights infringements. It is noteworthy to mention that there was no record of the proposed *Safe sport institution* in the Tokyo 2020 sustainable plan documentation. Also, as noted after the Games had been delivered, the safe sport institution was not developed before and after the delivery of the Tokyo 2020 Games. Based on the findings of this study, there was no evidence that children were given a safe and inclusive space to express their views.

7.5. Voice and Audience

Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child establishes the right of every child to freely express his or her views in all matters affecting them, and the subsequent right for those views to be given due weight, according to the child's age and maturity (pg. 5). However, this study found little evidence that children were consulted before and after the bid to host the Tokyo 2020 Games. High profile organizations such as HRW have documented the extent to which children, especially child athletes, were neglected in Tokyo in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games. In Chapter 6, I demonstrated that that the bid documents emphasized physical participation, as different initiatives were developed such as making tickets cheaper for children to encourage physical participation. However, as Lundy argued, physical participation is not enough. As evident in the documentary analysis, the aspect of voice was missing in the Tokyo 2020 bid documents and policies. Similarly, interviewees confirmed that this was also the case for the Tokyo 2020 Games planning, as there was no evidence that children had been given a voice and audience in advance of the Games. Giving a reason for why children were not given a voice, Interviewee D noted that there was no chance for children to be given a voice. He also went further to note that "even if children were given a voice, there is the probability that no child would speak out or speak up". Independently, five out of the seven interviewees agreed that it is hard for children in Japan to speak out. While Interviewee A attributed the inability to get child athletes to speak out in Japan to cultural preservation, Interviewee D attributed the inability to speak up and speak out to culture and fear of what might happen if they speak up, especially if these children have been abused in some way. Stating examples, Interviewee D mentioned that "some of the concerns of child participants in the Olympics, especially elite child athletes, is that they might lose their spot if words get out that they had spoken to authorities". In the context of the Tokyo 2020 Games, they

went on to suggest that the average Japanese child thinks of their culture before anything else, and this could not have been different for Tokyo 2020 Japanese child participants.

When a child feels like they have been exploited, they will not speak out because they will stand out. Someone will make a fuss and they will embarrass their family in that way. Even if the family will not feel embarrassed, the perception of the child is that they have brought embarrassment to their family. Harmony is really important in the Japanese culture, and they will do anything to preserve that (Interviewee D)

Similarly, a member of the organising committee corroborated Interviewee D's observation. They submitted that it is very difficult to get child athletes to talk in Japan, because the prevailing culture does not support children speaking up (Interviewee A). Speaking further, they mentioned that most of them cannot speak up. A statement which was corroborated by Interviewee D. As explicitly stated, this is because of the Japanese hierarchical structure: As interviewee D stated

It's a luxury due to the culture and the hierarchical nature of the Japanese people. Especially the younger generation in Japan, they can hardly speak to their management or senior people due to the hierarchy (Interviewee D)

Other than the cultural hierarchical pressure against the child, Interviewee D also noted that the elite child athlete, participating in the Tokyo 2020 Games must also deal with similar situations with their coaches. According to Interviewee D, "Child athletes in Japan do not have control over themselves, they are answerable to their coaches, and there is little they can say about issues concerning them", and:

The Japanese culture is also not helping because there is a lot of hierarchy. The environment favours abuse, if a child athlete is being abused by the firm they belong to, they will still definitely find it hard to complain or suggest reformation ideas (Interviewee D):

As a way of working around the system to find a common ground for children who planned to participate in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, Interviewees D and E, respectively, suggested that legal representation and options of anonymity was the only feasible way to have given children a voice and audience in the Tokyo 2020 Games. This, according to Interviewee E, would produce

better results and enable abused children to speak up without fear of repercussions. As Interviewee D describes it, “the first point of action is for children/child athletes to have an adequate representation so that they can comfortably say their mind without fear of being harassed by their coaches or other people”. Contrary to Interviewee D’s submission about representation being the first call of action, Interviewee F argued that “hearing the child” is the first call. In their words, “for a child to be adequately represented, they need to be heard”. Howard and Madrigal (1990) suggested that perhaps parents are the best representatives in speaking on behalf of the child, because, sometimes, it’s their responsibility. However, Everley (2020) suggests that this might mean that parents would choose accomplishment instead of wellbeing. Interviewee A suggested that adult representation does not necessarily translate to voice and audience for the child. Interviewee A also noted further that the TOGOC pushed more for physical child participation, as this meant that the child would actually be the one participating, and not the guardian. Interviewee A went on to note that child volunteers and child athletes had already signed up for Tokyo 2020. However, as stated by Interviewee E, although participation can be a thing of pride, especially as child athletes, Japanese parents still have a hold on their children, thus child inclusion by means of participation might be dependent on their permission. While this is not necessarily a bad thing, it can make child inclusion impossible, which can potentially impact the child’s wellness and social inclusion (Prilleltensky, 2010).

While some of the interviewees spoke about the reasons why children were not given a voice in the Tokyo 2020 Games, Interviewee F mentioned that their organisation made attempts to speak to some children and child athletes in advance of the Games. They, however, noted that they encountered difficulties in their attempt to approach some of the children. While they attributed the child athletes inaccessibility to the fact that these child athletes were always with their

guardians or coaches, They also attributed their difficulty in gaining access to these child athletes to the Japanese culture. In their words:

Approaching children in Japan was difficult; hence, we were not able to get any child to contribute to our child protection campaign. They are either with their parents or being chaperoned by school guardians (Interview F)

Because of the resistance Interviewee F and their organisation faced in their attempts to reach out to children, physically, both Interviewee F and Interviewee G mentioned that they had to re-strategize by devising other means to reach out to child athletes and prospective volunteers. They mentioned that they had to work alongside local organizations, as well as pushing their campaign through digital means.

Four of the respondents who are representatives of child rights organizations in Japan, made reference to the pandemic causing disruptions and uncertainties. However, their respective organizations continued to attempt to create awareness about their child rights protection initiatives. Interviewee G, who oversaw the Tokyo 2020 campaign for their organisation stated that the 2020 postponement was leveraged as an opportunity to create awareness about their organisation and their child rights protection strategies, should the Games go ahead. Interviewee F, on the other hand, stated that they continue to strike alliances with some local companies such as Air BnB and hotel owners, and other places where their campaigns would be effective. The importance of having platforms and running campaigns on digital mediums was also highlighted by Interviewee F as this was important if they had to reach a certain group of children.

In order to reach children and visitors, we are going to explore the digital option. Obviously, most of the children are on social media networks now. Therefore, if we want to reach them better, we have to adapt to their mode of communication. Currently, we are engaging with the department of tourism and events and their social spaces. We also run and track our campaigns to be sure of the effectiveness. We want people to know where to come to when they need help (Interviewee F).

Both Interviewee F and Interviewee G hinted on education being a crucial factor in giving children a voice and audience in this new age. Interviewee G suggested that Tokyo 2020 could have given children a voice and audience by devising other means, such as social media, to reach out to their target children. Interviewee F believed children who do not know their rights would not have much to say even if they were given a chance to suggest how they would like to be represented in the Olympic Games. Thus, they suggested that subsequent Olympic Games need to invest in education about child rights, using different platforms. This is important because “Children being able to say when something is not right and having procedures just in place to change this in the Olympics Games is crucial (Interviewee D). In Interviewee D’s words:

Children need to have education about their rights about these events. When children are clueless about their rights, their voice is suppressed. Most times, the child athletes only know that they are in the Olympics, they do not know who organises it, and they do not know that there are bodies in charge of the Games – bodies like the IOC and JOC that they can speak to when they have issues about the Olympic Games (Interviewee D).

Corroborating this, Interviewee E also noted that, “most children do not even know that there are NGOs they can go to for help; they know more about their coaches than they know about the organising bodies. In Interviewee E’s words:

Many times, people talk about child participation and inclusion in mega sporting events. Who talks about the IOC, the children’s knowledge about the events and what they are entitled to? Most of the time, they do not even know who the IOC is. These children need to be educated about the Olympics, participating in the Olympics, what their rights are, and what the IOC’s responsibilities to them are. Education gives the child a voice (Interviewee E).

According to Lundy (2007) inclusion does not guarantee audience. Hence, the challenge is to find ways to give children a voice and audience, after which their suggestions are taken on board and embedded in policies guiding.

7.6. Influence by representation in policies

The previous section presented interview findings about the lack of voice and audience in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games planning, and interviewee's recommendations for having representatives speak out on behalf of the child, since the culture in Japan does not support children speaking out themselves. However, as Lundy (2007) argues, one of the most common and cogent criticisms levelled at Article 12 is that it is easy for adults to comply with the various outward signs of consultation and ultimately ignore children's views. Further to this, Lundy (2007) noted that the challenge is to find ways to ensure that adults not only listen to children but that they take children's views seriously. While this cannot be universally guaranteed, Interviewee B argued that the first step to ensuring child influence is policy representation. According to Interviewee B, "policies can be monitored". This corroborates Lundy's (2007) argument about the ability to monitor the implementation of Article 12. According to her, while the implementation of Article 12 cannot be guaranteed, it can be monitored. It is possible to implement procedural safeguards which make the process more open and transparent, and which create the conditions in which it makes it uncomfortable for adults to solicit children and young people's opinions and ignore them. The findings of this study, however, suggest that, until now the act of policy representation has been lacking in Japan, making a coherent approach to child rights problematic. Interviewee C, while corroborating that policy representation was missing in the Tokyo 2020 Games, also recognized that it was too late to embed child rights commitments in Games-related policies. They, however, argued that this would have been the best approach to making provisions for child rights protection because, "these policies are the ones that bind the host cities. In addition, the Olympic Games policies are the ones that guide the Olympic movement" (Interviewee B). Commenting on the Japanese government's affiliation with child/human rights organizations, an independent human rights representative suggested that while it is great that Japan has a great relationship with

advocacy groups, “this commitment does not make up for the lack of child rights measures in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies” (Interviewee D). There were no child rights specifics in the Tokyo 2020 bid documents. Interviewee B acknowledged that embedding specific child rights protection considerations in policies would be a move in the right direction.

The *Children’s Rights in Sports Principle* suggested that protection measures go beyond paper and policies representation, as representation in policies do not necessarily equate to action. According to an independent human rights organisation, “child rights provisions when represented in policies do not automatically become a certainty” (Interviewee E). Speaking about Tokyo 2020, Interviewee A mentioned that even if specific child rights provisions were embedded in the Tokyo 2020 policies, there was no guarantee that the provisions would be strictly adhered to. According to Interviewee A, there is still the need for stakeholders to ensure that those child rights protection measures come to fruition. As interviewee A further noted, “there is a need for someone to be behind the policies pulling weights to ensure that the provisions in the policies are carried out”. In the documentary analysis, child rights were generalised under the umbrella of human rights, suggesting that there has not been adequate representation of children in policies guiding the Tokyo 2020 Games. When commenting on this, Interviewee B noted that more needs to be done, arguing that children are most often the recipients of the consequences of leaving child rights protection measures out of policies. For example, having and dealing with child rights issues could have been avoided if the Beijing Olympic Games organizers had provided adequate representation and provision in policies, backed up by the proactive actions of stakeholders. Citing the Beijing Olympics, further, they mentioned that most of the information they worked with did not come from stakeholders, even though the host community had policies, which they claimed had enough information to influence their protection measures (Interviewee B):

I have realised that most of these policies do not have anything regarding what's happening with children in mega sporting events, in terms of violations. What we have is a lot of evidence coming out from closed regions. So, how do we come up with good protective strategies if we do not have a solid evidence base? Especially when we do need to get to the evidence base before we completely develop our strategies and decide what interventions would be most strategic and would have the greatest impact? (Interviewee B).

Ideally, representatives felt that the *Children in Sport Principles* developed by UNICEF Japan in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games should have been officially adopted for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. However, in the case of Japan, Interviewee A noted that the Japanese sport community has been dominated by “victory supremacy” ideology/culture for decades, which makes it difficult for Japanese sport to follow some of the guidelines. Interviewee G, the lead Tokyo 2020 campaigner for an independent child rights organisation in Japan, corroborated this, saying that they had a model for influencing Olympic host communities and sites, however, the fact that Japan did not have child rights policies in place has made it difficult for them to progress smoothly with some of their initiatives.

The *Children in Sports Principles* echo the disregarding of child rights in sport communities from the children's perspective (Interviewee A). While the *Children in Sports Principles* may have benefitted the very selected few elite athletes, the ideology/culture of Japan has disregarded the best interests of most children (Interviewee A). Despite Interviewee G and Interviewee A's suggestion that Japan has not done enough to represent children in the policies guiding the Tokyo 2020 Games because of a childfree culture in the country, a member of the JOC advanced a different view. They stated that they were aware of criticism about the culture and ideology of Japan, especially since winning the bid to host the Olympic Games, however, “regardless of the culture and ideology, the Japanese government still try to advance the cause of child rights in Japan” (Interviewee A). OCM also mentioned that Japan introduced the “Sport Act”. This act

“claims” that everyone, regardless of his or her gender, age or other characteristic has the right to sport. They also stated that even though Japan does not have specific child rights policies for the Tokyo 2020 Games, the Japanese government has been encouraging NGOs who have come forward with child rights protection suggestions:

I think the Japanese government is intentional about child rights provision, which is why the government and the sports community embraced the *Principle* when we introduced it in 2018. In addition, the Japanese Government has embraced NGOs who have come forward with their suggestions as regards the Tokyo 2020/21 Games (Interviewee A)

This claim made by the Interviewee A supports the commitments made in the *Japanese Pledge and Commitment* document, where the Japanese government documented the various child rights NGOs that the government supports. In concluding this section, there was disagreement as to how committed the government and Games organizers have been. Critics have called for greater host city intentionality in its approach to child rights provision, protection and representation in the Olympic Games. Specifically, Lundy (2007) explained that the reality is that Article 12 must be interpreted in conjunction with Article 5 of the UNCRC (which states that adults’ right to provide appropriate direction and guidance in the exercise by the child of the rights in the Convention must be carried out in a manner consistent with the evolving capacities of the child). It has been established that adults (representatives) have a role to play in ensuring that the right provision is made for the child in conjunction with the UNCRC. However, based on the findings of this study, there were advocacy organizations which actively tried to influence child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games, however, there is no evidence suggesting that the views of these organizations were adequately represented in the policies of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

7.7. Inclusiveness of Tokyo 2020 governance structure

The inclusiveness of governance structure in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games was discussed in chapter 6, in the context of child rights policies and principles in place before and after bidding.

While the section established that there were indeed structures in place, it was not established if the structures put in place were ultimately effective at minimizing child right infringements. In their conceptual model for rights-based mega sporting event governance, McGillivray et. al (2019) highlighted that “actions speaks louder than words” (pg. 183), hence the need to assess and analyze the roles that stakeholders (mainly the organising committee) played in ensuring that child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games were respected and protected. Alongside the government, they are also responsible for developing the policies and principles that guide the Olympic Games. Commenting on the role of the IOC, most of the respondents mentioned that it could have done more to advance the cause of child rights in advance of the Games. Making reference to FIFA, Interviewee A stated that the IOC has not been intentional enough about leveraging the Olympic Games to promote child rights. As stated earlier in this chapter, in response to the 2020 Human Rights Watch report, the JOC liaised with the Japanese Government to propose a safe space institution for children. This provides some evidence of progress on the JOC’s part. The IOC, on the other hand, has given little indication to suggest that it is committed to the protection and promotion of child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games. Interviewee A, a member of the organising committee, mentioned that they expected more from the IOC. Candidly, they stated that, “child rights in Tokyo 2020/2021 would have had more specificities, if the IOC had been intentional in their approach towards the child rights movement” (OCM, interview), commenting further that:

The IOC, as we know, is one of the examples of the stakeholder who have been leveraging the local communities to raise the standard or upscale the people on the ground, in terms of safeguarding the children. For example, the definition of sexual harassment is intentionally blurred in the Olympic Games, more so the Tokyo 2020/2021 Games. Which is not the case in FIFA. FIFA has spelt it out (Interviewee A).

Corroborating this, Interviewee D agreed that the IOC needed to be clearer on what they expected in the Tokyo 2020 Olympics Games, especially in the case of child rights. While commending the

fact that the IOC made general human rights commitments, Interviewee D went ahead to comment that, “it is not enough to generalize human rights, and child rights specificities need to be outlined as well”. Interviewee C also stated that, “the IOC needs to make sure that the government of host cities respect the rules of the IOC” (Interviewee C), and “If the government does not have rules that are up to the standard of human right treaties, then the IOC should make the government of the host city live up to it (Interviewee C).

Section 7.4 highlighted the provisions made by the TOCOG, in conjunction with the Japanese Government by means of reporting mechanisms(hotlines) and the proposed Safe Sport Centre. Interviewee A, referring to this hinted that the relationship between the IOC and the JOC was not strong enough. Hence, there was not much to say about what other child rights measures could have been put in place before the 2020 Games. This, Interviewee A attributed to the lack of leadership by the IOC. Interviewee A suggested that the IOC has not taken the leadership in the IOC and JOC relationship, and as a result of this, there are lapses in how things should have been done in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Quoting Interviewee A:

I know that your interest is in what has been done, and what will be done in the context of 2021. This is really tricky. I think you have to understand the structure between the IOC and 2020 local organising committee [...] the mentality of the people in the Tokyo 2020 organising committee, they are basically really conservative. They are not proactive in making new policies, so if IOC said to the Tokyo 2020 Organising committee to do some things, they will respond. That’s the mentality. They need to be told. But the IOC, on the other hand, in my opinion tend to think that they do not take the leadership, and the organising committee should take the leadership. The relationship between the IOC and the LOC is like that. That makes the problem complicated. The problem now is about who takes the leadership? Who fills the gap of the child rights problems projected at the Olympic Games Games? (Interviewee A)

Corroborating the expected leadership proactivity on the IOC’s part, Interviewee C stated that “the role of leadership in the Olympic Games should be held by the IOC (Interviewee C). This has also been mentioned by international advocacy organizations such as World Player, Centre for Sports

and Human Rights, Human Rights Watch. Human Rights Watch addressed the child rights problems projected at the Olympic Games, as discussed in the early section of this chapter, and called on the IOC to be more intentional about child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. While this call prompted the JOC to make moves as regards child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, Interviewee D noted that before the Human Rights Watch publication, the JOC did not take the issue of child rights seriously, despite the obvious recurring child rights situation in Japan. Similarly, as mentioned by Interviewee A, the JOC has done some work in the past 17 years. This was before the Tokyo 2020 Games was awarded. In Interviewee A's words:

I must tell you, IOC really didn't take the issue of child rights serious in the past. They did some project over the past 17 years. With all respect, they are doing what they can do, but what they have been doing is not really effective (Interviewee A)

They also mentioned that, in their opinion, the HRW's publication should have prompted the IOC to put some pressure on the JOC to make more child rights provision in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games, However, the barest minimum was done:

HRW has put some pressure on the IOC telling them to have a talk with the JOC to build up a really effective system. The IOC and JOC eventually had a conference to talk about the issue. However, we haven't come to a conclusion yet. I really think that the IOC intervention and leadership is necessary, and if we want to do something in the context of the Olympics, what the organising committee can do is limited. That is why IOC leadership is really important (Interviewee A).

This corroborates Donnelly's (2008) argument about who exactly should be involved in regulating child abuse in sporting events. The regulation of child abuse in sport is the responsibility of both governments and supranational organizations like the IOC (Donnelly, 2008) and the JOC. Sometimes, child abuse happens when mega sporting events are being organised; hence, children need to be prioritised (Donnelly, 2008). According to Aina et al (2021),

Because Tokyo 2020 was awarded to Japan before the IOC introduced its human rights policy (in 2017) and strengthened its protocols to respect, protect and promote human rights as part of the bid and delivery process, these Games appear to have paid lip service

to the issue of child rights. Analysis of formal policies and interview findings demonstrates a misalignment between generalized commitments to human rights and child rights conventions and (a lack of) specific plans in place to govern the 2020 Tokyo Olympic Games.

Furthermore, even though the IOC tried, however, because there were no legally binding human rights procedures in the Tokyo 2020 contracts, the IOC was unable to make the Japanese government make certain human rights commitments, in the lead up to the Tokyo 2020 Games (Aina, et. al 2021).

7.8. CONCLUSION

Chapter seven has provided a distinct perspective on the child rights situation in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, drawing on interviews with influential stakeholders in the human rights space. Several key themes emerged, though these were understood in diverse ways by the respondents, because of their affiliations and level of involvement in planning for the Tokyo 2020 Games. In the interview conducted, it was unanimously agreed by the respondents that mega sporting events also have negative impacts on children. Speaking on the negative impacts on children, especially elite child athletes and volunteers, the interviews also agreed that there were inadequate provision for protection in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies. This meant that children and their rights were susceptible to abuse in the Tokyo 2020 Games. This also meant that children could have been abused in the Tokyo 2020 Games without any repercussion to the abuser.

Using Lundy's (2007) model of participation, in this chapter I have established that participation and protection are interrelated. Like in chapter 5, I have provided evidence that child rights have not been given the attention they deserve in Tokyo 2020, especially in the context of Lundy's proposed model. While the documentary analysis signified that there were few provisions made generally under the human rights umbrella by the host city, interviews pointed out that some of the provisions were not in full effect, which meant that advocacy organizations had to step in to

provide some solutions. This is problematic because responsibility for child rights protection and promotion should lie with the Japanese government and the local organising committee, the TOCOG.

For the Tokyo 2020 Games, there appeared to be a clear unintentionality about child rights found in the policy sphere and this was reinforced in interviews. Human rights bodies and child rights organizations were critical of the IOC for not promoting a child rights focus by embedding child rights provisions in the policies guiding the Games. The interviewees noted that policies are important if child rights in sporting events are to be protected, as these policies are the documents that do not only guide how the host city plans the Olympic Games, but also binds the host cities, just as financial guarantees do. A positive child rights outcome starts with adequate representation in policies.

Finally, I have drawn attention to the lapses of the IOC in ensuring that host cities apply child rights measures. While the respondents made note of the lack of leadership of the IOC in ensuring that child rights are adhered to by host cities, there are pointers towards the fact that the IOC is being intentional about introducing human rights measures in future Olympic Games including Paris 2024. However, based on the focus of this study, it is evident that child rights being categorized under the general umbrella of human rights is not beneficial towards children, as children tend to be overlooked. There is a need to separate child rights from human rights, if there will be changes to child rights in the Olympic Games. The same way there are specific requirements for human rights, women's rights, commercial rights, media rights protection in the policies of the Olympic Games, particularly the Olympic Charter, there also need for specific requirements for child rights protection measures in the Olympic Games guiding principles. All these and more will be analyzed in the next section, after which this study proposes a framework

to leveraging child rights in the Olympic Games which focusses on recognizing children as right bearers, including children in the decision making processes, embedding specific child rights specifics in the Olympic Games policies, monitoring the process of putting the policies to practice, and delivering every child rights protection promises.

CHAPTER 8: CHANGING THE NARRATIVE OF CHILD RIGHTS IN THE OLYMPIC GAMES

8.1. Introduction

This study has investigated child rights in mega sporting events, using Tokyo 2020 as a case study.

In the findings chapters, I have addressed the study's research questions which were: (a) to examine the dimensions of child rights infringements in the Olympic Games, (b) to explore what measures have been put in place to mitigate child rights abuse in the Tokyo 2020 Games., and (c) to examine the roles of stakeholders, event organizers, advocacy organizations and event owners in complying with the UNCRC in ensuring that child rights are well represented and adhered to, both in paper and actions. Using both McGillivray et.al's (2019) concept of delivering a mega sporting event that leverages human rights, and Lundy's (2007) model of participation, the findings were structured to fit the conceptual dimensions of the study. In this chapter, I analyze these findings, drawing on three prevalent themes that emerged from the study: 1) the absence of child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games bid documents and policies, 2) the role of advocacy organizations as change agents, and 3) the need for leadership for child rights in the Olympic Games.

This analysis chapter starts with a discussion of how greater recognition of child rights can be fostered in the Olympic Games. This is then followed by a discussion about the role of advocacy organizations as change agents for child rights in mega sporting events. Finally, I discuss the need for leadership for child rights protection and provision in the Olympic Games, after which I outline a holistic framework for delivering the Olympic Games from a child rights perspective.

8.2. Fostering the recognition of child rights in the Olympic Games

Throughout this study, I have highlighted the non-intentionality about child rights in the Olympic Games. Other scholars have also documented the non-existence of child rights in sport, especially in mega sporting events (see Hong 2004; Donnelly 2008; Hess and Bishara, 2019). This study's

findings corroborate a continuing lack of recognition of child rights, tracing it to the absence of child right-specific policies and principles guiding the bidding, planning and delivery of the Olympic Games. In this study I have argued further that the basis of this unintentionality lies in children not being considered as right bearers due to certain factors. While the UNCRC places great importance on child rights being prioritized, Donnelly (2008) argues that mega sporting events still tend to overlook children. Recent scholars (see Aina et al. 2021; Aine, Muhonen and Toivonen, 2022) have also argued that there continues to be violence towards children in mega sporting events, which suggests that child rights are still deprioritized at the planning stage. The fact that child rights are deprioritized was clearly portrayed in the planning for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, as there is little evidence to suggest that children and their rights were foregrounded. This can be seen not only in the policies guiding the Games, but also in the way child rights were represented by the IOC, JOC, TOGOC, and the wider Japanese state – both local and national. According to Canosa and Graham (2022) and Lang (2022), this lack of intentionality towards child rights reflects children’s historical marginalization which is founded on a well established theory of children of a particular ages’ citizenship status. From this perspective, children being recognized as citizens is a mechanism for child rights intentionality. In the context of mega sporting events, children being recognized as citizens by the organizers is an important prerequisite for child rights protection. “Recognition”, in this context, is a key factor. As Martin and Wood (2022) argue, procedure and recognition are key foundations of legitimate forms of governance. According to HRW (2019), there were confirmed violations of child rights in Tokyo during the period when the Olympic Games were being planned. This was attributed to negligence in terms of lack of governance structures for child rights provision and protection, thereby corroborating Lee-Ludvigsen, Rookwood and Parnell’s (2022) argument that the contemporary controversies of mega sporting events are often tightly linked to their governance and governance

structure. Similarly, drawing on McGillivray et al (2019), progressive human rights outcomes begin with the quality of governance arrangements put in place for mega sporting events at the planning stage. For progressive child rights outcomes to be achievable, recognition of children and their rights, in addition to quality governance arrangements for child rights protection need to be part of Olympic Games planning. Ideally, this would also mean that before the bidding stage of the Tokyo 2020 Games, specific child rights protection measures would have been included in the Olympic Charter, while also making it a prerequisite for prospective host cities to draw a child rights protection plan in their bidding documents and policies (Chappelet, 2016). Second, at the bidding stage, the National Olympic Committees (NOC), and state actors such as government of host cities (Tokyo) and sponsors of the Olympic Games would have worked together to put in place robust child rights protection measures, with the intent to further implement them. Indeed, as Muller (2015) claims, the bidding stage is the best time to change the parameters that were excluded in the planning stage.

Fostering recognition of child rights in the Olympic Games is a collective piece of work which must involve the many stakeholders, starting from the Olympic Games leadership. As outlined previously, attention to governance for children was not a substantive part of the planning stage of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, as the IOC did not employ modes of policy governance mechanisms to encourage the inclusion of child rights into the management of the Games (Ross, Leopkey and Mercado, 2019). This is not unexpected, as according to Hanson (2012) the extent, priorities or even precise content of children's rights in a variety of sectors is not readily available. Hanson (2012) attributes this to the sensitivity surrounding the concept of children and their rights. As he argues, children's rights are a morally sensitive domain having to deal with strong, and often competing, normative and ideological perspectives (Hanson, 2012). Based on this argument, there is a clear tension in the way child rights are perceived, and organizations and event agencies tend

to be reluctant to delve into the child rights terrain because of its sensitivity. However, this tension is clearly unfounded as there exists a standard principle for dealing with the sensitivities surrounding child rights and interests across the three P's - Provision, Protection and Participation (Jerome and Starkey, 2022). Moreover, the UNCRC is a clearly defined guideline which event organizers and private organizations can follow should they want to be intentional about child rights, regardless of the competing, normative and ideological perspectives attached to child rights. The UNCRC, published in 1989, represents a standard bearer, which could be more effectively used by awarding bodies and organising committees to inform policies and provisions for child rights. As Nunn (2013) states, there is no need to be sensitive to children's right to freedom, right to provision or any other rights. On the contrary, child rights sensitivity and children's vulnerability should be a propelling factor for a sustainable child rights protection strategy. This was not the case in the planning for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, seeing as the seeming sensitivity towards child rights propelled the Olympic Games governance body to stay away from enforcing child rights protection measures in their Tokyo 2020 policies.

Revealing evidence of non-commitment to child rights (provision for protection) in the Tokyo 2020 Games was straightforward. Starting from the documentary analysis of the Tokyo bidding documents, there was little or no evidence of commitment to child rights protection in the Tokyo 2020 Games. As suggested by interviewees, this was primarily because children are not recognized as rights-bearing persons in Japan. Several interviewees also mentioned that children do not have the autonomy to speak up, even when they are abused because of the hierarchical nature of the Japanese culture. This conflicts with the provisions included in the UNCRC which give the child a right to speak up. I argued earlier that, sometimes, culture and human rights are conflicting, however, cities find a way to make both concepts work together. This was not the case for Tokyo, in the context of child rights, as the interviewees had to improvise and devise other means to

approach Japanese children. A frequently mentioned word in the interviews conducted for this study was “hierarchy”, indirectly suggesting that children under the age of 18 cannot speak up in Japan, especially if they are still under the authority of their parents or coaches. This helps explain why there was little evidence of children being given a voice in the Tokyo 2020 Games both in policies and delivery. Linking this with children being recognized as right bearers, it can be argued that in a society where children are recognized as right bearers, children may not be subjects of hierarchical expectations, and they are better protected from abuse (Hanson and Peleg, 2020).

The Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games did encourage some child participation, including making tickets cheaper for children. However, for Lundy (2007), if important aspects such as giving every child (see Ng, Bloom, Corcoran, Fletcher and Sibley, 2022) a voice, audience, space and influence are neglected, then the concept of participation is not holistic. While the participation initiatives for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games are commendable, as highlighted by UNCRC (2009), exposing children to risk of harm through participation without providing adequate protection measures, represents unethical practice and cannot be understood as implementing participation in line with the principles of the UNCRC. Moreover, as stipulated by the interest theory of rights, the primary function of rights is the protection of fundamental interests. Therefore, since children undeniably have fundamental interests that merit protection, it is perfectly sensible to attribute rights, especially welfare rights to them (Brighouse, 2002).

One way to show respect for children and their views is by embedding child rights protection strategies in policies (Aina et al. 2021). Even though the Tokyo 2020 Host City Contract and the Olympic Charter made provisions for other forms of rights, ranging from commercial rights to media rights, child rights were neglected. The *Japan Human Rights Commitment and Pledges* document did highlight that the Japanese Government had child rights affiliations with some

NGOs such as UNICEF prior to hosting the Games. However, again, this might be a case of agenda setting to improve public opinion (Liu and Yuan, 2012), considering the publicity that child rights were getting around the period (2019) that the JHRCP was published. In addition to this, the affiliations and commitments mentioned in JHRCP neither influenced, nor were reflected in the bid documents. Thus, it appears that the JHRCH was published in response to questions about Tokyo 2020 and child rights. As regards organizational initiatives to protect child rights, interviews suggested that the plan to provide a “safe space” for child athletes only came to be, after HRW published the article “I was hit so many times I can’t count”. Beyond the inability of Tokyo 2020 to deliver safe spaces, there is an indication that the initiative was reactive. To this, I argue that there would not be a need for reactive unsustainable provisions if child rights had been recognized and incorporated at the planning stage.

In sum, returning to Canosa and Graham (2022), it is clear that child marginalization exists in sport, and this theory of child marginalization in sport played out in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games when child rights were excluded from the initial principles and policies guiding the games. Exclusion of child rights from the initial bid documents suggests that first, the Olympic Games event owners and host city bid committees might not believe that child rights can be violated through sport. Second, the Olympic Games event owners, the IOC, JOC and TOCOG probably do not understand the importance of child rights protection in the Olympic Games, and finally, the Olympic Games governance (IOC, JOC, host city government) do not recognize children as right bearers. It is worth noting, however, that respondents accepted that children suffer violations in sporting events and recommended that adequate protection be provided for child rights. More specifically, respondents agreed that violations to child rights seem to be on the rise, and the best way to address violations from the grassroots is through the IOC, JOC and host government. This is unsurprising, as Lang (2022), and Aina et al (2021) document the rising trend of child rights

violations, spanning across different Olympic Games, while Talbot (2022) argues that the IOC and the host government remain the only agents able to see legal remedy for violation of rights in the Olympic Games. Beyond the awareness of the continuous trend of child rights violations, there was also an agreement that the main reason for child rights neglect is linked to event owners not recognizing child rights protection as integral to a successful Olympic Games delivery. This reflects broader discussions on the inability of sporting events leadership and governance to recognize that children are right bearers (see Canosa and Graham, 2022; Lundy 2007). I argue that there needs to be greater awareness about children being legitimate right holders. I also argue that for this awareness to have maximum impact, in addition to the leadership of the Olympic Games accepting that the Olympic Games violate child rights in different dimensions, they also need to be at the forefront of fostering the recognition of child rights in the Olympic Games.

8.3. Advocacy organizations as ‘change agents’ for child rights

According to Mohanty (2004), NGOs are instrumental in bringing large-scale sustainability changes to various levels of society. The emergence, development and importance of these organizations constitutes a significant and integral aspect of social transformation (Mohanty, 2004). Much has been said about advocacy organizations being instrumental to changing the narratives of human rights and child rights in mega sporting events (see Caudwell and McGee, 2018; McGillivray et al, 2019; Heerd and Rock, 2022). As we have seen in the case of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, advocacy organizations have brought about a much-needed awareness to the issue of human rights through different dialogues and strategies. This section partly answers research question three, which seeks to analyze the roles of stakeholders (inclusive of advocacy organizations) in ensuring that the UNCRC is adhered to in the planning of the Olympic Games.

Den Hond and Bakker (2007) suggest that ideological differences among activist groups motivate them to choose different tactics in motivating change. Explaining this further, they argue that the

tactics that activist groups use range from petitions and lobbying to confrontations and sabotage. As discussed in the findings, some of these tactics were utilized by advocacy organizations who had a stake in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. First, the use of dialogue was adopted by NGOs who were interviewed for this study. This, according to De Athayde and Ikeda (2009), suggests an attempt to encourage human rights adherence from the perspective of improving policies which might lead to more positive child rights outcome (Miyake and Koarai, 2022).

In the general mega sporting event terrain, since 2008, Aina et al (2021) have argued that there has been a change in how human rights are perceived and built into governance arrangements. Similarly, McGillvray et al (2019) also argued that some progress is evident in the general human rights terrain, as a result of a heightened push from advocacy organizations to make the Olympic Games certifying authorities become accountable for whatever happens to underaged citizens, at their events. In furthering the cause of child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, human rights agencies enacted different strategies to attract the attention of the Japanese government and the IOC to the state of child rights in Japan. This is also applicable in the general mega sporting events, as NGOs continue to enact different strategies in strengthening the relationship between mega sporting events and human rights protection. Riegel and Mumford (2022) have suggested that advocacy organizations can be divided into two main types: old and new advocacy organizations. Some of the advocacy organizations interviewed for this study fall under the category of the newly established advocacy organizations. There were differences in the approach taken towards influencing child rights changes in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, compared to some of the approaches adopted by old advocacy organizations such as HRW and UNICEF. While the newly established advocacy organizations influenced changes, more from the aspect of providing mechanisms for protection, the old activists previously mentioned utilized a more daring approach. This is in line with Riegel and Mumford's (2022) argument about the disparities of

approach between new and old advocacy organizations. According to them, organizations such as HRW usually address issues through confrontations and lobbying, and this is because these organizations have the ability to influence policies directly because of their access to policy makers (Riegel and Mumford, 2022). While lobbying has been acclaimed to be one of the key strategies of old advocates to secure access to policy makers, this was not evident in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Even though old organizations including HRW and UNICEF had greater flexibility to lobby policy makers directly, these organizations changed their approach, because dealing directly with the IOC yielded no outcome. As one of the respondents stated, “The idea to change approaches came after we learned that our child rights views and concerns would not be addressed by the Tokyo 2020 Sourcing code”. This was after they had presented their concerns and views directly to the IOC. While HRW took a public approach of blaming and shaming the IOC and Japanese sport organizations through publications and the use of media, UNICEF and CSPHR adopted a different approach of influencing through workshops and publications of proposed change-inducing documents. Again, this was because going directly to the IOC and JOC had failed to yield any results. However, Talbot (2022) suggests that regardless of the disparities between advocacy organizations, it is crucial that human rights advocacy groups continue to find ways to accurately and meaningfully communicate their claims to avoid the IOC continuing to avoid their responsibilities to host cities.

Talbot (2022) gives credence to advocacy organizations who are responsible for playing a key role in influencing change in child rights, even though they continue to be caught in the middle of the wide gap between the IOC and grassroots advocacy organizations. Even though there were no grassroots advocacy organizations captured in this study because of the limitations of interviews, in the context of this research, the new advocacy organizations can be described to be currently caught between the IOC and the old advocacy organizations. In order not to be caught in the middle

of the strategies of old advocacy organizations such as HRW, UNICEF it is perhaps understandable why some of these new advocacy organizations take a non-confrontational approach in dealing with the child rights situation in Japan in advance of the Olympic Games. This approach fits the description of ‘advocacy innovation projects’ as described by Lee and Cunningham (2019, p.249). By providing measures for child protection in Tokyo, in advance of the Olympic Games, these new advocacy organizations also provided solutions (Bloodgood, 2011) to identified child rights problems in advance of the Games and utilized sport-based initiatives to help address broader development goals (Svensson and Hambrick, 2019). Advocacy organizations might not be able to compete with States in terms of coercive capability or money, but they can provide solutions to some issues that the government cannot immediately provide solutions for (Bloodgood, 2011). Although, in the case of Tokyo, the JOC provided some reporting mechanisms (hotlines), these were discounted based on non-functionality. While the reporting mechanisms provided by NGOs served child athletes in Japan, “it was also created to serve children in general”, thereby corroborating submissions that the role of NGOs in ensuring human rights in sporting events is “for the better good” (Svensson and Hambrick, 2019). “For the better good” in this context refers to serving the means of something bigger outside the specific context of sporting events. This reflects McGoldrick’s (1996) argument of sustainability being an important factor in the conception of change. From this perspective, it can be inferred that NGOs have played a major role in effecting change by making certain provisions (providing a child reporting mechanism) for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. There, however, remains a question of how sustainable these provisions are, and for how long the provisions will serve children in Tokyo, especially since most of the provisions were designed specifically for the Olympic Games.

In the document developed by the Centre for Sports and Human Rights for the Tokyo 2020 Games, titled “*Sustainable Sourcing, Grievance Mechanisms, and Human Rights at Mega Sporting*

Events”, the Executive Director of Games Operations, TOCOG, touched on Tokyo 2020 aiming for sustainability and legacies of inclusion and human rights. While this was not aimed specifically at children and their rights, it represents a pointer towards the fact that the host communities, event owners, and organising committees are starting to consider human rights as a “must have” in the Olympic Games. By engaging with key stakeholders and holding an advocacy event about sustainability and human rights, CSHR was able to get the TOCOG to think about human rights and sustainability of rights protection principles during and after the Olympic Games. This is a welcome development, but there is still a need for advocacy organizations to push for specific child rights protection guidelines if greater child rights protection during and after the Olympic Games is going to be achieved. Alternatively, advocacy organizations can also hold governments accountable to some standards (Clark, 1995). This is evident in the approach adopted (shaming) by old NGOs in the context of Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

McGillivray et al (2021) have argued that some advocacy organizations have moved away from shaming to a more collaborative approach with awarding bodies. However, findings from this study suggested otherwise, in some instances. For example, HRW did not only adopt a naming and shaming strategy, but it was also the only strategy they utilized in their bid to influence change to child rights in the context of Tokyo. For Pacheco-Vega and Murdie (2021), this is a strategic action aimed at specific actors. In this context, this was a strategic action aimed at the IOC, JOC, child athlete coaches and the Japanese government. Philip (2021) has argued that naming and shaming is not enough to change the behavioural norms of the host countries, however, it can be an effective way to facilitate interactions between the domestic (within host country), and international human rights advocates. ‘Facilitation’ in this regard is the exact thing that makes the difference needed (Philip, 2021). While naming and shaming might facilitate interaction, there is the question of how this facilitation might produce change. For Tokyo, naming and shaming

facilitated discussions round about establishing a safe sports Centre, but it was not enough to ensure the establishment of that facility. To this end, it can be argued that shaming and naming produced minimal change to child rights beyond the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games.

While shaming was found to produce minimal change in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the instances of collaborations by new advocacy organizations influenced more change. This is not surprising, as this approach has been recorded to be an essential and successful approach when it comes to child rights (Rosenberg, Hartwig and Merson, 2008). Luna (2001) noted that in several cases, NGOs take the route of confrontation when they see that certain stakeholders have posed a risk to their communities or entities because of their activities. The report published by HRW titled “*I was hit so many times I can’t count*” documented that there were entities in Japan (coaches, parents and some players) who were engaged in activities such as physical violence, coaching techniques, that increased risk to child athletes in Japan. By publishing this article and stating that clear and comprehensive reform is needed to eliminate these practices and protect children, HRW succeeded in identifying and highlighting corporal punishment in Japan and used the media to confront the IOC. This strategy had also been adopted by HRW in past Olympic Games. For instance, HRW submitted a proposal to the IOC’s Copenhagen Congress in 2009, proposing that a permanent mechanism be put in place to monitor human rights in host countries before, during and after the Olympic Games:

To avoid Olympics-related human rights violations in all future host countries, Human Rights Watch has proposed creating an IOC standing committee to monitor human rights in host countries. This committee would help set and apply human rights benchmarks for potential Olympic hosts regarding media freedom, labour rights, freedom of expression

and civil liberties. Most important it would be staffed with experts and tasked monitoring abuses before, during and after an Olympics (Human Rights Watch, 2020).

Joachim (2003) has argued that even though NGOs can be influential in creating new child rights interest at the Olympic Games planning stage, some host organising committees may be reluctant to allow NGOs to influence changes to their pre-planned policies. Similarly, Holzscheiter (2016) also argued that advocacy organizations' representational power is more easily assumed and possibly exploited where resistance and opposition is minimal. Resistance and opposition possibly explain why the centre for safe sport was not instituted in the context of Tokyo 2020. Interviewees noted that there was opposition to some of the advocacy approaches to influence change in the Tokyo 2020 Games as regards child rights. This is on par with previous Olympic Games such as Beijing 2008 when some Chinese Olympic officials and IOC officials sought to defuse controversy by arguing that advocacy organizations should not exploit the Games to further their own agenda (Price and Dayan, 2009). When resistance like this happens, especially when it comes to working for children, according to Holzscheiter (2016), renegotiation happens. This explains the recurring situation, where specific child rights organizations had to meet up with the Japanese government, at least twice, prior to the Tokyo 2020 Games to discuss the issues of child rights, specifically, child labour, trafficking and abuse towards child athletes. As was seen in the *Sustainable Plans (Tokyo 2020 Source code, edition 3)* document of the Tokyo 2021 Games, which was published in 2019, some of these measures were included. Even though these measures were added as an afterthought, based on recommendations, this is evidence of advocacy organizations initiating or accelerating change, as argued by Schulenkorf and Edwards (2012).

If advocacy organizations had not intervened in the Tokyo 2020 Games, there would have been no child rights represented in any of the bid documents and policies as there were no child rights

measures in the documents originally submitted by the Tokyo 2020 Bid Committee to the IOC. The ability of NGOs to influence change to the Tokyo 2020 policies is commendable. However, according to Furrer (2002), the inclusion of sustainable policies within the Games organizational concept must be as a result of voluntary initiatives on the part of the organizers and responsible authorities. This means that child rights must not be an afterthought or a greenwash PR-type strategy, but a genuine effort to maintain or even improve the quality of life for both child participants and children who might be affected as a result of hosting the Olympic Games (Furrer, 2002).

In conclusion, in the context of Tokyo, both old and new advocacy organizations played roles in ensuring that the Tokyo 2020 Games were delivered in compliance with the UNCRC. However, we can see that the roles played by these organizations were mostly unsuccessful, as they failed to influence the IOC and JOC to implement significant child rights protection measures in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Although it can be argued that even though some of these advocacy organizations recorded success in the area of provision for protection, more success would have been recorded if the IOC and JOC had also implemented functional protection measures. This tells us that, while child rights can be addressed through advocacy, transparency, responsiveness and accountability (McGillivray et al, 2019) on the part of the Olympic leadership are also important factors in successful child rights protection implementation. Advocacy organizations in Tokyo played their role in suggesting changes to policies, developing child rights protection strategies, blaming and shaming the IOC to elicit a form of response and change to child rights approaches in the Olympic Games policies, even creating dialogues by form of workshops and meetings with the IOC and JOC. However, despite everything done by these advocacy organizations, there was a lack of accountability and responsiveness on the part of the IOC and JOC to affect any significant changes to how child rights were addressed in the Olympic Games policies and delivery. This also

explains the dynamics of human rights, in the context of the general mega sporting event terrain. Advocacy organizations play their roles, however, only on few occasions have there been accountability and responsiveness on the part of the leadership. As mentioned earlier, protecting child rights in sport is a collective effort which requires significant effort from stakeholders, inclusive of advocacy organizations and the Olympic Games leadership. Advocacy organizations can try to influence changes to policies, however, if there is no commitment from the IOC or the NOC, there might not be legal remedy for violations of child rights. Therefore, more than anything, there needs to be a level of commitment from the Olympic Games leadership if the UNCRC are to be adhered to in the Olympic Games, and if child rights protection measures are to be included in the policies guiding the Olympic Games. This brings me to the topic of the importance of leadership in championing the cause of child rights protection and provision in mega sporting events.

8.4. Leadership for child rights protection and provision in the Olympic Games

Young athletes have suffered from harmful effects to their life and development as well as economic and sexual exploitation without sufficient protection by either FIFA or the IOC (Shinohara, 2020). The UNCRC is an essential instrument for respecting and protecting child rights, however as detailed by Shinohara (2020), this is yet to be actualised, and there has been debates about who should take responsible leadership (Megheirkouni, Naylor and Oshimi, 2022) of strategic issues such as human rights and child rights in sporting events. This study, from the start, has documented an inadequacy of well thought out leadership structure to spearhead child rights initiatives. More specifically, the documentary examination chapter (chapter seven) found that there were ineffective governance structures in place to cater for child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games, both in the initial bid documents and principles guiding the Games, which inadvertently affected the intentionality about child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. In

lieu of this, it can be argued that lack of child rights specific in the policies and principles guiding the Olympic Games boils down to irresponsible leadership on the part of the IOC and the JOC to provide child rights protection measures in the policies of the Olympic Games without being prodded. For example, the JOC had to be prodded by advocacy organizations before adding child rights phrases into the sustainability document. This suggests that responsible leadership is still an ethical dilemma in the Olympic Games, as argued by Rodenburg, Hayes, Foti and Pegoraro (2021). Similarly, based on Megheirkouni's (2022) argument for responsible leadership, for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, responsible leadership was needed to create a sustainable positive child rights impact beyond the event itself.

As regards questions about who should take the leadership of child rights in mega sporting events, Willett (2019) has argued that the issue of child rights protection in the Olympic Games should be championed by the host government and organising committees, with support from expert stakeholders in the field of human rights and child rights. This means that protecting child rights in the Olympic Games should be a collaborative endeavour, involving the IOC, JOC and other sport and non-sport related stakeholders. I have previously argued (see section 8.2) that even though fostering a recognition of child rights in the Olympic Games is a collective effort, this effort needs to be championed by the IOC, as their role is to supervise and make sure that the rules of the Olympic Charter and the Olympic host city contract are respected. As with other forms of mega sporting events such as FIFA and previous Olympic Games, advocacy organizations have been known to take the lead for child rights changes – this was no different in the case of Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. However, there is a limit to what advocacy organizations can achieve outside the leadership of the IOC and organising committees. While NGOs and experts on child rights influence changes as best as they can, more changes would have been achieved if the IOC had enshrined child rights as one of the prerequisites for hosting through their policies (such as the

OC) and principles. As regards how this might be realized, Heerdt (2018) proposed that mega sporting events owners can establish a shared responsibility and accountability framework for shared responsibility as a way through the complex web. This would mean that, in the context of the Olympic Games, the IOC, through the Olympic Games policy, has to account for the varying nature of actors (such as construction firms, state actors, Olympic Games sponsors, sports governing body, host country government, and organizing committees) and their contributions. As further noted by Heerdt (2018), instead of leaving it up to certain actors, establishing accountability and responsibility for mega sporting events related human rights abuses should be based on an inclusive approach that takes the contribution of all actors into account.

The IOC has taken some measures to include human rights in the policies of future Olympic Games, starting with Paris 2024, however, this also needs to be followed through in the context of child rights. As much as the IOC is doing to ensure that human rights are protected, discriminations against children should also be handled with priority. This corroborates Greff's (2018) view on the IOC taking the leadership on child rights for the Olympic Games. According to him, members of the host organising committees must not only abide by the minimum standard of human rights protection as defined in the UN Guiding Principles but should also take account of the convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women, as well as the Convention on the Rights of Child (Greff, 2018). While this would be a breakthrough, there also needs to be a leadership structure in place to ensure that the policies are adhered to. This is because being persuasive about child rights is not the same as achieving results. This is evident in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games case study, as the provisions made by the TOGOC were not functional. This suggests that ensuring that administrative arrangements in favour of child rights is a necessity, even though there are arguments that imposing human rights specifics on host communities might violate the state's sovereignty (Grell, 2018). From a positive perspective, this can be argued as the

IOC simply providing a base level of protection for the population in diverse host cities, especially groups particularly vulnerable to violations of human rights, where distinct approaches to human rights exist (Talbot, 2022). On the other hand, if one looks at how the IOC tends to force host countries to enact domestic legislation aimed at safeguarding its own commercial interest and that of its sponsors, then the argument of the IOC violating the states' sovereignty appears rather weak and hypocritical (Grell, 2018). In this study I have documented that there are different rights, ranging from commercial rights to media rights in the Olympic Charter and Host City Contract or Tokyo 2020, limited specifics for human rights, and no measures for child rights protection. Based on this alone, if commercial rights and media rights were enacted in these legally binding policies, then rights for marginalized people such as children could also have been enacted in these policies as well. Achieving compliance, however, requires both political will and a significant investment in new organizational capacity, including training of volunteer, leaders and professional staff and the socialization of all stakeholders, including athletes, coaches, parents and guardians (Kidd, 2021). This takes determined leadership and a concerted effort to achieve (Kidd, 2021).

In the findings, it was discovered that the Japanese culture is heavy on adults' approval; hence, this affected how decisions pertaining to child rights would have been made for children, especially child athletes in the Tokyo 2020 Games. In addition, there was evidence to suggest that even though the Tokyo 2020 Games encouraged child participants, both as volunteers and elite athletes, respondents agreed that participants were subject to report to their parents, guardians or coaches. However, this should not be an issue as the IOC can still legally include elements of voice, audience, influence and space participation, while the government can support the IOC. And as for the case of vulnerability, Canosa and Graham (2022) argued that even in the most complex situations, children can be supported to participate in research and influence decision-making in positive ways. This corroborates Willet's (2019) stand on the effectiveness of collaboration.

According to Bertram (2008), leadership plays a key role in collaborative efforts. By implementing a strategic plan, for example, leaders can increase the level of motivation for collaboration, even if there is no immediate need for a collaborative effort. Following the logic of this argument, if the IOC had shown leadership, the JOC and other stakeholders would have been motivated to provide more child rights protection measures. Therefore, in sum, to protect children from being violated by, and in the Olympic Games, the IOC should be the lead advocate and take a stand for child rights protection requirement, just like they have done with commercial rights, media rights, and some elements of human rights. This means that the IOC must be clear on what they expect in the Olympic Games, especially in the case of child rights. For example, the definition of sexual harassment is intentionally blurred in the Olympic Games, more so the Tokyo 2020 Games, which is not the case in FIFA. This, in essence, suggests that if the IOC specifies what they expect to see in the Olympic Games, then the host city and the local organising committee would have no choice but to act on it. It is interesting to note that the bid documents provided by the Tokyo 2020 bid committee did not have child rights specifics in them. Despite this, Tokyo still won the bid to host the Tokyo 2020 Games. This could only mean two things: (a), the IOC does not prioritize child rights, and (b), the Tokyo bid committee also did not prioritize child rights. It is difficult to deny that there are complexities about child rights leadership, especially because of the sensitivity surrounding the concept of children (Hanson, 2012). However, this is no grounds for the IOC and JOC to shy away from representing children and their rights. As noted by Liu (2017) the IOC can provide remedy to rights issues by implementing its authority under the language of the Olympic Charter to provide certain rights protection measures, and prompt compliance. Furthermore, as a non-governmental organization, the IOC can expand its jurisdictional power and use its choice of an Olympic Games host country to flex its muscle against rights violations by ensuring that host cities present child rights protection measures as part of their bid documents. Taking the leadership

of child rights in the Olympic Games, starting with the Olympic Charter, as noted by Megheirkouni et al. (2022), provides guidelines for other stakeholders, while enforcing host cities to present child rights protection measures as part of their bid documents enables the host city and organising committees to be more intentional about the child and their rights.

8.5. Proposed Child Rights Protection Framework

Based on findings from examining the Tokyo 2020 Games bid documents, interviews with stakeholders and the general themes of analysis in this chapter, it is evident that the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games had no clearly defined principles for child rights participation and provision for protection measures. I have argued that this is because there was no leadership intentionality about child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Games context. I also argue that the lack of intentionality about child rights can be attributed to the fact that children are not recognized as right bearers by the Olympic Games event owners (IOC) and other national stakeholders (JOC and the TOCOG), in the context of Tokyo 2020). Consequently, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games failed to meet the requirements of the UNCRC which offers an unprecedented opportunity for children to fully participate in events and the planning processes for events. This includes giving them a voice, providing them a safe space to space to air their views, giving them audience and influence.

Even though the UNCRC places importance on children and how their rights are being represented in various sectors, there is still a gap in how children are represented, especially in the policies and principles guiding the planning and delivery of the Olympic Games. This thesis fills the gap and proposes a framework for delivering an Olympic Game from a child rights perspective.

The proposed framework, graphically illustrated in Figure 8, is grounded in the UNCRC, findings from this research, and the existing conceptual frameworks that guided this research (Lundy 2007; McGillivray et al. 2019; UNICEF, 2018). In order to fill the gap of how child rights are being

represented in the Olympic Games, I argue that positive outcomes for child rights are most likely to occur if children and child rights are: (a) recognized as rights bearers (b) involved in decision-making processes, (c) embedded in policies guiding the Olympic Games (d) monitored before and during the Olympic Games and (e) delivered. These five steps, as portrayed in Figure 8 are progressive, and they are dependent on each other. I explain the relationship between these themes in the next section.

Figure 8: Framework for child rights protection in the Olympics developed for this study

8.5.1. Recognition of children as rights bearers

Based on evidence from this study, children were not recognized as rights bearers in the planning for the Tokyo 2020 Games and this study proposes that for child rights to be adequately represented, children must be recognized as rights bearing persons by both state and non-state actors, starting with the IOC. This is in line with the UNCRC, and the principles of Article 12, which suggests that children are right bearers and should be recognized as such. This model (represented in Figure 8) suggests that if children are not recognized as right bearers, they will

continue to be neglected in the processes governing the planning and delivery of the Olympic Games. There, however, have been debates about why children should not have rights. One such debate is centred on children's capabilities and competences to exercise their rights. However, as Cowden (2012) argues, child interest theory has successfully removed the conceptual impediments to children being right holders by determining that it is not necessary to have the capacity to enforce a claim to realize a claim. In this sense, children do not necessarily need to have the capacity to exercise a right before holding it. Furthermore, the UNCRC gives specific expression to the application of human rights to children and explicitly recognizes their entitlement to a full range of rights: civil, cultural, economic, political and social (Aina et al., 2021). This suggests that children and their rights should be fully recognized regardless of opposing views. This can be done by ensuring children's legal rights as stated in the UNCRC are fully implemented (Lang, 2022) and incorporated into the Olympic Games policies.

8.5.2 Involving children in decision-making processes for the Olympic Games

The second step to ensuring that child rights are adequately addressed in the Olympic Games is to involve children in decision-making processes. Once children are recognized as rights bearers by the necessary Olympic stakeholders, it would be relatively straightforward for these stakeholders to involve children in the decision-making processes for Olympic Games planning and delivery. Based on Lundy's (2007) model of participation, which is grounded in Article 12 of the UNCRC, there is a better chance of the Olympic Games having positive child right outcomes when children are involved in the decision-making processes. While Lundy's (2007) model of participation (audience, voice, space and influence) is useful, it is not all-encompassing. The Lundy participation model is one aspect of delivery that levers on human rights. As evident across past Olympic Games such as the London 2012 Olympic Games and the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, the bid documents for these Olympic Games were heavy on participation. Also, as evident in the

responses from the interviewees and documents examined for this study, children were encouraged to physically participate in the Olympic Games without an input from any child, nor child representatives. This conflicts with the modified UNCRC's (2009) proposal that child dialogue be considered even before child participation. Therefore, this study proposes that, according to Article 12 of the UNCRC, children that can form their own views have the right to, and should rightly, express those views. This framework does not only propose that children who can make decisions about their participation in the Olympic Games should be invited for dialogue, children who are incapable of decision-making should also be represented adequately.

Cowden (2012) argues that children are often sidelined from making decisions because sometimes they are not knowledgeable about topics of discussion. As a solution to this, in the context of the Olympic Games, educating and training children, early enough, about their rights is a crucial factor to be considered (Waldron and Oberman, 2016). In a study conducted by Waldron and Oberman (2016) regarding how children aged 0 - 7 should be made aware of their rights in order to ensure full participation, 96% of respondents indicated that children should be made aware of their rights by the age of 11, while 64% identified 0-7 years as appropriate. This suggests that every child deserves to know their rights and to exercise them. In adapting this finding for this framework, I propose that children of all ages should be invited to participate in the decision-making process of the Olympic Games. An example of where children were successfully included in decision making processes is the case of Ireland, when children were strategically included in the policy process of the Irish government (Pinkerton, 2004). Consultations (interviews, focus groups) were done with an average of 800 to 2,500 children within the age range of three and above, in conjunction with strategic child leaders such as educationists, parents and child rights leaders. At the end of the interviews and consultations, a forum was also held for child participants, representatives and guardians to review the findings before the policies were finalized and published (Pinkerton,

2004). This example is a testament to the fact that child participation is possible when there is a will, regardless of perception about perceived level of understanding and age (Nigel,2002).

Based on this, I, argue that children aged 10 – 17 are capable of being involved in decision making processes. However, they need to be educated about their rights first (Sher, 2001), and then approached directly by the Olympic Games event owners, stakeholders and relevant child rights NGO for interviews and focus groups discussions to get their opinions on the Olympic Games and how they might be adequately protected. This can also be done in alliance with educationists, teachers and coaches (Shier, 2001). After these interviews, consultations and focus groups have been conducted, children should also be invited to sit alongside adults to discuss the findings of the consultation process while jointly determining what should go into the policies (Host City Contract). In addition to this, as proposed by Knowles-Yáñez (2005), in developing the HCC, the JOC can also look at data available on existing child rights issues and feedback from reporting mechanisms to create protection policies for children in the Olympic Games. And finally, for children aged 0 – 9, in line with Chawla (2001), indirect involvement would work for them. This can be achieved by seeking the opinions of relevant representatives such as guardians and educationists.

8.5.3. Embedding child rights principles in policies guiding the Olympic Games

After recognizing children as right bearers, and involving them in decision making processes, I propose that the rights for protection and provision should be embedded in the principles and policies of the Olympic Games. Embedding, as argued by Al Hussein and Davis (2020), is the process of ensuring that the IOC's human rights commitment is driven across the organization, and into its values and culture. Having understood this, child rights principles and practices need

to be embedded in mega sporting events planning, to ensure that the threats towards children are exposed and mitigated appropriately (Aina et al. 2021). In the same way, this framework proposes that child rights need to be embedded in the policies and principles guiding the Olympic Games if they are to be leveraged effectively. The Tokyo 2020 Olympics recorded an absence of child rights specifics in the initial bid documents and principles guiding the Games. This is because there was no requirement to embed child rights commitments during the bidding and planning phases. If child rights in the Olympics are to be actualized, it is imperative that the IOC acts responsibly (Megheirkouni et al. 2022) by embedding a clearly defined child rights principles in the bidding and planning processes. Specifically, it is recommended that the IOC include clearly defined child rights principles in the Olympic Charter, as this would make it obligatory for prospective host cities to embed child right protection specifics in their bid documents such as the HCC and Sustainable plan documents. In addition, as noted by Al Hussein and Davis (2020) other than including child rights protection specifics, the IOC also need to embed child rights due diligence processes such as including child rights clauses in some contracts with sponsors and higher-risk business partners, as this would help the organization handle a wide range of existing child rights issues, as well as future ones in line with the UNCRC. In answering the question of how this can be implemented in practice and who retains the responsibility for the child rights considerations, Heerdt and Rook (2022) propose that the IOC creates an independent child rights advisory board, whose major duty would be to develop a tailored child rights policy for the Olympic Games, while also reforming the Olympic bidding process to include child rights standard just like FIFA ammended the bidding requirements for the 2026 tournament to include specific human rights standards, labour standards and risk assessment reports (Heerdt, 2018).

8.5.4. Monitoring child rights in the Olympic Games

Due to the lacuna between legal obligations to human rights and the actual situation, monitoring is an essential component of the international human rights system. Monitoring illuminates the situation of human rights commitments and ensures the relevancy of instruments (Collins, 2008). This framework proposes that after child rights have been embedded in policies and principles guiding the Olympic Games, the host cities, the organising committees and advocacy organizations need to keep checking the quality of the policies and keep the policies under systematic review before the Games delivery. The findings of this study alluded to the fact that embedding principles in policies is not the ultimate goal, there also must be people constantly monitoring the processes of child rights. This also corroborates McGillivray et al's (2019) argument that actions speak louder than words. Therefore, it is imperative that the IOC and the TOGOC set up respective independent monitoring committees (Grell, 2018) to actively review the effectiveness of child rights protection processes in the Olympic Games before, during and after each edition. These independent monitoring bodies should include child rights experts such as child rights advocates (Pinkerton, 2004) or independent bodies who are knowledgeable about children and how their rights can be upheld and represented adequately. To minimize potential conflicts of interest, the IOC members and representatives of other sports governing bodies should not have a seat on the monitoring board (Grell, 2018). To improve the child rights record of the Games, during the planning process, the independent monitoring body will need to ensure that child rights are addressed extensively in the host selection process.

8.5.5. Delivering child rights promises

Finally, delivery of child rights promises in the Olympic Games is as important as recognizing, involving, embedding and monitoring. Evidently, in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, there were no child rights promises made. However, as a remedy to this, the first four steps of this framework

(Recognize, Involve, Embed and Monitor) are proposed as important steps to take, if child rights promises are to be made and legalized in the principles and policies of future Olympic Games. If these steps are followed, and a holistic child rights provision for protection and participation strategies are developed in subsequent Olympic Games, there would then be a need for these promises to be delivered. As noted in the interview findings, respondents agreed that policies do not guarantee delivery. Therefore, building on step four (see section 8.5.4) which discussed the importance of monitoring child rights in the Olympic Games, it is being proposed in this final step of the framework that the same set of independent monitoring bodies be responsible for ensuring that every child rights promise made in the planning phase is delivered accordingly. In documenting how this might be achieved, Symonides (2018) proposed that after the bidding stage, the monitoring body should be responsible for monitoring and shaping the implementation of child rights by ensuring technical cooperation between the IOC and the host cities in delivering an Olympic Games that has a clearly defined child rights principle. And finally, according to Grell (2018), the role of these monitoring bodies should not necessarily have to be confined to monitoring and providing recommendations but should also include the power to directly impose sanctions in cases where child rights abuses occur.

8.6. Conclusion

This chapter has discussed, in-depth, the three main analytical themes that emerged from the literature review and the research findings. As evident from the findings, the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games had no clearly defined principles for child rights participation and provision for protection measures. I argue that this happened because there was nobody to take up leadership on child rights representation in policies. I also argue that the lack of intentionality about child rights can be attributed to the fact that children are currently not recognized as right bearers by the Olympics event owners (IOC) and other national stakeholders (JOC, in the context of Tokyo 2020).

In analyzing the findings, I discussed how it is important to foster greater recognition of child rights in the Olympic Games. I outlined how advocacy organizations can be change agents for child rights. Linking this with fostering child rights recognition in the Olympic Games, I argued that advocacy organizations are doing their best in ensuring that children do not take a back seat in the Olympics. More specifically, I noted how advocacy organizations stepped in by making provisions for children ahead of the Games. While some child rights organizations influenced the organising committees to develop policies to include child rights, some other NGOs organized workshops to call attention to the child rights issues in Japan. Because of HRW's published article, Japan abolished corporal punishments in the year 2020, ahead of the Olympic Games. I, however, argued that advocacy influence is only possible where there is no resistance. When resistance occurs so that change cannot be fostered, then renegotiation is necessary. I also argued that advocacy organizations should not be the only people responsible for child rights protection in the Olympic Games. There is a need for the IOC to take leadership of child rights, as this will yield more collaborative outcome from all stakeholders. Before the IOC can take the leadership, there has to be a change in the way the IOC perceives child rights. Specifically, there are two things that need to change. First, the IOC needs to come to the realisation that child rights violations in the Olympic Games is a problem that needs attention. Currently, there is no evidence that the IOC realises how much the Olympic Games infringe on child rights. Second, the IOC needs to pay more attention, show more care for children and their rights.

Finally, in a bid to add to knowledge in the field of child rights and fill the gap of how children might be adequately represented in the Olympic Games, I developed a framework – recognize, include, embed, monitor and deliver. As mentioned earlier, child rights seem to be an afterthought at mega sporting events. The proposed framework represents a holistic approach to delivering an Olympic Games from the perspective of child rights. Although there are different frameworks for

rights protection and participation models, there is no specific model for child rights protection in the Olympic Games. The framework developed in this research will help event owners and organizing committees to develop clearly defined child rights principles in subsequent Olympic Games editions.

9.0. CONCLUSION

In this chapter I conclude this research study. First, I return to the overall aims, objectives and research questions underpinning the study, addressing how each has been achieved. Following this, a brief summary of each chapter is presented. This is followed by an outline of the main findings of the study and its principal contribution to knowledge. Finally, study limitations and recommendations for further research are outlined.

9.1 Review of Study Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study was to assess child rights in mega sporting events, using Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as a case study. In achieving the aim of this study, the objectives were to (a) critically examine the policies and plans in place to protect and promote child rights in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, (b) evaluate the dimensions of child rights infringements associated with the Olympic Games in the context of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, (c) critically assess the measures in place to mitigate child rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games, (d) analyze the roles of key stakeholders in ensuring that the UN Convention on the Rights of Child is adhered to in the planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, and (e) analyze the level of child rights representations in Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games policies.

The study's research questions were designed to aid the process of addressing the objectives in order to achieve the overall aim of the study. Based on literature review and identified gaps in the field, three research questions were developed:

1. What are the dimensions of child rights infringements associated with the Olympic Games?
2. What measures are in place to mitigate children's rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games?

3. What are the roles of stakeholders, event organizers, advocacy organizations and event owners in ensuring that the Tokyo 2020 Games are delivered in compliance with the UNCRC?

All three research questions have been addressed using different qualitative methods. Research question one was addressed through empirical literature and semi structured interviews. Research two and three were addressed using a combination of semi structured interviews and documentary analysis. These methods were utilized under the umbrella of the case study approach.

This study aimed to contribute to literature and debates about child rights protection, child rights provision and child participation in decision making in the mega sporting event landscape in general and the Olympic Games specifically. To achieve this, the study explored the dimensions of child rights infringements as portrayed in literature, and the role of appropriate stakeholders in ensuring child rights protection drawing on the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games context.

9.2. Summary of Chapters

I have addressed the study aims and objectives by structuring the thesis as described below.

In chapter 1, the study commenced with the background for assessing child rights in mega sporting events. In addition to this, the chapter also briefly introduced the main subtopics of discussion – human rights, mega sporting events, child rights and their linkage with mega sporting events. The chapter also laid out the structure for the study. Before the discussion around mega sporting events and their linkage to human rights, there was a need to review general human rights principles. This was necessary because it offered a general understanding of human rights from different points of views and gave an insight into how human rights are perceived globally, coupled with human rights expectations widely.

Chapter two set out the debate around the definition of human rights and the schools of thought about it being an entitlement or a social construct. This chapter concluded that generally, all humans are entitled to their rights being upheld, however, in the context of sport, human rights were socially constructed, as they were constructed to fit into the world of sport. It was concluded that sport is a valuable human rights movement tool.

Following on from the human rights and sport discussion, establishing that sport is a tool for the human rights movement, chapter three focused on mega sporting events and their linkage with human rights. The chapter started with discussions about definitions and debates relating to mega sporting events. These included debates on the size and impact of mega sporting events on host communities. Linking these debates on size and impacts together, the chapter concluded that in defining mega sporting events, size, impacts and media coverage are key factors. It was also concluded that even though the Olympic Games hold values that support the human rights movement, human rights still get infringed upon. This, it was suggested, can be mitigated by ensuring that bidding to host the Olympic Games is done through the lens of human rights and child rights, as issues of child rights infringement in the Olympics have also been prevalent in the past 20 years.

To conceptualize child rights, chapter four focused on child rights in the Olympic Games, and how child rights protections have been conceptualized in the literature. There was a discussion of two relevant conceptual frameworks that informed the remainder of the study. First, McGillivray, et al.'s (2019) concept for leveraging human rights in sporting events and, second, Lundy's (2007) model of participation were explained. Before outlining the models and frameworks that form the conceptual basis of this study, the study discussed child rights in the concept of the Olympic Games, while highlighting the principles of the UNCRC and examples of child rights infringement

in the Olympics. Finally, the chapter established that the IOC has a role to play in upholding the rights of children in the Olympic Games.

Chapter five discussed the methodology and methods adopted to address the study research questions. The research questions were to: (a) discover what the dimensions of child rights in the Olympic Games are (b) find out what measures were in place to mitigate child rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, and (c) what the roles of stakeholder, event organizers, advocacy organizations and event owners are in ensuring that the Tokyo 2020 Games are delivered in compliance with the UNCRC. First, the chapter provided a rationale for the research philosophy adopted for this study – the epistemological philosophy before stating the research strategies and methodologies. As stated in this chapter, this is a qualitative research study. In order to address the three research questions, document analysis was conducted on documents and policies in place for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. In addition to this, interviews were conducted with stakeholders and NGO affiliates. The single case study approach was adopted for this study because this study aimed to do an in-depth study on a specific group of people (children) in a particular setting (Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games). Finally, this chapter documented the analytic process for the data.

The qualitative findings of this study were documented in chapters six and seven, while the analysis was presented in chapter eight. Bid documents of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games and the interviews conducted were analyzed thematically. Building upon McGillivray et al (2019), Lundy (2007) and the UNCRC, an in-depth analysis was carried out to assess child rights in mega sporting events from the perspective of provision and participation, using Tokyo 2020 as a case study. These conceptual frameworks also influenced how the documentary analysis and semi-

structured interviews for this study were carried out. As the study unfolded, the findings filled the gaps that had been identified in the literature review about past Olympic Games.

9.4. Main study findings

There were no mentions of child rights in the initial bid documents presented by Tokyo to the IOC. After the bid was won, specifically two years (2018, 2019) before the Tokyo 2020 Games delivery, child rights were mentioned in two documents (the JHRCP and the sustainability plan document (Tokyo 2020 Sustainable sourcing code, 3rd edition). However, in addition to the fact that these were an afterthought, the child rights measures in the documents were not clearly defined, as both documents only focused on child labour. While it was good that the bid documents (both the IOC and host city) had child participation strategies, it was also discovered that the documents only had measures for physical participation. Using Lundy's (2007) model for participation, other aspects of participation such as space, inclusion, voice and audience were missing in the participation strategies and decision-making processes.

Second, answering research question number one which was to evaluate the dimension of child rights infringement in the Tokyo 2020 Olympics. Using empirical literatures, it was discovered that child rights violations in general mega sporting events can be in the form of physical or mental abuse, harassment, and trafficking. However, in the context of Tokyo, through the semi structured interviews conducted, it was discovered that the stakeholders were concerned about child labour, trafficking and corporal punishments of child athletes. These were their major concerns because these child rights issues had pre-existed in Tokyo, Japan before winning the bid to host the Olympic Games.

Third, answering research question two which was to measure the provisions in place to mitigate child rights from being infringed at the Tokyo 2020 Games, through document examinations of

the Tokyo 2020 bid documents and policies, it was found that there were little to no measures in place to mitigate child rights from being infringed in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Specifically, the Olympic event owners and the local organising committees did not provide adequate protection mechanisms for the Games, as evident in their omission from Tokyo 2020 bid documents and policies. In addition, the study, through interviews with key stakeholders, demonstrated that there were no functional provisions in place – hotlines were not functional nor child friendly, nor did they have data retention ability. In addition, there were promises of Safe Sport Centre before the Olympic Games which were not delivered. After the Games were delivered, it was discovered that this safe space was not developed, neither were there other mechanisms in place to protect child rights before, during and after the Games. The study, however, found that independent NGOs had provided reporting mechanisms for children before and during the Games. This supports Bloodgood's (2011) claim that advocacy organizations can provide solutions to some issues that the government cannot immediately provide

Fourth, the IOC failed to provide effective leadership in ensuring that child rights were protected in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games as there were no mentions of the UNCRC or children in the Olympic Charter. Despite the powers it possesses, the IOC did not make it obligatory for host cities to make provisions for child rights in the planning or delivery of their premier event. Study respondents believed the IOC should have taken the leadership in ensuring that child rights were protected. Furthermore, the JOC also did not play any role in ensuring that the UNCRC was adhered to in the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Evidence suggests that NGOs played a leading role in ensuring that child rights were protected. Even though there was a limit to what could be achieved based on the ownership structure of the Olympic Games, some NGOs managed to influence some changes in the policy of the Games. This addressed research question three. For subsequent Olympic Games, this might mean that NGOs might put more pressure on the IOC and

NOC to take the leadership role for child rights. This is because, from a legal perspective (see Talbot, 2022), the IOC can achieve more success in the context of child rights protection in the Olympic Games. Also, on the other hand, if NGOs are not able to influence change to the IOC's current stance on child rights (minimal involvement), advocacy organizations might continue to provide solutions (Bloodgood, 2011). However, this raises the question of how sustainable the provisions might be, because like I argued earlier, advocacy organizations can try to influence changes to policies, however, if there is no commitment from the IOC or the NOC, there will be no legal remedy, or sustainable remedy for violations of child rights.

Finally, in relation to governance arrangements including transparency, responsiveness, and accountability, it was found that the Japanese government only embraced accountability and responded after NGOs revealed that there were no measures for child rights protection in Japan, in advance of the Tokyo 2020 Games. The Japanese government provided an independent document stating their stance on child rights and its protection, while also promising that they would do their best to ensure that children were protected. However, in this aspect of inclusion and democratization, the study findings suggest that children were not at any point included in the decision processes of the Games. In the context of formalization, as mentioned earlier, formalization of child rights in the policies were afterthought. Finally, in the context of management plan, there was evidence that the Tokyo 2020 Games organising committee aimed to avoid child labour while building infrastructures for the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Also, this was only added to the Tokyo 2020 sustainable plan after the United Nations dialogued with the IOC.

Before the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, there was little attempt to implement the UNCRC in the policies and principles guiding the Olympic Games. This was also the same for the Tokyo 2020

Games. A close look at the Paris 2024 Olympic Games also suggests similar neglect of child rights specifics. Paris 2024, through their #stayactive initiative encourages child physical participation while leaving out the other models of participation such as voice and audience, as proposed by Lundy (2007). In addition, while the Olympic Games seem well established in their participation strategies, there continue to be little or no mechanisms for protection for child participants – both elite participants and volunteers and for children who might be directly or indirectly affected by the Olympic Games. Third, the lack of intentionality about child rights in the Olympic Games can be traced to a lack of leadership for child rights. Fourth, even though advocacy organizations have stepped in to fill in the gaps in how host cities and organising committees of the Olympic Games, there is a limitation to how much the advocacy organizations can deliver. This is because, sometimes, advocacy organizations must collaborate with children’s primary guardians, governments and organising committees as regards children and their rights. Furthermore, findings and evidence showed that the hierarchical structure and culture of the Japanese system made it so that children were not able to speak up in the Tokyo 2020 Games. This, I argue, is one of the reasons why voice, audience were missing in the Toyo 2020 Games.

9.5. Contributions to knowledge

The previous sections in this chapter have outlined the ways through which this study was conducted. To reiterate, the aim of this study was to address child rights in mega sporting events, using Tokyo 2020 as a case study. This study makes a clear contribution to knowledge by providing a new way (single case study approach and documentary analysis method) to assess child rights in the Olympic Games.

This study also contributes to the wider debates around child rights and mega sporting events. While child rights have been previously assessed in the context of mega sporting events (see Donnelly, 2008, Dowse et al., 2018), with discoveries confirming that child rights indeed get violated in mega sporting events, and that there is a certain level of non-intentionality about child rights in mega sporting events. There, however, remains a considerable gap as to why child rights continue to be neglected in the Olympic Games and a holistic framework to delivering an Olympic Game from a child rights perspective. In summary, current literature tells us that child rights being neglected in mega sporting events is a recurring phenomenon but does not tell us why this is so and what can be done to stop this from being an issue in future Olympic Games. Even though recent studies have addressed why child rights are not a priority in the Olympic Games delivery (see Aina et al. 2021, Lang, 2022), these discoveries do not tell us the principal cause of this intentionality. This research makes a contribution by addressing these gaps and producing a study that enables a robust understanding of child rights in the Olympic Games.

Given the discoveries from interviews conducted and documents examined, I have highlighted that the Olympic Games is one mega sporting event that lacks child rights leadership, which reflected on how child rights protection and provisions were addressed before, during and after the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Building on this, I argue that child rights continue to be infringed in the Olympic Games, first, because child rights measures are not embedded in the policies and principles of the Olympic Games and, consequently, because child rights are not embedded in the policies, host cities are not obligated to consider child rights in their delivery of the Olympic Games. Second, I argue that child rights principles are not embedded in the policies and principles of the Olympic Games because the event owners and local organising committees do not consider children as right bearers. I also argue that this is also one of the principal reasons why children were not involved in the decision-making processes of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. In this

regard, there is a need for children to be considered as right bearers by the Olympic Games leadership and host cities so that child rights can be adequately provided for, in the Olympic Games.

Secondly, McGillivray et al (2019) and Lundy (2007) argue that there are major factors to consider in delivering mega sporting events from a child rights perspective. These pathways focused on the importance of provisions (this could be in form of governance structures and other protection mechanisms, formalization in policies), protection (the roles of representatives such as parents, government, advocacy organizations), and participation (inclusion in decision making processes). I added and went beyond these concepts to make an original contribution to knowledge by arguing that beyond the three P's, other factors must be considered to realistically deliver mega sporting events from a child rights perspective. This is evident in my contribution to the academic field and knowledge exchange. In an article led by me, titled *Embedding child rights principles and practices in mega sporting events planning*, I suggested that embedding child rights principles and values in specific terms in the policies of the Olympic Games is a key step to bringing a permanent change to child rights violation challenges. I also suggested that in addition to embedding child rights principles in policies, there is also a need for sustainability in the plans towards acting out the embedded principles. Furthermore, in a book chapter I substantially contributed to, around the wider issues of disability and events, I also brought to fore the dimensions of violations faced by vulnerable groups when events are hosted. In this book chapter, I also proposed policy-precedence for marginalized and vulnerable groups, right from the bidding stage.

And finally, In the bidding and planning of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games, which ended up being postponed for a year, there were no tangible plans to protect and promote child rights, and the Games were not delivered from a child rights perspective. In order to make it easier for future

Olympic Games to be delivered from a child right perspective, this research has made a clear contribution by developing a child rights framework for delivering an Olympic Games from a child rights perspective. This framework, *Recognize, Involve, Embed, Monitor, Deliver* is a holistic conceptual framework of how child rights can be upheld, represented and delivered in the Olympic Games. This framework is a conceptual contribution to literature as regards child rights. The framework provides an understanding for how child rights might be addressed both in the context of sporting events, and in the context of child rights in other sectors. In summary, the framework suggests that for the Olympic Games to be delivered from a child rights perspective, children must be recognized as right bearers; children must be involved in the decision-making processes (either directly or by representation); a clearly defined child rights principle must be embedded in the policies of the Olympic Games; child rights must be continuously monitored by an independent monitoring body, and finally; child rights promises must be enforced and delivered. This conceptual model will particularly benefit the IOC, NGOs, and future Olympic Games host cities, as this model can be translated into guidance for event owners and host organizers' policies in advance of the Olympic Games. This model, when applied, will help future researchers in determining if subsequent mega sporting events have been planned and delivered from a child rights perspective. In practice, this model covers the three P's of child rights – provision, participation and protection, and provides practical ways of applying each step in real life scenarios. To ensure that this model is disseminated appropriately, this model will be submitted for peer review, and published in journals. In addition, my career trajectory is tilted towards taking up policy roles at UNICEF or Centre for Sports and Human Rights where I can help influence child rights policies more directly, and also continue to help implement my model.

9.6. Study Limitations

The limitations of this study lie, among other things, in the number of interviews conducted, as mentioned in chapter four. Based on the sensitivity of the subject of discussion, prospective interviewees withdrew from the interview process. Also, considering that the interviews were conducted shortly before the delivery of the Games, stakeholders whose contributions would have impacted this study more were either too busy to be interviewed or unapproachable. This can also be attributed to the prevailing COVID-19 situation, at the time.

The COVID-19 pandemic also meant that I could not travel to Japan to observe, as planned. This affected the study as I was unable to observe, gather my data to get firsthand information about the child rights situation in Tokyo before and during the Tokyo 2020 Games. Generally, it has been highlighted that COVID-19 impacted researchers' ability to conduct primary fieldwork, as researchers had to make changes to ethnographic fieldwork by switching to remote approaches (Watson and Lupton, 2022). This was my reality. I had to switch to remote approaches (video, call, email interviews and document examination). Even though this was a hindrance in some way, it was cost effective and allowed me make connections beyond my geographical location from the comfort of my home. While this was a blessing in itself, it also came with the pain of having to deal with connection issues, time difference and language barriers without a ready interpreter. Some interviews had to be rescheduled because of this.

Lastly, prior research studies that have been conducted in relation to this study are limited. No prior research of this kind (looking at policies to assess child rights in the Olympic Games from the point of view of participation, provision, protection) has been conducted. This limited the literature I could consult and use in the review and analysis.

9.7. Future Research

In addition to the recommended framework, it is recommended that future studies and researchers focusing on child rights should give thoughts to approaching it from a holistic perspective. This might include adopting a participant observation or ethnographic methodology to produce an added child centred viewpoint. To achieve this, there might also be a need to liaise with child-centred organizations and a utilization of child friendly research approaches. Further researchers can also benefit from considering drawing on past and future Olympic Games editions so that continuities and discontinuities can be more effectively contextualized.

I also propose that further research be conducted, working with advocacy organizations, to understand a deeper dimension of child rights violations in mega sporting events. Currently, there is a body of work being done by advocacy organizations in evaluating child rights violations, whereas there are limited studies on this by researchers. There is a need for a better understanding of the extent of these violations, and what they mean for mega sporting events delivery. Therefore, I propose that both NGOs and researchers collaborate to academically evaluate the scale of child rights violations such as trafficking and child labour, and how they should be captured in the context of the Olympic Games.

This study has demonstrated that child rights are yet to make meaningful progress in the context of planning, organization, delivery and leadership of the Olympic Games, as there continues to be different dimensions of violations to children and their rights. There also continues to be a nonchalance to the recurring issues of child rights infringements in each Olympic Games. Moreso, there has there been no concrete commitment towards safeguarding children and their rights from being violated. Recently, the IOC provided some human rights objectives for 2024. These objectives would include an ammendment of the OC and an inclusion of some set of principles for the management of human rights. In addition to this, the IOC has also shown commitments to

respect human rights in line with the UNGDPHR, and also made promises to include human rights requirements for cities bidding to host the Olympic Games (IOC, 2022). These are moves in the right direction, however, child rights has, yet again, been overlooked.

In sum, child rights need to be placed higher on the agenda of researchers, organizations and event owners to ensure that, in the future, children and their rights are respected, protected and promoted in the context of hosting future mega sporting events.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 - Participant information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Assessing child rights in mega sporting events: Tokyo 2020 Olympics and Paralympics as case study

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear, or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research is concerned with the activity surrounding the Olympics. The aim of this research is to analyze the mechanisms through which children's rights are being protected and provided for, drawing on the context of the 2020 Tokyo Olympics and Paralympic Games. To achieve this, the researcher will examine the extent of policies and plans in place to protect and promote child rights for the Tokyo 2020 Olympics and Paralympic Games by conducting interviews and analysing policies and principles in place for the Tokyo 2020 Games.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a key stakeholder in the field of Child Rights and mega sporting events; as such, your views are of interest to the researcher and this study.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this

information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. Please know that should you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

We would like you to take part in a one on one interview regarding your involvement, views or experience as regards child rights infringement and upholding in the Olympics, Specifically Tokyo 2020 Olympics. If you agree to participate, the principal researcher will e-mail you asking for your availability. Depending on your availability, you will be asked to participate in one semi-structured interview which will take place through skype or one to one, or email, depending on your choice of communication medium. If one to one, or skype interview is your preferred choice, the interview will last for approximately 30-45 minutes and you will be asked various questions that either highlights your experience in the Olympics host city, and the role you or your Organisation is playing to ensure that child rights are being protected in the 2020 Tokyo Olympics. The interview will be audio-recorded and, your name will be included in the write-up of the interview or any resultant studies. The audio-recordings will be transferred from the audio-recording device to a password protected hard-drive, while all information sheets and transcripts will be kept in a locked drawer, within a locked room. All information collected from you will be stored, analyzed and reported in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2018). No personal details about yourself will be required. The data will be kept for 10 years following the completion of the study, after which it will be destroyed.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no possible risks or disadvantages of taking part in this study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The research will add to the limited literature regarding the assessment of child rights in the Tokyo 2020 Olympics.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at [REDACTED] UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at [REDACTED]

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. We will not anonymize or pseudonyms the personal data you provide as they are already public knowledge.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at [REDACTED] If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information

Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details and details of data subject rights are available on the ICO website at <https://ico.org.uk/for-organizations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Detail any intended recipients of personal data if not explained elsewhere, and also advise if any personal data will be transferred outside the EEA, and if so to where.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the interview will form part of a study which will inform subsequent research within the Ph.D. project. In addition, this data will be written up as part of a University of the West of Scotland Ph.D. thesis and may be presented at academic conferences or submitted to peer review journals.

Who has reviewed the study?

MCS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher Name: Oluwaseyi Aina

The University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor Name: David McGillivray

The University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you

Appendix 2 - Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Assessing Child Right in mega sporting events: Tokyo 2020 Olympics and Paralympics as case study.

Ethics Approval Number: [REDACTED]

Investigator(s): Oluwaseyi Aina [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information (*provide information on what personal information specifically will be collected*) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

Initials

I agree to having my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

Appendix 3 – Summary of Child rights protection Framework

Appendix 4 – Olympic Governance Structure

